

**Implementation of sustainable supply chain management
in UK SMEs in construction industry**

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ABSTRACT

This research explores how UK construction companies in the SME sector implement sustainability practices into their supply chain management. The objectives of the research are to conduct comprehensive literature review on supply chain management, sustainability, sustainable supply chain management, implementation processes, theories and concept of SMEs; to investigate the key drivers to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully in UK SMEs in the construction industry; to examine the implementation process of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in the construction industry; to understand the barriers that UK SMEs in the construction industry face during the implementation of sustainable supply chain management and to make recommendations that can be utilised by UK SMEs in the construction industry to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully.

A literature review was conducted from a broader topic as supply chain and narrowed it down for sustainable supply chain management implementation with the aim of providing an understanding for the readers about the importance of interlinked fields. The literature review of existing literature addressing sustainable supply chain management implementation was carried out in order to identify the gaps in the literature such as drivers to implement sustainable supply chain management, implementation process of sustainable supply chain management and barriers to implement sustainable supply chain management. In order to fill these identified research gaps, a qualitative research methodology was adopted. The data was collect through semi-structured, multi-respondent and in-depth interviews in five case studies of SMEs in the construction industry. The data was analysed thematically by using the NVIVO qualitative data analysis software.

The findings indicate that SMEs develop the motivation to implement sustainable supply chain management mainly as a result of top management commitment. The identified implementation process has seven steps and demonstrates the resources that can be used in each step in order to achieve success in the implementation. Furthermore, the research identified the barriers to implement sustainable supply chain management in SMEs that lead the companies to find solution and succeed in the implementation.

The thesis provides literature to fill in the identified gaps and a conceptual model that can be used by the academics as its theoretical contribution. The practical contribution of the thesis is a SSCM implementation process and practical guidance to overcome from the potential barriers to implement SSCM successfully by using identified resources.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AICPA – American Institute of Certified Public Accountants

BREEAM – Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method

CEEQUAL – The Civil Engineering Environmental Quality Assessment and Awards Scheme

CICA – Canadian Institute of Chartered Accountants

CIMA – Chartered Institute of Management Accountants

EMS – Environmental Management System

FORS – Fleet Operator Recognition Scheme

FSC - Forest Stewardship Council

RBV – Resource Based View

SME – Small and Medium Sized

SCM – Supply Chain Management

SSC – Sustainable Supply Chain

SSCM – Sustainable Supply Chain Management

UK – United Kingdom

UN – United Nations

WCED – World Commission on Environment and Development

WRAP – Waste and Resource Action Programme

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background

A supply chain is a diverse connection network of activities, businesses, relations, individuals and technologies (Ahmed, 2017; Carter, Rogers and Choi, 2015). These connection networks have to be legally separated businesses (two or more organisations) that pass the materials forward, linked by information and financial flows (Stadtler, 2015). The ultimate goal of a supply chain is transforming an unprocessed raw material into a finished product that can be used by a final customer (Vitasek, 2013). The final customer should be satisfied with the entire stages of supply chain which begins with the supplier and passes through the production, distribution and retailing (Syed, 2012). According to Kot (2018) the functioning of a supply chain of an organisation is measured through the impact of it on social system, environment and through the profitability of the business. The efficient management of supply chain is crucial to be successful in the competitive construction industry (Papadopoulos *et al.*, 2016; Butkovic, Kauric and Mikulic, 2016).

The phenomenon of business focused supply chain management (SCM) started in late 1990s and gradually evolved through the development of information technology capability and global competition (Min, Zacharia and Smith, 2019). Then in 2010s, researchers and the SCM practitioners have become more interested in SCM as they find it as an important element to achieve the competitiveness of their organisations' supply chains (Ageron, Gunasekaran and Spalanzani, 2012) and as a result the SCM began to develop continuously by generating more opportunities for them to study and develop knowledge based on issues that are important to service providers, customers and organisations (Stock, Boyer and Harmon, 2010). The definition of SCM is diverse as a result of practitioners' and researchers' attempts to introduce a better description, explanation and prediction for the SCM phenomenon. One definition for SCM is that, it is a systemic, strategic management of the traditional business activities and the procedures across these business activities within a particular organisation and across businesses within the supply chain in order to improve the performance of the organisation and whole supply chain (Min *et al.*, 2019). Another definition is that, it is an important business strategy that enhances competitiveness of enterprises as a result of the practitioners' knowledge and enhanced interest in SCM (Simamora, Aiman and Subiyanto, 2015). Likewise, there are few

other definitions mentioned in the literature review chapter (chapter 2; section 2.3.1 overview) of the current study. The effective SCM is a significant way of achieving competitive advantage and advancing organisational performance as the competition is between the supply chains and not among the organisations (Syed, 2012). Yet, according to the researcher's understanding the competition among the organisations develop with the sustainability integration to the business strategy.

The concept of sustainability started to gain attention with the incorporation of social, environmental and economic concerns into business strategies (Sajjad, 2015). Global and national organisations practice sustainability in order to achieve competitive advantage and to improve stakeholder value. The literature has defined the term sustainability in several ways (Bruno, 2018). Hence, defining the sustainability concept is not direct. As examples; according to Starik and Rands (1995 cited in Carter and Rogers, 2008) sustainability is the organisation's ability as an individual organisation or as a collection of organisations, to exist for a prolonged period and grow; according to Chin, Tat and Sulaiman (2015) sustainability as a business strategy closely relates to corporate social responsibility; according to Carter and Rogers (2008) sustainability refers to the integration of social, environmental and economic responsibilities of an organisation in order to accomplish long-term economic validity. Although there are several definitions for sustainability, Bruno (2018) considered the definition by World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) as the widely used definition. It defines sustainability as *"a development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs"* (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987: 41). But WCED's definition is confusing as it does not clearly mention how organisations are involved in the process and what roles they need to play in order to promote the principles and goals of sustainability (Sajjad, 2015). Somehow, the chief executive of an organisation should make sustainability as the priority of the organisation (United Nations Global Compact (UN Global Compact), 2019). More importantly, organisations should make efforts to set targets and standards in sustainability (Lu, 2017).

Sustainable supply chain (SSC) or in other words supply chain sustainability is the intersection between the sustainable development and supply chain (Ni and Sun, 2018). It is an important characteristic of an organisation that helps to be sustainable (persist for a prolonged period of

time and grow). The reason behind this situation is that the positive perception of the stakeholders (customers, employers, employees, suppliers etc) regarding the integration of social, economic and environmental concerns into the supply chain system. Consequently, if the SSC is not managed properly within an organisation, the organisation it-self might not be sustainable in the long run.

According to Meixell and Luoma (2015), sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) broadens the concept of SCM by improving the performance of three sustainability dimensions (environmental, social and economic dimensions). Similarly, Svensson (2007) explains that the SSCM expands the approach of SCM by emphasising social, environmental (ecological) and economic aspects of business practices and theories such as corporate social responsibility. Sajjad and Eweje (2013: 58) view “*SSCM as an interdisciplinary approach which integrates sustainability and SCM disciplines to accomplish sustainable business outcomes for the entire supply chain partners*” including manufacturers, consumers, organisations governing over the supply chain and other stakeholders such as shareholders. SSCM is also defined as the designing, coordinating, organising and controlling of a supply chain in order to become accurately sustainable and to generate profit without making any adverse impact on the environmental and social systems (Pagell and Shevchenko, 2014). The actions that include the correlations between the components and relations in a supply chain are also called as SSCM (Kot, 2018). These actions aim to achieve sustainable development of an organisation through economic, environment and social activities. The achievement of SSCM represents the supply chain members’ attempt towards the incorporation of SSCM into the traditional supply chain of an organisation (Roy, 2018). In the current study, SSCM is defined as the integration of environmental concerns into the supply chain in order to achieve the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generation to meet their own needs. The reason to include only environmental concerns is explained in section ‘1.2 Rationale’.

Additionally, sustainability integration in supply chain management has impacts on reduction of environmental issues (Alzawawi, 2014). Climate change, waste generation, rising carbon emissions and resource scarcity are the environmental issue across the globe (Dadhich *et al.*, 2015). Any organisation that has a supply chain of raw materials, uses packaging, produces waste or consumes water and energy contributes for the environmental issues (Waste and

Resource Action Programme (WRAP), 2015). In fact, the environmental issues are developing with the increasing building needs of the human being as they attempt to have a civilized life (Yilmaz and Bakis, 2015). The reason behind the development of the environmental issues is that the excess amount of constructions, demolitions and maintenances that require to fulfil the building needs of the human being. These buildings use multiple resources and larger amount of energy that affects the quality of water and air which then leads to climate change (Vyas, Ahmed and Parashar, 2014). Further, the pollution caused with waste is a vital environment issue (Alzawawi, 2014). In the year 2017, 100 millions of waste was produced by the construction industry and only 20% of that waste was recycled (Alwan, Jones and Holgate, 2017). These environmental issues can be controlled and improved through an environmental management system (WRAP, 2015). An environmental management system (EMS) is a strategic approach to manage the impacts on the environment.

A small and medium enterprise (SME) can be defined with the number of employees, turnover, assets and equity as it does not have a single and a simple definition (Syed, 2012). According to European Commission (n.d.), SMEs are the enterprises which employee fewer than 250 people, which acquire an annual turnover not more than 50 million euro or/and annual balance sheet total not exceeding 43 million euro. SMEs are not only the small versions of larger organisations (Kechiche and Soparnot, 2012) but also they play a major role development of global as well as national economies (Kot, 2018; Chin *et al.* 2012).

In the UK, nearly fifth of the SMEs come under construction industry (Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy, 2018). Construction industry manages projects that require efficient and effective use of machinery, materials, human resources and technology (Salami, Aydinli and Laptalioral, 2016). The SMEs in the UK construction industry that manage projects have to follow the environmental targets set by the UK government (Alwan *et al.*, 2017). In 2019, UK government have become the first major economy in the world to pass laws to achieve overall net zero carbon emission by 2050 (Committee on Climate Change, 2020; HM Treasury, 2020). This is in addition to the most ambitious target set-out for all new commercial and domestic buildings to be net zero carbon. In the current study, the researcher did not gather data about these government environment targets as it is the researcher's intention to focus primarily on the implementation process of the SSCM.

Apart from these government targets, UK construction industry needs to concentrate on the sustainability issues such as pollution as a negative impact of generated waste (Alwan *et al.*, 2017) for the reason that in the year 2016, UK construction and demolition waste generation was 66.2 million tonnes (Department for Environment Food and Rural Affairs, 2019). UK construction industry use recovery and landfills as two major waste treatments (Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs, 2019; Alwan *et al.*, 2017). In England, there are more than 1200 landfills in coastal areas having implications effect on the climate change and pollute the ecosystem (Brand *et al.*, 2017). In order to reduce waste disorganisations, the UK government charges have amended a ‘Landfill Tax Legislation’ where the government charges £94.15 from the construction organisation for the wastes ending up in the landfills (HM Revenue and Customs, 2018). However, this policy increases the prices of the buildings as the construction organisations charge this amount from the customers and as a result efficiency of the environmental reduces (Alwan *et al.*, 2017). Yet, having an EMS helps an organisation to identify opportunities to reduce waste going to landfill and manage the legal compliance (WRAP, 2015).

1.2 Rationale

It is important to understand the interlinked fields of the SSCM in order to achieve sustainable business development (Reefke and Sundaram, 2017). According to Gurzawska (2019), supply chains of the organisations grow and become complex as a result of economic globalisation which makes SCM a necessity. Significant portion of business profitability is generated through SC while integration of sustainability helps to achieve competitive advantage (Reefke and Sundaram, 2017). The literature review (chapter two) of this study aims to generate the understanding of SC, SCM, SSC and SSCM in order to demonstrate the importance of interlinked fields.

“Sustainable practices— whether in supply chain management or any other business activity— are a function of two conjoined principles: (1) they must enhance ecological health, follow ethical standards to further social justice, and improve economic vitality; and (2) they must be prioritised whereby the environment comes first, society second, and economics third” (Markman and Krause, 2016: 4). Accordingly, an organisation should maintain a balance

between three dimensions of sustainability concerns in order to achieve SSCM. Yet, environmental concern has to be the first priority among the three dimensions. Recently, academic researchers have been given more importance to the studies related to SSCM as a result of its importance on organisation's responsibility (Paingrahi, Bahinipati and Jain, 2018). Specifically, the environment perspective of sustainability is an important research area in SSCM. The reason to mention the environment perspective of sustainability as a critical research area is that the decisions made by the supply chain managers in relation to environment without sufficient information which gives rise to adoption of common assumptions such as maximise customer satisfaction while minimising the cost and which gives rise to adoption of readily available rules for decision making (Wu and Pagell, 2011). According to Panigrahi, Bahinipati and Jain (2018), SSCM integration is an underdeveloped research area compared to some of the researches under environmental perspective of SSCM such as green packaging, distribution, warehousing and transportation (green packaging requires less storage space in warehouses and during transportation); carbon footprint reduction; reuse and recycle (it is an important element of green operations); environmental standards (ISO 14000, 14001) and eco-friendly technologies (environmental friendly technologies help to achieve pollution free production process). Therefore, the researcher of the current research study found that the implementation process of SSCM environmental perspective as another important research area that is currently underdeveloped.

The SME sector is an important business sector in the world in terms of environment, social and economic impacts they make (Kechiche and Soparnot, 2012). Specifically, European SMEs are essential drivers of change and innovation in Europe (Asare and Prempeh, 2016). In the 2018 and 2019, 99.9% UK businesses are SMEs (Rhodes, 2019; Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy, 2018). The SMEs are very important for the UK economy as they account for 38% of GDP (Fay, 2017). The SMEs' environmental impacts are significant where they require having improved environmental protection and sustainable development performance. Yet, publications of successful stories and practices in sustainability implementation are hardly found as most of the SMEs are privately owned organisations (Blackhurst, Cantor and O'Donneell, 2012). Also, SSCM studies in SMEs are currently underdeveloped or are largely ignored (Shibin *et al.*, 2017; Ashby, 2014). The current research study evidenced implementation of SSCM, in particular the environmental dimension of SSCM in the UK SMEs as important study area.

Among the 99.9% SME businesses, construction industrial businesses are the highest in terms of number of SME businesses (Rhodes, 2019; Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy, 2018). The UK construction industry restrains multifaceted supply networks that produce different end products over short time scales (Russell, Lee and Clift, 2018). Developers, investors, designers or architects, manufacturers, contractors, demolition experts and raw material suppliers are included in the multifaceted supply network of the construction industry. This multifaceted characteristic of the construction industry's supply chain multiplies the environment implications of a final outcome, from designing to completion of a project (Russell *et al.*, 2018; Balasubramanian and Shukla, 2018). The UK construction industry is a significant industry to promote sustainability in order to minimise the environmental impacts (Russell *et al.*, 2018). However, these three researchers mention that there is a structural issue in promotion of sustainability in the UK construction industry. Once again, the current research study verified that it is important to study the implementation process of SSCM specifically the environmental dimension of SSCM in the UK SMEs in the construction industry.

1.3 Research Gap

According to Kot (2018) there is a need to study the implementation of sustainable development concept in SCM in SMEs. The reason is the ignorance of SMEs when conducting SSCM studies. Although the interest in SSCM has increased, there is limited managerial and academic understanding on how companies integrate SSCM into the organisations (Sajjad, 2015). Specifically, frameworks and models of SSCM implementation presented in the literature is limited (Zimon, Tyan and Sroufe, 2019). Moreover, the SMEs may have diverse attitudes towards the SSCM implementation (Sajjad, 2015) which are not presented in the literature.

It is also necessary to study the drivers and barriers when implementing SSCM successfully. Sajjad (2015) justifies the importance of studying motivators and barriers to implement SSCM as there are few studies on this research area. Zaabi, Dhaheri and Diabat (2013) also supports this research gap by mentioning studying the barriers to implement SSCM as a research area that can be studied further as it is helpful for the SMEs. Therefore, the current study aims to fill these literature gaps of implementation process, drivers and barriers and make a theoretical

contribution to the environment aspect of SSCM while developing a new insight into implementation of SSCM in the UK construction SMEs.

1.4 Research Aim

This study aims to make recommendations to UK SMEs in the construction industry to be able to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully.

1.5 Research Objectives

The research objectives are identified in order to achieve the main research aim. Those objectives are as follow;

1. To conduct comprehensive literature review on supply chain, supply chain management, sustainability, sustainable supply chain, sustainable supply chain management, implementation processes, theories and concept of SMEs.
2. To investigate the key drivers to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully in UK SMEs in the construction industry.
3. To examine the implementation process of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in the construction industry.
4. To understand the barriers that UK SMEs in the construction industry face during the implementation of sustainable supply chain management.
5. To make recommendations that can be utilised by UK SMEs in the construction industry to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully.

1.6 Research Contributions

According to the Quality Assurance Agency for UK Higher Education (QAA) (2020 & 2014), doctorate theses make contribution to existing knowledge and professional practice. Baptista *et al.* (2015) agrees with this statement and mentions that the doctoral theses are expected to make significant theoretical and innovative practical contributions to the study area. These significant contributions must be original, creative and relevant to the field.

The current research study achieves quality of a doctoral thesis by providing a theoretical contribution and a practical contribution. The theoretical contribution is a novel conceptual model that can be published and critiqued by other academics. Also, the thesis provides literature that fills the identified literature gaps in the current research study. As examples it presents the drivers to implement SSCM, the process that needs to be followed when implementing SSCM and the possible barriers that needs to be addressed in order to implement SSCM successfully.

The practical contribution is a SSCM implementation process with guidance to overcome the barriers to implement the process and to select relevant resources in order to implement the process successfully. The limitation of managerial understanding on how companies integrate SSCM into the organisations can be eliminated through the practical contribution of the current research study.

1.7 Research Methodology

The current research study is based on the qualitative data obtained out of the semi-structured questionnaires. Multiple case studies were used from a self selected sample to collect the cross-sectional qualitative data. The researcher of the current research study analysed these data thematically by using the NVIVO data analysis software.

1.8 Thesis Structure

(Source: Compiled by the author)

Figure 1 summarises the structure of this particular thesis. It is organised with seven chapters namely introduction (the current chapter), literature review (chapter two), methodology (chapter three), case studies (chapter four), analysis (chapter five), findings and discussion (chapter six) and conclusion (chapter seven).

The current chapter (introduction chapter) chapter introduces the research topic and the key concepts. The first section of this introduction chapter provides the background of the study while defining the key concepts that are helpful to build a general idea about the research topic.

In the second section justifications are provided through literature to highlight why this study is important. Then the third section mentions the research gaps that are presented in the literature. The fourth and fifth sections outline the research aim and the objectives of this particular study. This follows penultimate section that includes an overview of the research methodology. In the final section the structure of this research is presented. The content of the introduction chapter develops this research thesis's direction towards the literature review chapter, methodology chapter and conclusion chapter.

The literature review chapter (chapter two) develops the current research study based on the existing literature. These existing literatures are presented in a critical synthesis and arranged relevant to the subheadings. At the end of the literature review chapter a conceptual framework is developed and accordingly a semi-structured questionnaire was developed to collect data. The literature review aimed to achieve the first objective (to conduct comprehensive literature review on supply chain management, sustainability, sustainable supply chain management, implementation processes, theories and concept of SMEs) of the current study.

The research methodology chapter (chapter three) provides details about the systematically designed research method that was adopted in the study of the implementation of sustainable supply chain management in the UK SME sector of the construction industry. The research methodology justifies the philosophical view that the researcher adopted in the current study. It also explains the dynamic research approaches and justifies the reason for adopting inductive research approach. Further, it discusses data collection techniques and data analysis techniques under the research design. In addition, the advantages and limitations of the adopted techniques are also discussed. Furthermore, the research methods are explained while justifying the reason for adopting qualitative research method. The respondents' valuable participation was helpful for the researcher to conduct a qualitative research and to make recommendations that can be utilised by the UK construction SMEs to successfully implement sustainable supply chain management practices and procedures.

The case studies chapter (chapter four) introduces the case studies by providing the backgrounds and the sustainability practices of them. All these information were collected from the company websites and from their annual reports. But, the researcher does not include any references in order to maintain the anonymity of the data and to abide by the UK data protection act 2018.

The next chapter is the analysis chapter (chapter five). The collected data are analysed by using NVIVO software. In order to develop a clear picture about the collected data, the important quotations from the respondents are mentioned and interpreted accordingly. This chapter aimed to achieve the second objective (to investigate the key drivers to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully in the UK SMEs in the construction industry), the third objective (to examine the implementation process of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in the construction industry) and the fourth objective (to understand the barriers that UK SMEs in the construction industry face in the implementation of sustainable supply chain management) of the current study.

The analysed qualitative data and the existing literature are used to develop the discussion (chapter six) of the current study. In-depth interpretations of the collected data are used to compare and contrast the information in the existing literature. The discussion chapter leads to the conclusion chapter.

The conclusion chapter is a combination of summary of the discussion, recommendations, contribution to the knowledge and directions for the future researches. This chapter aimed to achieve the final objective (to make recommendations that can be utilised by UK SMEs in the construction industry to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully) of the current study.

1.9 Summary of the Chapter

The introduction chapter has provided the background and definitions to the key concepts that relate to the current study area. The purpose to conduct the current study was presented through the rationale and research gap. This introduction chapter has mentioned the aim and objectives that need to be achieved. In addition, the research methodology that is planned to be used was also presented. Finally, the thesis structure is revealed. The next chapter (chapter two) provides logically arranged existing literature that relate to the current study.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

“The literature review is designed to demonstrate the researcher’s knowledge of a particular subject area, field and discipline” (Grant and Osanloo, 2014: 19).

In this particular literature review, the researcher aims to achieve the first objective of the research by conducting a comprehensive literature review. It generates the understanding of interlinked fields that relate to SSCM. The supply chain of an organisation significantly contributes to the sustainability and therefore the management of the supply chain (SCM) is important to initiate sustainability practices (Panigrahi *et al.*, 2018). The supply chain of an organisation is not capable of achieving the competitiveness without the integration of SSCM that increases the performance of the organisation (Santosa, 2015). Therefore, it is important for the readers to develop their understanding about the interlined fields and it is helpful to implement SSCM successfully.

This chapter commences with section 2.2 which covers concept of supply chain in general and in the construction industry. This section is followed by section 2.3 which reviews the existing literature on SCM which includes the objectives, impacts, enablers and barriers to implement SCM. The concept of sustainability, its dimensions and sustainability performance indicators are discussed in section 2.4. This section is followed by section 2.5 which defines sustainable supply chain and implementation of sustainable supply chain. Then, section 2.6 reviews SSCM which covers concept of SSCM, model of SSCM, dimensions of SSCM, impact of SSCM on organisations, implementation process of SSCM and external and internal enablers to implement SSCM. Section 2.7 discusses the concept of SME. Institutional theory and resource based view theory are reported in section 2.8 under the sub-title theories relating to sustainable supply chain management. Section 2.9 introduces the conceptual framework and concludes this chapter by providing a summary for the chapter.

The literature reviews of the sub-titles are organised from a broader perspective for the particular sub-title to a narrow down perspective that directly link to the main research topic. Brief overviews followed by diverse definitions for the key terms (supply chain, SCM, sustainability, sustainable supply chain, SSCM and SMEs) are provided in order to review the previous

definitions and to finalize definitions which are appropriated for the current study that help to maintain an equal understanding between the researcher and the readers.

2.2 Supply Chain

2.2.1 Overview

Different organisations in the supply chain, links between them, financial, flow, information flow and material flow are important points to be included when defining supply chain. Christopher (2011) illustrates a supply chain as an organisational network which involves upstream supplier and downstream distributor relations in different activities and processes that produce value added products and services delivered to final customers. This particular definition has included several points to gather without providing any explanations to them. As an example, it mentions about different activities between the suppliers and the distributors. Therefore, in the current study these activities are interpreted as financial, material and information flow between the main contractor and supplier. This interpretation becomes evident with Singh and Verma (2018) explanation of supply chain as a group of three or more organisations that directly involved in the upstream and downstream flows of finances, products, services and information.

The supply chain is also defined as a network that consists of ‘nodes’ and ‘links’. The ‘nodes’ are referred to as organisations with the ability to decide and maximise the organisations’ achievements within the constraints in which they operate and ‘links’ are referred to as the correlation between two nodes through transactions of finance, information and material flows (Carter *et al.*, 2015). This definition is much clearer than the Christopher’s definition. Yet, it could provide more clarification for finance, information and material flow. Syed (2012) fills this gap and mentions ‘financial flow’ involves payment schedules, credit terms, information about discounts etc, ‘information flow’ includes order transmit and delivery status update and finally ‘material flow’ in other words product flow is the movement of goods from suppliers to customers.

When it comes to the overview of the supply chain, the researcher finds it important to mention about the dimensions of the supply chain structure. By highlighting these dimensions, Alwaysheh and Klassen (2010) have conducted a study on incorporation of social issues in the management of supply chain. Here, they have included socially responsible purchasing and environmental

management in to the social issues of a supply chain. Therefore, the researcher categorises this article as relevant to the current research study where environmental management is one of the focal points. In this article, three dimensions of supply chain structure are discussed. They are namely transparency, dependency and distance. The transparency is the availability of the information to the end users and to the other organisations in the supply chain. It improves the awareness of stakeholders' on the decisions and activities of the organisation (Katenbayeva *et al.*, 2016). The supply chain information must be traceable in order to disclose or in other words to maintain transparency of the particular information. According to Awaysheh and Klassen (2010), the dependency means the reliability of an organisation on other organisations of the supply chain for capabilities, resources or components. The third dimension is the distance where the managers have to select local suppliers in order to reduce data gathering issues, assessment issues and implementation issues. Relatively to the current study, the transparency of construction material flow benefits in construction project planning and the transparency of information flow improve the construction project progression (Cus-Babic *et al.*, 2014). The dependency between the organisations is a must in the construction industry in order to maintain a power balance and to complete the construction project (Donato, Ahsan and Shee, 2015). There is a tendency that main contractors have more control over SMEs when there is a power imbalance.

2.2.2 Supply chain in the construction industry

The construction industry has its own approach to define and demonstrate the supply chain. According to Designing Building Limited (2019a), supply chains in the construction industry are unique as a result of the difference between the buildings that are developed by a group of consultants, contractors and suppliers who may never have worked together and may never work together again. In a traditional construction project, consultant work as first tier supplier who work for the client and the contractor use a supply chain of sub-contractors and suppliers to construct a building. Katenbayeva *et al.* (2016) agrees with definition and mentions that the supply chains in the construction industry are highly sectioned as those supply chains involve several parties with different purposes and rely heavily on subcontractors. The sample of the current research study is the second tier SME contractors that use a nonlinear supply chain according to the needs of their clients.

The supply chain of the construction industry is also different from other industries such as manufacturing industry. Although there is a link between the construction industry and manufacturing industry (Young, Hosseini and Laedre, 2016), the supply chains of the two industries are different when comparing the information and material flows (Negi, Ahuja and Baruah, 2017). Manufacturing industry has a linear supply chain while the construction industry has a nonlinear pattern in its supply chain (Figure 2). The reason for the nonlinear supply chain is the unique construction projects which include different requirements of clients and different project participants according to the scopes of the projects. This situation is more evident from the statement of Supply Chain Sustainability School (2017a). It mentions that the supply chains in the construction industry have nonlinear networks of performers that change around construction projects that demand high standard outcomes. This means that the organisations in the construction supply chain needs to give priority for the end users' requirements and make adjustments for projects through passing the material, fund and information accordingly.

Figure 2: Supply chain construction organisations

(Source: Negi *et al.*, 2017)

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According to Al-Werikat (2017), the construction industry is more complex with the size of the construction projects, large quantities of site materials and financial flows (from subcontractors and other tiers) and subcontractors. The construction companies have traditionally concentrated on the supply chain, where materials flow from the primary suppliers to the construction sites. The construction supply chain consumption (Hosseini *et al.*, 2014), for example, Dijk, Tenpierik and Dobbelsteen (2014) suggest that the construction supply chain should attempt to consume the raw materials and energy efficiently or recycle the waste in order to achieve zero residue. According to the construction supply chain needs to be managed systematically in order to reduce the environmental impact without any

regards to the size of the project. Kabirifar *et al.* (2020) mentions the waste reduction as the most effective waste minimisation method. The waste reuse (using the same construction material more than once) and the waste recycling (conversion of used construction materials to new materials) are effective when minimising the waste going to landfill. The construction waste that sends out to the landfills needs to be minimised as the construction solid waste is significantly higher than the waste generated by the other industries on a global scale (Amaral, *et al.*, 2020).

Yet, the complexity that develops with the size of the construction project requires higher level of planning, organising and collaboration between the members of the supply chain (Al-Werikat, 2017). This collaboration leads to continuous information flow and more efficient information sharing. As a result of the continuous information sharing, the construction industry does not have a linear information flow pattern.

Finally, the nonlinear supply chain of the construction industry needs to be managed accurately in order to remove waste from the supply chain, to reduce cost, to complete the projects on time, to achieve competitive advantage etc (Papadopoulos *et al.*, 2016). It is therefore vital to garner knowledge on the current practices of SCM within the construction industry.

This section achieved the objective of conducting a comprehensive literature review on supply chain. The supply chain of an organisation considerably contributes to the sustainability and therefore the SCM is important to initiate sustainability practices. In light of this section, 2.3 Supply Chain Management is allocated to provide an analysis of the existing literature on SCM.

2.3 Supply Chain Management

2.3.1 Overview

In 1982, Keith Oliver, introduced the ‘supply chain management’ to the public domain (Laseter and Oliver, 2018; Frankel *et al.*, 2008). Since the introduction of the SCM, the definition of SCM is confounding because of diverse definitions that have been proposed in the literature (Stock and Boyer, 2009; Mentzer *et al.*, 2001). Initially, the conceptualisation of SCM was narrow which dealt only with material flows between organisations (Sajjad, 2015) and over a period of time the concept has got extended to include information flow (Stock *et al.*, 2010). This article does not

provide any reason for the expansion of the SCM conceptualisation and also does not mention about the financial flow incorporation to the SCM conceptualisation. Therefore, it is evident that the financial flow was neglected at the beginning of the SCM conceptualisation (Bessler, 1999 cited in Pfohl and Gomm, 2009).

The diversity of the SCM definitions is justified from a series of past studies in 1990's. At the beginning of 1990's, SCM is defined as an organisational strategy. As an example, according to La Londe and Masters (1994) SCM is an organisational strategy that organisations use to deal with the challenges in managing the flow of materials between the point of origin and the point of consumption and in achieving organisations' market share and profitability objectives. In 1998, SCM was defined as a business activity. As an example, SCM was the management and incorporation of several business operations relating to the supply chain (Lambert, Cooper and Pagh, 1998). Here, business operations were explained as the activities within and between companies that produce a specific output of value to the ultimate user. Finally in 1999, the SCM was defined as a combination of customers, operations and suppliers. According to Tan *et al.* (1999), the SCM was also described as the concurrent incorporation of customer desired inventories, internal operations and upstream supplier performance. At the beginning of 1990's the definition began to address the market share and profitability while at the end of 1990's the definition included the suppliers and ultimate customers in to the theorisation and formulation of the SCM. These definitions have mentioned the supply chain activities in common and have expanded the definitions by adding extra points in to them. Therefore, they are classified as diverse definitions.

In the existing literature, several studies define SCM as management of supply chain business activities as highlighted in the examples given below;

Lambert and Cooper (2000) provides a detailed definition and an overview for SCM. Accordingly, SCM is the management of several business relations across the supply chain. Managing the supply chain network structure, managing the supply chain business processes and managing supply chain components are the interrelated elements of successful SCM. The supply chain network structure includes identification of members of the supply chain, identification of the three structural dimensions of supply chain network (comprise of 'horizontal structure' in other words the number of tiers across supply chain, 'vertical structure' in other words the

number of suppliers and customers in each tier and finally 'horizontal position') and identification of different types of process links across the supply chain. Further, it indicates two main management components namely 'physical and technical management components' (includes planning and control methods that guide the organisation in a desired direction, activity structure which indicates how the organisation is performing its activities, organisation structure, communication and information flow facility structure and finally product flow facility structure in other words the network structure across the supply chain) and 'managerial and behavioral management components' (includes management methods comprise of the organisational philosophy and management techniques, power and leadership structure, risk and reward structure and lastly culture and attitude). As an analysis, this particular article mentions the fundamentals to become successful in SCM apart from the explanation of SCM. Also, the authors make it clear for the readers what components they meant to mention as management. Therefore, the researcher finds this definition as much clearer than the definition in 1990's.

The article written by Melo, Nickel and Gama (2007) is another example that shows SCM as the management of supply chain business activities. Accordingly, SCM is the process of efficient planning, implementation and controlling of the supply chain activities. The planning of supply chain activities, implementation of these activities and controlling are the phases of management of business activities. This article does not provide information about the mentioned three phases. Different to this definition, Svensson (2007) defines SCM as a business philosophy that attempts to incorporate the dependent activities, actors and resources between the origin of a product to utilisation of the particular product. This definition illustrates the dependencies of the organisations in the supply chain in order to complete the supply chain business activities.

Another diverse definition of SCM as the management of supply chain business activities is the Council of Supply Chain Management Professionals (2018). It defines SCM as the planning and management of suppliers finding, goods and services obtaining, conversion and all logistics management activities. In other words, SCM is the management of demand and supply within intra and inter companies (Council of Supply Chain Management Professionals, 2018; Blanchard, 2010; Meehan and Muir, 2008). The logistics activities include the 'inbound logistic activities' such as receiving, storing and disseminating inputs to products and 'outbound logistics

activities' such as collecting, storing and distributing products to buyers (Vitasek, 2013; Blanchard, 2010).

In contrast, the existing literature defines SCM as management of the supply chain relations as reviews in the following paragraphs.

Stock and Boyer (2009) has conducted a literature review of previous definitions of SCM. Then they propose SCM as the management of relations within and between organisations and business units that consist of suppliers, purchasing, production, logistics, marketing and related systems that assist forward and reverse flow of material, service, finance and information from the manufacturer to ultimate customer in order to add value, to maximise profitability and to achieve customer satisfaction. This definition specifically mention SCM as the management of 'forward' and 'reverse' flows related to supply chain while La Londe and Masters (1994), Lambert and Cooper (2000) and Stadtler (2015) explain SCM as the management of flows related to supply chain not particularly 'forward' or 'reverse' flows. Further, the definition of Stock and Boyer (2009) differs from the previous definitions mention in this thesis as it mentions the objectives of SCM at the end. Once more the diversity of the SCM definitions is justified.

Christopher (2011) has provided another example for defining SCM as management of the supply chain relations. Accordingly, the management of upstream and downstream relations with suppliers and customers in order to achieve a profitable outcome is referred to as SCM. Here, the delivery of higher customer value at less cost to the supply chain is mentioned as profitable outcome. Also, the management of upstream suppliers and integration of downstream business customers is an important element of successful SCM implementation (Tan, 2002). Further, Carter *et al.* (2015) explain organisation's relationship with suppliers as upstream relation and organisation's relationship with customers as downstream relation. Christopher's definition mentions SCM as the management of organisation's relation with suppliers and customers and excludes the discussion about the management of material, information and financial flows as Stock and Boyer did in their definition. Therefore, once again the diversity of the SCM definitions is justified.

Apart from defining the SCM as the management of supply chain business activities and management of the supply chain relations, SCM is also defined as the coordination of material

and components flow. According to Chin *et al.* (2015) SCM is the coordination of raw materials and components flow from different suppliers and manufacturing companies. It leads organisation's sustainability as it creates opportunities for the organisation to integrate environmental, social and economic performance into its supply chain decision making process (Meixell and Luoma, 2015). The supply chain decision making process is a combination of order fulfilment that includes purchasing, internal operations and logistics and product development that includes location, product design and packing. SCM is a task of combining organisational units with a supply chain and linking information, material and financial flows in order to fulfil the demands of the customers (Stadtler, 2015). The definition of SCM specifically in SMEs is therefore different from the above mentioned definitions.

In SMEs, SCM is defined as an approach that helps SMEs to function in a more responsive and cost effective way through integrating the processes at operation, strategic and tactical levels (Baymout, 2015). The pressure from the globalisation makes SMEs to reduce their prices against their services and quality. Yet, SCM helps SMEs to improve their performance and profitability through improving their ability to acquire supplies of the right quality, at the right time and at the favoured prices. According to the perception of the researcher, this definition tries to highlight that SCM helps the SMEs to secure their financial status as they have limited budgets in comparison to the larger organisations.

In the construction industry, SCM is the understanding of breakdown and quality of products and services, logistics, organisations, activities, resources and information that transform raw materials in to a final product (Designing Buildings Limited, 2019b). This definition is a combination of actors, activities, materials and information of construction supply chain. Having this definition in mind and practicing SCM is beneficial for the construction companies and their clients (Constructing Excellence, 2019). Real time cost reduction and value addition, waste reduction and removal from the process, delivery of better value to the clients, repeat business with main clients and confidence in long term planning are classified as particular 'the benefits for the organisations' in the supply chain while expectation fulfilment, quality, functionality, project completion in a timely manner and within budget with minimum defects are classified as 'the benefits for the clients'. These benefits to the clients develop their satisfaction level and create higher reputation for the construction industry (Constructing Excellence, 2019; Al-

Werikat, 2017). Apart from the benefits for the construction organisations and their clients, the economic growth of other industries such as manufacturing industry also classified as the beneficiaries of construction SCM (Wibowo, Handayani and Mustikasari, 2018). SCM assists construction organisations to maintain more control on construction projects that involves multiple numbers of suppliers (Al-Werilat, 2017; Wibowo *et al.*, 2018). The following section (2.3.2) discusses the objectives of SCM that could be found in the existing literature.

2.3.2 Objectives of supply chain management

Organisations have targets and objectives to be efficient in their day to day tasks. The objectives can be classified as ‘long-term objectives’ which aim to accomplish in the future and ‘short-term objectives’ which intend to achieve the long-term objectives. Organisations who practice SCM has ‘short-term objectives’ such as to reduce the cycle time, to decrease inventory and to increase productivity, whilst having increased market share, customer satisfaction and profitability as their ‘long-term objectives’ (Li *et al.*, 2006; Tan, 2002). Both of these articles mention these objectives without providing any explanations for them. Also they do not mention what they meant by short-term and long-term objectives. They are left for the readers to interpret by themselves.

Fulfilling the value expectations of SME’s customers through converting raw materials of lower costs into high quality finished or semi-finished outcome is another objective of SCM (Chin *et al.*, 2015). Yet, the SME’s customer expectations or the demands need to be fulfilled through well organised resource use that includes the capacity of distribution, inventory and labour (Asare and Prempeh, 2016). Higher customer satisfaction adds value to the organisation and maximises the profitability. Value creation for the organisation and profitability maximisation are also classified as the objectives of SCM (Stock and Boyer, 2009). If organisations are able to maintain continuous profitability, it is possible for them to achieve the long-term performance improvement objective of SCM that affects to the individual organisation and the supply chain as a whole (Mentzer *et al.*, 2001). Further, SCM of SMEs aims to achieve consistency and reliability of the organisation through revenue maximisation, expenses minimisation and through all the assets utilisation (Syed, 2012). Additionally, appropriate organisational culture is crucial in order to achieve SCM objectives (Cao *et al.*, 2015). If not, internal organisational cultures disagree

with each other and as a result the final outcomes get affected. If these objectives are achieved, they lead an organisation to accomplish positive impacts as mentioned below.

2.3.3 Impact of supply chain management on organisations

The impact analysis of SCM is crucial for organisations as it guides the SCM system and helps organisations to achieve positive impacts or benefits. Tangible and intangible are the two benefit categories of SCM system which improve competitiveness of organisations (Hsu, 2005). Additionally, Syed (2012) illustrates the cost saving through higher market share and less production cost as tangible benefits and cost saving through customer satisfaction and loyalty as intangible benefits of SME's SCM system. As both of these articles do not explain the meaning of tangible benefits and intangible benefits, the researcher predicts tangible benefits as the benefits that can be measured in monetary terms and intangible benefits as the benefits that cannot be measured in monetary terms.

Meehan and Muir (2008) indicate improvement in supply chain communication and responsiveness as important benefits of SCM that guides SMEs to deliver higher customer service and value which then results in SMEs gaining competitive advantage. However, in comparison to Syed's article in 2012, Meehan and Muir do not categorise the benefits or does not provide much impacts of SCM.

Koh *et al.* (2007), agrees with above mentioned impacts of SCM on SMEs without classifying them as intangible and tangible benefits. Rather, the author mentions that the SCM enhances flexibility of organisations to adjust to the changes in business environment, achieve competitive advantage through delivery lead time reduction and increased responsiveness, appropriate planning of resource utilisation leads to cost savings, inventory level reduction and finally SCM helps organisations to calculate the accuracy of supply chain forecasts. Therefore, SCM can be classified as a necessary characteristic of an organisation basically to achieve a higher position in any industry.

Motivate factors as discussed in the below section (2.3.4), lead an organisation to implement SCM and achieve positive impacts or the benefits for the organisation.

2.3.4 Enablers to implement supply chain management

In this section, the factor that motivates organisations to implement SCM is discussed. Yet, the current study does not provide a series of enablers as the discussion is not aimed at studying this particular area. Somehow, organisations specifically SMEs must follow their business conditions and competitive priorities when implementing SCM (Thakkar, Kanda and Deshmukh, 2019). The owners and the senior managements have the understanding about their organisation's business conditions and competitive priorities. Therefore, they become the major influencers who can implement SCM techniques within a SME (Chin *et al.*, 2012). They are motivated and capable of developing the roadmap to implement SCM. Apart from the understanding, the whole supply chain visibility; risk in other words the probability of success; value in other words the correlation between cost and benefit and the methods used to balance the risk and the value are also categorised as the significant factors associated with the successful implementation of SCM in SMEs (Baymout, 2015). Followed by these enablers, personal contacts with the customers and employees, flexibility to response for the limited demands and flexibility to supply for fluctuating demands are also classified as some more enabling factors to implement SCM.

Although there are several benefits of the SCM, the SMEs find it difficult to implement SCM as there are barriers which are discussed in below section.

2.3.5 Barriers to implement supply chain management

Organisations specifically SMEs have barriers when implementing SCM. Yet, the current study does not analyse the existing literature on this due them being heavily concentrated on SSCM. However, in the construction industry SMEs, inadequate information technology infrastructure, suppliers' resistance to change, resource accessibility issues, price oriented and short term approaches, lack of senior management support and trust issues about the supplier are some of the barriers to implement SCM (Salami *et al.*, 2016). This study has been done in Turkey which has a status between developed and developing countries. Therefore, it is conflicting whether the mentioned barriers can be generalised for developing or developed countries. In contrast, Meehan and Muir (2008) have done their study in England where it is categorised as a developed country. It mentions lack of skilled people to manage supply chain development in SMEs, lack of power to influence other members in a supply chain, lack of interest of other members in a

supply chain towards participating in supply chain development are some more barriers to SCM in developed countries.

This section critically reviewed the literature on SCM and achieved the first objective of the current research study. The next section (2.4) critically reviews the existing literature on sustainability. The management of the supply chain is important to initiate sustainability practices in order to achieve competitive advantage.

2.4 Sustainability

2.4.1 Overview

The section 2.4.1 helps the readers and the researcher of the current study to develop the general understanding the sustainability. According to Meixell and Luoma (2015), sustainability is a crucial aspect affecting organisations who intend to fulfil the demands of their businesses and the stakeholders. This article attempts clearly demonstrate economic benefits, environmental concerns and social concerns are classified as the business's and stakeholders' (stakeholders are classified as primary stakeholders including suppliers, customers, top managers, employees and shareholders and secondary stakeholders including community, government, non-governmental organisations, competitors etc) higher standard demands from an organisation. When making efforts to fulfil these demands, an organisation must consider the ability to fulfil the demands of the future generation as well (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987). As an example; humans' try to achieve their housing needs by going beyond their satisfaction level which ultimately effects to the climate change (Gough, 2015). In this regard, the demands of the present generation might be fulfilled by generating negative impacts for the future generation. In contrast, sustainability makes a balance between the human wellbeing of the present and future generation.

The definition of sustainability is diverse (Sajjad, 2015; Sajjad and Eweje, 2013; Canadian Institute of Chartered Accountants (CICA), the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA) and Chartered Institute of Management Accountants (CIMA), 2011). Here, in the current study the sustainability definitions in SMEs and construction industry are

presented. When searching for existing literature on sustainability, the researcher found number of articles. Yet, the below mentioned articles are the suitable articles for the current study.

In SMEs, sustainability can be the long term business perspectives, corporate citizenship, environmental performance or any combination of those three (CICA, AICPA and CIMA, 2011). It is becoming a priority of all sizes of organisations. For SMEs, sustainability is important as their customers are looking at the environmental performance of organisations. Organisations can implement sustainability practices for the benefit of their communities, the environment and the bottom line margin improvement of their business as well their customers. Some organisations might begin with sustainability as the foundation for the organisation while other organisations move their business models towards more sustainable business models. They practice sustainability in order to generate employees' commitment and loyalty, improve organisations' profitability and to improve relationships with suppliers and customers. Integrating sustainability into the management processes of the larger organisations is a straightforward task as they have resources in particular staff, finance and time (Upstill-Goddard *et al.*, 2016). However, for the SMEs in the construction industry, scarcity of the resources such as expertise, customer demand, supply chain pressure, awareness and finance are challenging for the integration of broader sustainability practices (Upstill-Goddard *et al.*, 2016; Revell and Blackburn, 2007). The following discussion provides a brief overview of the three dimensions of sustainability.

In the UK construction industry, sustainability is defined as the development that fulfils the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of the future generation to fulfil their needs (Supply chain sustainability school, 2017b). Sustainable construction includes developing value to the users and customers, treating and respecting stakeholders fairly; improving and protecting the natural environment, reducing the construction's impact on natural resource and energy utilization and finally sustainable construction includes gaining more profits and making the construction industry competitive. In contrast, sustainability is defined as specifically the environmental sustainability that creates economic benefits for the UK construction organisations (Abuzeinab, 2015). This article argues that it shall more specifically focus on the environment as the construction industry, in comparison to other industries accounts for the largest context for human activities and consumes more natural resources than any other

industry. Consequently, the definition of sustainability shall change. It shall therefore be emphasised that should the construction industry show reluctance to change due their short term material gains, the greater the risk of future generations facing an uphill battle to maintain a sustainable eco-system whilst fulfilling their needs and the researcher therefore considers this phenomenon as the reason why SME's should include environmental sustainability into their supply chains.

2.4.2 Dimensions of sustainability

The three dimensions of sustainability are introduced in the current section (2.4.2). Yet, the current research study prioritises the environmental dimension as rationalised in the rationale section in the first chapter (introduction chapter). The sustainability literature has started to use a triple bottom line approach that includes people (in other words social), planet (in other words environment) and profit (in other words economic) concerns in business contexts (Chaudhary, 2015; Ahi and Searcy, 2013). In 1994, John Elkington established the term “triple bottom line” in order to describe the concept of sustainability in the business context (Pishchulov *et al.*, 2018). The triple bottom line explains sustainability as a balance between social, economic and environment dimension of growth (Lu, 2017). Washington (2015: 34-35) mentions that sustainability has been explained as the sustainable growth or the development of the society, environment and economy. However, the author, Washington (2015) argues that sustainability focuses on the long term sustainability of the society and the environment while sustainable development focuses on the endless economic growth.

Environment concerns, social concerns and economic performance are the three dimensions of sustainability (Meixell and Louma, 2015; Seuring, 2013; Ashby, Leat and Hudson-Smith, 2012). Yilmaz and Bakis (2015) also justify environment protection, social fairness and economic progression as the three dimensions of sustainability. According to Dyllick and Hockertd (2002), focusing only on economic sustainability of an organisation can be successful for short-term, while in the long-term organisational sustainability requires all three dimensions. As a justification for Dyllick and Hockertd's statement, Morali and Searcy (2013) mention that the interrelationship between the social, environmental and economic dimensions leads an organisation to a sustainable growth.

Further, Miller and Engemann (2018) explain the economic, social and environmental dimensions of sustainability. 'Economic sustainability' helps organisations to save capital while 'social sustainability' dimension focuses on organisation's stakeholders including local communities, stockholders and employees. Reducing energy consumption costs is an example for economic sustainability of supply chain. Integrating environmental friendly steps in supply chain is the 'environmental sustainability'. The environmental sustainability protects natural capital namely usable land, biodiversity, navigable waterways and clear air. Although the natural capital does not appear on organisation's balance sheet, it is important for an organisation as it facilitates business operations. Kopnina (2017) mentions concerns related to challenges ranging from climate change to biodiversity loss to pollution as the environment sustainability. Organisations can measure to what extent they practice these sustainability dimensions through identifying their sustainability performance indicators as mentioned in the below section (2.4.3).

2.4.3 Sustainability performance indicators

An organisation that plans to implement SSCM needs to identify the sustainability performance indicators as it helps to gain an understanding about the sustainability characteristic and impacts of organisation activities. After conducting a literature analysis, Miller and Engemann (2018) mention performance indicators that relates to sustainability (Figure 3) and provide explanations for them.

Below, figure 3 shows three levels of performance indicators namely direct, indirect and external. Managing business cost which comes under economic dimension helps organisations to measure the economic performance relating to sustainable supply chain. The cost include 'direct costs' namely labour cost, material cost and distribution cost of production and delivery, 'indirect costs' such as warranty costs, recycling costs etc. and 'external costs' such as regulatory fines. Managing natural capital and available resources helps organisations to measure the environmental performance relating to sustainable supply chain. Mostly organisations depend on the natural capital for instance stable environments for business operation. Social sustainability performance indicates through developing relationships with employees, customers, investors, NGOs and governments. While Miller and Engemann (2018) mention the above performance indicators (figure 3), Zhong and Wu (2015) analyse economic and environmental sustainability indicators specifically in the construction industry. Accordingly, structural cost (which includes

man power, machinery and material cost), maintenance cost, non-construction cost (which includes the fee of engineers, architects etc) and additional incomes (such as the income generated by using alternative materials) are the significant economic sustainability performance indicators and reduced material use, recycling rate, percentage of waste, water consumption and noise pollution are the major environmental sustainability performance indicators.

Figure 3: Sustainability performance indicators

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(Source: Miller and Engemann, 2018)

The section 2.4 achieved the research objective of conducting comprehensive literature review on sustainability. The next section reviews the literature on sustainable supply chain.

2.5 Sustainable Supply Chain

2.5.1 Overview

In this section, the current study provides a general understanding about sustainable supply chain in different industries. The current study does not go in-depth to sustainable supply chain as its primary aim is to study the implementation of SSCM. Therefore, the researcher used Kot's (2018) definition of sustainable supply chain and developed the review accordingly. The article defines sustainable supply chain as the maintenance of a balance between the economy, social and environment through an organisation's supply chain (Kot. 2018). An organisation can implement sustainability in a holistic manner by taking appropriate actions to address economic, environmental and social issues and develop an efficient long term supply system (Lozano and Huisingh, 2011). However, it is challenging to balance or to integrate all three dimensions of sustainability (social, environment and economic) into a supply chain management process as these three dimensions cannot be treated with discrimination but should be broadly summarised into a set of supply chain performance goals (Ni and Sun, 2018). Orr and Jadhav (2018) also admit that implementing a sustainable supply chain aimed at developing organisation's performance as challenging. Resistance to change, cost, lack of knowledge, lack of leadership commitment to collaborate supply chains with sustainability are some of the barriers that makes sustainable supply chain implementation challenging.

The section 2.5.2 analyses the implementation of sustainable supply chain.

2.5.2 Implementation of sustainable supply chain

Blackhurst *et al.* (2012) recommended four steps for SMEs to implement sustainable supply chain. These steps have been recommended after reviewing academic research in the manufacturing industry and not in the construction industry. However, the literature review of the current research study used this article as it views these steps as useful for the construction industry.

According to the recommendation of Blackhurst *et al.* (2012), the first step, 'understanding the facts' helps an organisation to perform an evaluation of supply chain sustainability in terms of environmental, financial and social aspects and needs of the organisation. This assessment helps

the organisation to identify potential opportunities that already exist. 'Developing a vision' is the second step of sustainable supply chain implementation. In order to develop a long-term vision, an organisation has to go beyond the previous assessment and understand entire supply chain and issues relating to the supply chain sustainability with the help of stakeholders. Following which a life cycle assessment should be done by concluding environmental, social and financial impacts of the products. The third step of supply chain implementation is 'creating a roadmap'. Focusing on the existing facilities to meet the basic compliance guidelines, developing a business case to address the identified gaps from the sustainability assessment, implementing the projects that can be implemented quickly with minimum investment and establishing standards to measure the improvements of sustainable supply chain practice are the tasks of the roadmap. Final step of sustainable supply chain implementation is 'executing, reviewing and changing'. Necessary changes have to be done for the implemented sustainable supply chain after reviewing the decisions regularly.

This section achieved the objective of conducting a comprehensive literature review on sustainable supply chain was achieved this section. The next section provides a critical review of sustainable supply chain management.

2.6 Sustainable Supply Chain Management and/or Sustainable Development of Supply Chain Management

2.6.1 Overview

This overview section aims to develop the understanding about SSCM through analysing the existing literature in any industry. According to Brandenburg, Gruchmann and Oelze, (2019) and Sajjad, (2015), Carte and Rogers (2008) are among the researchers who initiated the conceptualisation of SSCM. After conducting a large scale literature review, Carter and Rogers (2008) explain SSCM as the strategic, transparent integration and accomplishment of an organisation's economic, social and environmental targets through the systemic management of main inter-organisational business system in order to improve long-term economic performance of the individual organisation and its supply chain. This definition highlights two main aspects (Sajjad, 2015), firstly, it focuses on the three dimensions of the sustainability and secondly, it

proposes the need for supply chain coordination at inter-organisational business level among various supply chain members in order to improve sustainability performance.

On the other hand, Ahi and Searcy (2013) mention an in-depth definition for SSCM after analysing existing definitions of SSCM. Accordingly, SSCM is the establishment of harmonized supply chains through voluntary incorporation of social, environmental and economic concerns with main inter-organisational business processes that designed to manage capital, material and information flows associated with procurement, production and distribution of services or products with the aim of fulfilling the demands of the stakeholders, improving competitiveness, improving profitability and thereby creating a resilient organisation. Furthermore, these authors mention that the existing SSCM definitions address the characteristics of SCM and sustainability. The characteristics of SCM are classified as the flow focus (financial, material, information and service flows), coordination focus, stakeholder focus (customer satisfaction as an example), relationship focus (Internal and external relationships), value creation focus, efficiency creation focus and performance focus while the key characteristics of business sustainability are classified as the economic focus, environmental focus, social focus, stakeholder focus, volunteer focus, resilience focus and long-term focus (in brief a long-term economic performance). However, none of the SSCM definitions address all of the business sustainability characteristics and SCM characteristics (Sajjad, 2015).

With more attention given to environmental dimension of SSCM, Gupta and Palsule-Desai (2011) define SSCM as a set of managerial practices which includes environmental impact as a necessity that consider in all stages of entire value chain and a multi-disciplinary perception that encompass the entire product life cycle. 'Including environmental impact as a necessity' means that the organisations must perceive environmental impact of their activities across the entire value chain as an essential element of managerial decision-making rather than as a social pressure or a restriction imposed by government regulations or as a trend to develop by emerging to be 'green'. The entire value chain includes suppliers, partners, distributors and consumers. Strategic considerations (including organisational strategy, supply chain strategy and structure and marketing strategy), decisions at functional borders (including product design and product life cycle, pricing and valuation of returns and forecasting and value of information), regulations and government policies and finally integrative models and decision support tools are the

managerial decisions that integrates with SSCM. Further, organisations' view of sustainability must go beyond a narrow functional perception and include a broader perspective integrating problems, issues and solutions across functional restrictions.

When it comes to the overview, SSCM is supply chain evolution from traditional supply chain to sustainable supply chain (Roy, 2018). The SSCM is an important study area although the studies on SSCM in SMEs are not in a satisfactory level (Paingrahi *et al.*, 2018; Shibin *et al.*, 2017; Ashby, 2014). However, smaller to wider organisations in the developed countries such as UK, tend to integrate sustainability practices into their supply chain management operations as a result of their desire to minimise reputational risks (Hofmann *et al.*, 2014; Roehrich, Grosvold and Hoejmoose, 2014; Buddress, 2013), as a result of regulatory pressure and market pressure (Saeed and Kersten, 2019), as a result of their desire for a long-term existence through changing their practices and business models to address their negative impacts on environment and society (Pagell and Shevchenko, 2014), as a result to achieve business growth through maintaining an interlink between the sustainability practices and strategy of an organisation (Lu, 2017) etc.

Ashby, Leat and Hudson-Smith (2012) state that SSCM literatures are published from 2003 while SCM reviewed papers are published from 1996. Further, Touboulie and Walker (2015) mention that the literatures published prior to 2000, define SCM and environmental impacts as two different variables rather than clearly defining SSCM as an incorporated concept with sustainable development which includes environmental, social and economic dimensions. Also, Seuring and Muller (2008a) mention that the integration of three sustainable development dimensions appeared in the literatures in about 2002 and 2003.

In summary, the above discussion mentions SSCM as an important practice for organisations secure their long-term existence. It is a combination of the business characteristics and the SCM characteristics. Also SSCM is an integration of economic, environmental and social concerns into a supply chain. Although it is an important practice, the literature or the researches on SSCM in SMEs are in researcher's view still underdeveloped. The model of SSCM is presented in the next section (2.6.2).

2.6.2 Model of supply chain management

Figure 4 illustrates the triple bottom line concept which sustainability through balancing an organisation's environmental, social and economic performance (Figure 14). These three dimensions guide organisations to set targets such as greenhouse gas emissions reduction through the environmental performance dimension, developing employment opportunities through social performance dimension and to set financial targets through economic performance dimension. The model of SSCM suggests that at the enterprise level, social and economic performance, the organisations can get the best of both worlds long-term environmental performance without decreasing social and environmental performance (Carter and Rogers, 2008). Carter and Rogers (2017) explain the integration of economic, environmental and social performance into supply chain management as the three pillars of sustainable development.

(Carter and Rogers, 2014; Carter and Rogers 2008)

The three dimensions of SSCM management are explained in the next section (2.6.3). Yet more focus is given to the environmental dimension of SSCM as the current study aims to collect data on SSCM implementation to protect the environment.

2.6.3 Dimensions of sustainable supply chain management

2.6.3.1 Environmental dimension of sustainable supply chain management

Environmental dimension of SSCM is defined “*as a condition of balance, resilience and interconnectedness that allows human society to satisfy its needs while neither exceeding the capacity of its supporting ecosystems to continue to regenerate the service necessary to meet those needs nor by our actions diminishing biological diversity*” (Morelli, 2011: 5). According to the author, the concept of sustainability has been used when implementing this particular definition. The definition mentions that there needs to be a balance for the human impacts on the natural system which fulfils the needs of the present and the future generation equally.

Environmental issues develop when there is an imbalance for the human impacts on the natural system. For example, hazardous wastes and their emissions which are generated by supply chains are the main causes of environmental damage and pollution (Panigrahi *et al.*, 2018). The environmental dimension of SSCM is a solution for increasing environmental issues that guide the organisations to conduct their activities and supply chain processes without harming or disturbing the environment. More specifically, this guidance leads to emission reductions aspect of environmental dimension of SSCM which addresses the environment pollution through organisation’s greenhouse gas emission, through supply chain operations and through manufacturing (Pishchulov *et al.*, 2018). The reductions in emissions produce positive impacts on the organisations and financial performance (Gallego-Alvarez, Segura and Martinez-Ferrero, 2015). Therefore, organisations adopt environment dimension of SSCM on a voluntary basis or the organisations are imposed by government regulations (Pishchulov *et al.*, 2018).

Further, the environmental dimension of SSCM represents the external business conditions that are capable of creating the authorization for SSCM implementation (Roy, 2018). At this particular point, an organisation can outline the necessity and motivations associated with SSCM implementation. Fundamentally, the necessity and the authorization for SSCM implementation emerge from business customers and business stakeholders. When making a decision to

implement SSCM, an organisation must think about the environment impacts across the whole supply chain that includes the supplier selection, selection of distributor and customer awareness (Su *et al.*, 2015).

Environmental management comes under environmental dimension of SSCM. In the construction industry, environmental issues such as biodiversity, waste, carbon and water need to be reported systematically and measured in order to meet the legal environmental responsibilities set by EMS of an organisation (Supply chain sustainability school, 2017c). According to Green Element (2017), EMS is a structured framework for organisations that helps them to monitor, improve and control their environmental performance or impacts. It defines environmental responsibilities, identifies opportunities for waste reduction, reduces the risk of fines for environmental legislation refusal, attracts investors and stakeholders, records environmental performance against set objectives and ensures all operations have systems to reduce environmental impacts. Some organisations adopt international and national standard framework which set out the requirements of an EMS while other organisations adopt their own informal EMS. British standard BS8555 and ISO14001 developed by the International Organisation for Standardisation are some of the examples for international and national standards (Green Element, 2017; Supply chain sustainability school, 2017c). Further, BREEAM (Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method) and CEEQUAL (The Civil Engineering Environmental Quality Assessment and Awards Scheme) are some examples for international and national standards specifically in the construction industry (Supply chain sustainability school, 2017b).

The organisations, in particular the construction organisations that consider the environmental sustainability use natural resources with an ecological balance that they do not destroy them but develop them and hand them to the next generation (Yilmaz and Bakis, 2015). These organisations maintain this balance as the sustainability of a natural resource is depending on the ability of its renewal. Yet, increased building needs of the people as a result of the civilisation causes environmental issues during building construction, maintenance and destruction (Yilmaz and Bakis, 2015). Solid waste, liquid waste and gas emissions are the main environmental issues that cause negative impacts on the environment. Decrease in bio diversity, nonrenewable resource consumption, reductions of agricultural area, deforestation, global warming, soil

pollution, water pollution and air pollution are the negative impacts of increased natural resource usage. The construction industry in the UK is the largest user of natural resources and generates around 100 million tonnes of waste in each year (WRAP, the National Federation of Builders and Envirowise, n.d.). These tonnes of waste are classified as inert waste (waste that will not harm the environment such as glasses), hazardous waste (waste that will damage the environment such as mastic tubes) and non-hazardous waste (waste that will decompose such as plasterboard). In a construction site the inert and non-hazardous waste also has to be managed equally as the hazardous waste in order to maintain a safe environment for the workers.

Waste management in the construction industry is identified as the main issue of SSCM as it directly effects on the environment and the effectiveness of the industry (Wibowo *et al.*, 2018). In the construction industry, waste is generated throughout the design and construction stages. According to WRAP, the National Federation of Builders and Envirowise (n.d.), SMEs in the construction industry has to aim to reduce waste generation, reuse the generated waste, recycle the waste that cannot be reused and finally dispose the remainder. Waste management through reusing, recycling, using durable materials and educating employees helps construction organisations to reduce the cost, to increase safety in the sites and to develop productivity (Wibowo *et al.*, 2018). Enhanced communication between the contractors, subcontractors and suppliers is effective when it comes for the waste management and waste reduction throughout the supply chain (Udawatta *et al.*, 2015).

‘Balfour Beatty Construction’ is one of the top construction companies that practice environmental sustainability successfully. The company has reduced carbon emissions by 51% since the year 2010 (Balfour Beatty, 2021). The company has the understanding about the amount of carbon dioxide and other air pollutants production of the construction industry. Therefore, it aims to build a better future for everyone through reducing carbon emissions beyond and achieve net zero carbon by 2040 and through generating zero waste. Eliminating and reducing fossil fuels usage, replacing these for lower carbon alternatives, using renewable energy and installing electric vehicle charging points for car fleet are some of the activities that has being implemented to achieve these aims. The stakeholders including the customers, shareholders, communities and employees have contributed in indentifying these targets.

'BAM Construct UK' is another construction company that practices environmental sustainability successfully. The company has the understanding that construction industry uses many resources and that has lead the company to implement sustainability practices (BAM Construct UK, 2020). Under the environmental sustainability, the company aims to develop positive impacts on the climate and to make better use of resources by the year 2050. Reduction in energy use by digitalizing; use of renewable power, fuel and heat; carbon emission reduction; waste elimination and right material use are some of the activities that are implemented to achieve the environmental sustainability aims.

The next section (2.6.3.2), briefly reviews the literature on the economic dimension of SSCM. Here, the researcher has not done an extensive review as the current study focuses mainly on the environmental dimension of SSCM.

2.6.3.2 Economic dimension of sustainable supply chain management

“The economic sustainability element is based upon Solow’s (1974, 1986, 1993) amplified theory on capital convertibility and Hicks-Lindahl concept of maximum income, which can be acquired by saving essential wealth (capital) resources for the benefit of future generations, (implementing the principle of fair distribution among generations)” (Ciegis, Ramanauskiene and Martinkus, 2009: 32-33). This quotation illustrates the main target of economic sustainability as to increase profits. Meanwhile, Kannegiesser and Gunther (2014) mentions achieving financial targets such as revenues or profits as an example for the economic dimension. Profitability can be achieved through reductions in cost such as energy cost and raw material cost (Mokhtar *et al.*, 2016) and through the management of society and environment (Panigrahi *et al.*, 2018). Having said that the societal and environmental management leads to profitability, the management of environmental dimension of sustainability is the most important element for the European cities as it generates economic benefits and leads to economical sustainability (Nevado-Pena, Lopez-Ruiz and Alfaro-Navarro, 2015). The current research has identified that it is important to study the environmental dimension as it assists the economic dimension of SSCM.

The next section (2.6.3.3) briefly reviews the literature on the social dimension of SSCM and highlights why the current study prioritised the environmental dimension of SSCM over the social dimension.

2.6.3.3 Social dimension of sustainable supply chain management

The social dimension of SSCM basically deals with the maintenance of a healthy society where a particular organisation is functional. The social dimension is comprised of individuals and the organisation as a whole (Panigrahi *et al.*, 2018). In line with social dimension of SSCM, the decisions of supply chain managers and top managers should not violate the fundamental humanitarian ethics and value. Also it focuses on people's abilities and skills, partnerships and organisations. Creating new employment opportunities can be mentioned as an example for social dimension of SSCM (Kannegiesser and Gunther, 2014). Having said that, in the construction industry there is a tendency for human rights abuses such as delays in wage payments, inappropriate working conditions and bonded labour (Katenbayeva *et al.*, 2016). In order to address these types of human rights abuses, the UK government established the Modern Slavery Act in 2015. This act obligates the larger organisations in the construction industry, to show that they are working to reduce slavery within their supply chains in the country and overseas.

According to Montabon, Pagell and Wu (2016), environmental sustainability is more important than the social sustainability as functioning of the ecosystem is crucial for the survival of humans. Moreover, the social system that includes health, employment and quality of life need to be supported by the environment. The current research study accepts Montabon, Pagell and Wu's (2016) view point and conducts the research on the area of environmental dimension of SSCM.

The next section (2.6.4) analyses the literature on impacts of SSCM on organisations.

2.6.4 Impact of sustainable supply chain management on organisations

SSCM leads to a reduction of organisation's costs associated with packaging, disposal, health and safety, labour, recruitment and turnover; and leads organisations to achieve higher reputation (Carter and Rogers, 2008). Also according to Tseng, Lim and Wong (2015), SSCM does not only reduce the costs or increase the organisation's profitability; rather, it does increase

organisation's reputation that leads to productivity by way of enhancing their morale and commitment, reduce waste, material and resource consumption through enabling better resource utilisation.

Moreover, SSCM increases organisational performance including 'market based performance' (financial indicators that reflect fulfilment of customer needs, customer loyalty, market share etc), 'accounting based performance' (overall profitability of the organisation) and 'operational based performance' (characteristics relating to operational effectiveness as examples speed, flexibility, quality and costs) (Golicic and Smith, 2013). According to Dadhich *et al.* (2015) UK construction companies which practice environmental SSCM increase their profits by reducing their cost of waste disposal and transportation.

The construction clients require business consultants, suppliers and contractors to adopt sustainability practices and policies in their construction processes (Athapaththu and Karunasena, 2018; Tan, Shen and Yao, 2011). Furthermore, according to Adetunji, Price and Fleming (2011), the end user or the client select the main contractor depending on the price the construction company charges, depending on the environmental policies, innovation in construction process, modernisation in materials, health and safety performances and supply chain network of the subcontractors. In such situations, the main contractor must hire the subcontractors or the construction SMEs who practices the SSCM in order to satisfy the needs of the end user or the client. Having said that, the main contractors might select the subcontractors based on the reputation of the company which gained from practicing SSCM or based on personal relationships (Geach, 2016).

Another positive impact of the SSCM on construction companies is the increased competitive advantage. Lim *et al.* (2017) mentions environmental SSCM increases the competitiveness of organisations. Xia *et al.* (2018) also justifies that the companies who practice the SSCM achieve more competitive advantage than the companies who do not practice it. Further, the contractors have to follow the sustainability demands of the client's in order to achieve competitiveness (Athapaththu and Karunasena, 2018).

The next section (2.6.5) critically reviews the present implementation processes that are published in the literature.

2.6.5 Implementation process of sustainable supply chain management

The implementation of sustainable performance expands the transparency of supply chain management and business process while developing the opportunities for increased competitiveness (Zimon *et al.*, 2019). However, the implementation of SSCM depends on the identifiable benefits for instances competitive advantage and cost saving or depends on the identifiable risks such as loss of market share and reputational damage (Faisal, 2010). These practices are likely to be successful with internal and external factors that lead an organisation to implement sustainability strategies successfully. Organisational system, performance, organisation's need to advance, organisational policies and mindsets are the internal factors that influence the implementation of sustainability strategies (Law and Gunasekaran, 2012). Legal system in the country, social pressure, competition and market trend are the external factors that lead an organisation to adopt the environment, social and financial sustainability strategies.

Several authors have mentioned different stages of SSCM implementation process. However, in common, they have mentioned that each stage of SSCM implementation process involves management decision making which helps organisations to make their supply chains more sustainable (Federal Ministry for the Environment, Natural Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety, 2017; Chaudhary, 2015; Reefke, Ahmed and Sundaram, 2014). Discovering the unsustainable areas within a supply chain (Reefke *et al.*, 2014), prioritising the negative impact created on society, environment and economy of the organisation (Federal Ministry for the Environment, Natural Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety, 2017) and identifying the need of sustainability integration in to supply chain (Chaudhary, 2015) are some of the examples for management decision involves in SSCM implementation process.

2.6.5.1 Seven step SSCM implementation process

In Germany, the Federal Ministry for the Environment, Natural Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (2017), introduces seven steps for the implementation of SSCM in SMEs with specific emphasis on the environmental sustainability practices (Figure 5). Each of these steps help managers to decide which areas are more important for their organisations in order to make their supply chains more sustainable. The SMEs who have already introduced an Environmental

Management System (EMS) also can practice this process in order to implement the management of indirect environmental activities that impacts on the environment.

Figure 5: Seven process steps of SSCM implementation

(Source: Federal Ministry for the Environment, Natural Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety, 2017)

The first step of the SSCM implementation (figure 5), ‘mapping the supply chain’ helps organisations to gain an understanding about their suppliers and sub-suppliers who create value for the supply chains and the suppliers’ and sub-suppliers’ activities that lead to creating positive or negative impacts on people, environment and organisations. As an example suppliers’ and sub-suppliers’ supply chain activities might lead to natural disasters that create negative impacts on environment, people and organisations themselves by damaging their reputation. Therefore it is necessary to illustrate the supply chains of organisations (Federal Ministry for the Environment, Natural Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety, 2017). Moreover, the analysis of the whole supply chain is crucial to evident the sustainability issues (Silvestre, 2016).

The second step of SSCM implementation (figure 5) has three aims namely identifying sustainability aspects and impacts of organisation activities, assessing and prioritising sustainability risks of negative impacts and finally determining sustainability topics and action areas in order to implement SSCM by utilising organisations' own financial and human resources. This second process step helps organisations to prepare a materiality analysis, in other words an overview of the connection between sustainability aspects and negative impacts of those aspects or activities on environment, people and on organisations (Federal Ministry for the Environment, Natural Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety, 2017). As an example, Inyim, Rivera and Zhu (2015) mention fuel consumption rate, eutrophication potential etc as the components that assess the impact of construction industry while prioritising the global warming potential as the main focus of environmental impacts. These environmental impacts can affect negatively on organisations such as increased reputation risk (Gatzert, Schmit and Kolb, 2014). Accordingly, the construction organisations take action to implement SSCM in order to avoid these negative effects (Brooks and Rich, 2016).

The third process step in figure 5, 'analysing gaps and deriving measures' is an action that SMEs take when implementing SSCM. It aims at 'gap analysis' through comparing existing organisational objectives, measures and processes that is useful in the sustainable supply chain management framework and 'deriving measures' in order to improve sustainability performance in organisations' supply chains. The results gained from the materiality analysis in the previous process step should be used as the foundation for the gap analysis. At this step organisations have to develop mission statements by outlining the importance of sustainability aspects in supply chains. The mission statements indicate an organisation's key objectives while distinguishing themselves from their competitors (Galpin, Whittington and Bell, 2015).

'Adapting internal structures and processes' is the next process step of SSCM implementation. It aims at setting up or adjusting new and existing organisational business processes based on the materiality analysis results. Organisations should gradually integrate SSCM requirements into the existing organisational business processes and structures in order to achieve effective SSCM implementation. According to Young *et al.* (2015), the existing business processes and structures are the organisational factors that guide the performance and activities of an organisation and its employees'. For example, the employees of an organisation might have set environmental

behaviors that are influenced with the existing business processes and structures. The environmental behaviors of the organisation and employees can be changed by adjusting the existing business processes and structures although it is complex to change set behaviors. Identifying the members who is willing to adapt makes the changes efficient and effective.

Accordingly, the fifth SSCM implementation process step, ‘formulating supplier requirements and making them binding’ is helpful to identify the supply chain members who are willing to change. During this step, organisations discuss the requirements of the direct suppliers and ask for a self assessment of their SSCM implementation capabilities. The results of the self assessments lead to conventional supplier evaluation and helps organisations to decide on the suppliers that they can establish or continue business relationships. Then ‘a supplier code of conduct’ is integrated into the supplier contract by binding it for the direct suppliers and if applicable for the sub-suppliers as well. The supplier code of conduct is a document that formulates all the requirements for the direct suppliers and where applicable for the sub-suppliers.

‘Evaluating the sustainability performance of suppliers and building competences’ is the next process step that aims at evaluating the suppliers in order to ensure compliance with the code of conduct, developing suppliers’ capabilities in order to develop the supply chain and finally aims at integrating supplement criteria for new suppliers selection and existing suppliers confirmation. When evaluating the suppliers, the organisations should use the supplier self-assessment results to find out how they deal with risks associated with upstream processes. The supplier evaluation should go beyond the supplier self-assessment if there is any increased risk of contract violation. At this point organisations should conduct audits with the help of qualified auditors. Developing suppliers’ capabilities through forming a concrete action plan with the suppliers is the next step when the results of the supplier self-assessment and audit disclose any suppliers’ potentials for increased risk or violation of the contract. The results of materiality analysis and supplier self-assessment should be used when integrating supplement criteria for new suppliers’ selection and existing suppliers’ confirmation. It helps organisations to assume the existing processes and instruments and supplement them with sustainability criteria.

During the last process step in figure 5, Federal Ministry for the Environment, Natural Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (2017) mention that the organisations should report

information on sustainability supply chain management activities. Disclosure of sustainability impacts, details on risk and materiality analysis processes, details on value chain evaluation, information on the measures implementation including code of conduct and reference of audits are the important aspects that stakeholders expect from organisational reports in order to maintain an in-depth understanding about the organisational activities.

2.6.5.2 SSCM implementation decision making cycle

According to Reefke *et al.* (2014), implementation of SSCM involves decision making at all levels from the strategic decision making to operational decision making. Organising all these decisions in a proper manner helps organisations to develop more sustainable supply chains. Figure 6 illustrates cyclically organised decisions that integrate with the implementation of SSCM.

Figure 6: SSCM decision making cycle

(Source: Reefke *et al.*, 2014)

As a beginning for the implementation of SSCM, organisations have to discover the unsustainable areas of their supply chains. Thereafter, social, environmental and economic practices within the discovered unsustainable areas are studied in the learning stage. The learning stage helps organisations to identify the sustainable practices that lead them to make win-win decisions relating to SSCM (Reefke *et al.*, 2014). According to Beske and Seuring (2014), dedication to the triple bottom line is a sustainable practice that helps organisations to achieve win-win-win situations. The dedication to the triple bottom line includes decisions that evaluate strategies of SSCM. Further, Ahmed and Sundaram (2012) mention that the discovery and learning help decision makers to be able to visualise how sustainability can be achieved.

The organisations can use the visualisation and the decisions made in the discovery and learning to formulate strategies and decide the most suitable strategy to introduce and implement more sustainable supply chains (Reefke *et al.*, 2014; Ahmed and Sundaram, 2012). When formulating a strategy, an organisation should pay attention on necessary social capital and human capital in order to maintain a good communication between the executives, employees and suppliers (Lu, 2017). According to Beske and Seuring (2014), enhanced communication between all the members of the supply chain helps to increase the performance of overall chain and to improve collaborative business relationships in order to achieve sustainability performance.

Then, the organisations can make decisions regarding the design of systems, processes and people that are helpful to implement the formulated strategies (Reefke *et al.*, 2014). The implementation of the design is called transformation. The impact of this transformation on SSCM needs to be monitored in terms of key and cross performance indicators. Examining an organisation's social performance through health risk indicators, environmental performance through consumption of natural resources and examining economic performance through profits (Lu, 2017) are some examples of the performance indicators that help an organisation to monitor the impact of formulated strategy implementation on SSCM. This transformation is a continuous process that helps organisations to implement SSCM (Ahmed and Sundaram, 2012).

The decisions made in the monitoring, lead organisations to control or in other words manage the sustainable supply chains through proactive actions and corrective actions for under-performing or non-performing areas (Reefke *et al.*, 2014). This monitoring and controlling helps decision

makers to reformulate the strategies, redesign and continue the transformation process (Ahmed and Sundaram, 2012).

2.6.5.3 Environmental management system (EMS)

According to Nicolson (2016), the activities of any organisation with a supply chain require raw materials as inputs that produce services as outputs. The actions involved in the process of producing services have impacts on the environment which needs to be managed. The organisations practice the EMS as a model to minimise the impacts such as air pollution, reduction of natural resources, water contamination etc. Environmental legislations, supply chain pressure and investor pressure leads the organisations to implement EMS. The EMS facilitates the implementation of environmental sustainability practices (Kim and Chai, 2017; Darnall, Jolley and Handfield, 2008). The EMS is therefore needed to be implemented by SMEs on ‘plan, do, check, act’ model in order to identify, control and monitor the environmental concerns systematically (Stapleton, Glover and Davis, 2001).

Figure 7: Environmental management system model

(Source: Stapleton *et al.*, 2001)

As the first step, the top management of a SME needs to establish an environmental policy (The Business Environment Council and Environmental Protection Department, 2005; Stapleton *et al.*, 2001). The established environmental policy needs to present the organisation's commitment and vision towards the environment protection, needs to establish a framework for setting and reviewing environmental objectives, needs to be understood by the staff and needs to be signed by the top management (The Business Environment Council and Environmental Protection Department, 2005).

The second step is the planning stage which helps SMEs to establish objectives and processes that are necessary to achieve the established environmental policy. It includes the identification of environmental attributes of activities of an organisation, identification and conformation of

laws and regulations, establishment of environmental objectives for the organisation and planning the actions to achieve these environmental objectives.

The third step is the implementation of the actions and processes that are already planned. This step includes resource allocation, responsibility allocation, providing training and awareness about the environmental responsibilities, internal and external environmental issues communication, documentation of EMS and identification of emergencies and responses for them.

The next step is checking the effectiveness of the environmental policy, objectives and legal requirements (The Business Environment Council and Environmental Protection Department, 2005). Conducting audits on EMS helps to verify whether it is operating as planned (Stapleton *et al.*, 2001). As the final stage, conducting management reviews also helps to improve the EMS continuously.

The subsection 2.6.5.4 provides a comparison of three processes in the section 2.6.5.

2.6.5.4 Summary of the implementation processes of SSCM section

Seven process steps of SSCM implementation	SSCM implementation decision making cycle	EMS model
Mapping the supply chain	Discovering unsustainable areas	Developing environmental policy
Identifying sustainability aspects, prioritisation and determining actions	Learning	Planning
Analysing gaps of existing objectives, measures and process	Introducing strategies to implement SSCM	Implementation
Adapting internal structure and process	Designing systems, process and people to implement SSCM	Checking effectiveness of environmental policy, objectives and legal requirements
Formulating supplier requirements and binding	Implementing the design	Management review
Evaluating sustainability performance	Monitoring the impact of SSCM implementation	
Reporting	Reformulating the strategy, redesigning and continuing	

Table1: The implementation processes of SSCM (Source: Compiled by the author)

The seven process steps of SSCM implementation by Federal Ministry for the Environment, Natural Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (2017), SSCM implementation decision making cycle by Reefke *et al.* (2014) and the EMS model by Stapleton *et al.* (2001) have similarities and differences.

When it comes to the differences; the EMS model specifically aims at the environmental sustainability implementation which makes it different from the other two SSCM implementation processes. Also, unlikely the EMS model, the seven process steps of SSCM implementation and the SSCM implementation decision making cycle begins with analysing the

organisational supply chains and then analyse their sustainability practices. Another difference is that the seven process steps of SSCM implementation and the SSCM implementation decision making cycle discuss about utilisation of resources such as finance (liquid capital) and labour (human capital) when identifying or introducing actions or strategies. Finally, the seven process steps of SSCM implementation mentions the reporting of the sustainability activities as an important process step while the other two SSCM implementation processes ignore the reporting.

There is only one noticeable similarity between the three SSCM implementation processes. It is the evaluation of the implemented changes to the supply chain or in other words monitoring the effectiveness of implemented SSCM system.

In conclusion, none of the three implementation processes highlight the drivers pivotal to implement SSCM. Furthermore, they do not provide an in-depth understanding about what the barriers are when implementing the processes and how to overcome them to implement the processes successfully. The current research study found these questions as important when implementing environmental dimension of SSCM. Therefore, the current research study filled this gap while paying attention for the practical implementation process steps.

This section is aimed at guiding the UK SMEs in the construction industry to examine the implementation process of sustainable supply chain management and thereby achieve the research objectives. The next section (2.6.6) mentions the enablers to implement SSCM.

2.6.6 Enablers to implement sustainable supply chain management

According to Silvestre (2016), implementation of sustainability initiatives in the supply chain cause more sustainable business practices. The motivation is the main indicator that indicates the reason for the focus of these supply chains' money and energy on becoming more sustainable. The motivation develops with the risks associated as a result of not practicing sustainability and with the business opportunities of practicing sustainability. Further, Silvestre (2016) mentions regulators' policies, governmental laws, pressure from stakeholders and competitive advantage as some of the risks associated with not practicing sustainability and conversely, also mentions financial and other incentivisation tools such as future tenders for new works, positive reputational image among wider clientele etc. as opportunities of practicing sustainability initiatives.

Pressure from the stakeholders, demands of the customers, government regulations, resources of the organisations, competitive advantage and management of organisation's image are also generally classified as the motives to implement SSCM (Morali and Searcy, 2013; Bjorklund, 2011; Darnall *et al.*, 2008). Further, leadership across the supply chain is another factor that affects for the effectiveness and efficiency of the SSCM implementation (Bastas and Liyanage, 2018; Ansari and Kant, 2017). Also, the support and commitment of senior management towards SSCM activities leads organisations to implement and develop SSCM (Bastas and Liyanage, 2018). Incorporate emergency plans for any kind of disruptions in the supply chains in order to manage risk, strategy in agreement with organisation's overall strategy towards sustainability, communication with stakeholders to monitor the diverse supply chain operations and an organisational culture that promotes ownership and willingness to adopt ethical standards while focusing on the environment and society (Carter and Rogers, 2008). Apart from these motivators, the attention to minimize the negative environmental impacts leads organisations to implement SSCM (Paulraj, Chen and Blome, 2017). Meanwhile, Saeed and Kersten (2019), Oelze (2017) and Ahmed (2017) divide enablers for the implementation of SSCM in to external and internal enablers.

The next section (2.6.6.1) reviews the external enablers to implement SSCM.

2.6.6.1 External enablers for the implementation of sustainable supply chain management

According to Oelze (2017) the external enablers link with the context where an organisation operates. Supplier relationship with the organisation is mentioned as an example. Saeed and Kersten (2019) define the external enablers as external pressures and aspects that influence on internal actions of the organisation. Organisation's reputation, brand value, customer pressure, environmental and social legislations and pressure from the NGOs are also classified as external motivators to implement SSCM (Sajjad, 2015). While Ahmed (2017) mentions government, media, governance and global marketplace also as the external drivers, Saeed and Kersten (2019) categorise the drivers into three categories namely regulatory pressures, societal pressures and market pressures. Figure 8 illustrates the three categories and the drivers come under each category.

Figure 8: External Drivers of SSCM

ou a d (2019) c rd g e a e n (2019), t g o y d h e gional, national, e t l a t s a ons are important to initiate SSCM in an nisation. Societal i s a by the nonprofit organisations namely ie al roups and NGOs and by c ion ha nels such as n ha e olic awareness of organisation t na e formance. This awareness inf ue s he mpetition among pa s T a e ssure refers to the pressure m h market factors for instances e ha h llers.

Table 2 illustrates the literature that relates to each of the three drivers in re 8. Most of the studies have identified and t ed the competitive advantage which is l ified as a market pressure, media which is a fied as a social pressure and government l slations which is classified as a regulatory pre ures that lead organisations to implement S l. However, none of these studies have t d on UK construction organisations in the M l sector.

Table 2: Existing literature on external drivers of SSCM

External Drivers	Market pressure	<p>Organisations develop SSCM practices in order to achieve the competitive advantage (Vargas, Mantilla and Jabbour, 2018; Giunipero, Hooker and Denslow, 2012; Kleindorfer, Singhal and Wassenhove, 2005; Rao and Holt, 2005).</p> <p>Organisations practice SSCM as a result of competitors’ pressure (Hsu <i>et al.</i>, 2013; Harms, Hansen and Schalter, 2013; Zhu and Sarkis, 2007).</p> <p>Shareholders’ pressure leads organisations to implement SSCM as the shareholders are capable of withdrawing capital (Meixell and Luoma, 2015; Rivera-Camino, 2007).</p> <p>Organisations practice SSCM because of the institutional pressure from stakeholders (Gonzalez and Gonzalez, 2009).</p> <p>The pressure from the suppliers as a result of their fear of losing reputation, guides the organisations to implement SSCM (Gualandris and Kalchshmidt, 2014).</p> <p>Organisations get motivated to implement SSCM as a result of customers’ pressure to fulfill their demands (Bostrom <i>et al.</i>, 2015; Vural, 2015; Carter and Dresner, 2001).</p>
	Societal pressure	<p>NGO pressure on the organisations motivate them to implement SSCM and to reduce the emerging risks (Brandenburg and Rebs, 2015; Seuring and Muller, 2008b).</p> <p>Media exchanges information about sustainability issues which leads the organisations to practice SSCM (Govindan <i>et al.</i>, 2016; Mathiyazhagan and Haq, 2013; Seuring, 2013; Walker, Sisto and McBain, 2008).</p> <p>The public exert pressure on organisations to adopt SSCM as they developed understanding about the sustainability issues (Caniato <i>et al.</i>, 2012).</p> <p>The consumer organisations exert pressure on organisations to implement SSCM in order to create higher demand (Schrettle <i>et al.</i>, 2014).</p>

		The expectations of the communities and the welfare needs of the workforce exert pressure organisations to implement SSCM (social well-being / community focus) (Tate, Ellram and Kirchoff, 2010).
	Regulatory pressure	The government agencies develop legislations relate to workforces and environmental management that include fines for the organisations who do not consider the sustainability issues (Wu, Zhang and Lu, 2018; Taylor and Taylor, 2013; Koh, Gunasekaran and Tseng, 2012). Professional / trade associations have compliance requirements from the organisations in the associations' member list that make them which pressurised them into the implementation of the SSCM (Mzembe <i>et al.</i> , 2015).

(Source: Compiled by the author)

The following section (2.6.6.2) discusses the internal enablers to implement SSCM.

2.6.6.2 Internal enablers | im m i u s a s c ain management

According to Saeed and Kersten (2019), internal enablers (IE) relates to the organisation factors that are supported by the organisation to achieve its objectives. Oelze (2017) mentions several of the managers, supportive organisation literature, association of organisation strategies including sustainability strategy etc. as some of the internal enablers. Apart from the corporate culture and supply chain management are mentioned as further internal enablers (Saeed and Kersten, 2019). Economic optimism, management and social management are also classified as internal motivators (Saeed and Kersten, 2019). Furthermore, Saeed and Kersten (2019) mention four internal enablers namely corporate strategy, organisational culture, organisational resources and organisational characteristics. Figure 9 illustrates these four categories and their relationship in a category.

Figure 9: Internal Drivers of SSCM

ou and (2019)

2.6.6.3 Tri-oriented sustainable green SMEs

Meqdadi, Johnsen and Johnsen (2013) discuss the drivers of SMEs to implement sustainable management and organisation. It highlights the commitment, actual

concern of the management towards the welfare of the employees, values of the top/senior management and 'external drivers' which includes customer pressure, government pressure, regulatory pressure and laws. Alzawawi (2014) also mentions that many medium sized organisations view government regulations as drivers to implement SSCM in their organisations.

This section provides useful guidance to investigate the key drivers to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully in UK SMEs in the construction industry and to achieve the objectives of the current research study. The section 2.6.7 discusses the barriers to implement SSCM.

2.6.7 Barriers to implement sustainable supply chain management

The barriers to implement SSCM change according to the industry type, incentive system, reward system, managerial aspect of sustainability risk, public pressure and stakeholder pressure (Sajjad, 2015). However, there are internal and external barriers to implement SSCM (Ahmed, 2017; Oelze, 2017; Sajjad, 2015). Lack of process, lack of structure, lack of resources, cost, strategic issues, reputation risk, performance management, organisational size, corporate culture, stakeholders, functional issues and resistant to change are classified as internal barriers (Ahmed, 2017; Oelze, 2017; Pinto and Allui, 2016; Sajjad, 2015). Suppliers, media, government, global marketplace, customers, pressure from the competitors, lack of knowledge and regulatory issues are classified as external barriers (Ahmed, 2017; Oelze, 2017). Insufficient customer demand is another main external barrier that organisations view as impossible to overcome quickly as these external barriers require to collaborate with stakeholders in order to make changes in the sustainability perceptions (Sajjad, 2015).

Moreover, Ansari and Kant (2017) also mention barriers to implement SSCM although the authors do not separate the barriers as internal or external. The authors mention lack of training and expertise, lack of information and transparency, lack of leadership commitment, incapacibilities of suppliers, difficulties in reduction of energy and resource consumption, cost implications such as least capital cost, IT implementation barriers are also classified as boundaries for SSCM implementation.

When it comes to SMEs, they do not have expertise, finance, and technical resources to manage the sustainability of the supply chain (Pedersen, 2009). According to Meqdadi *et al.* (2013)

SMEs face barriers in implementing their customers' sustainability requirements and transferring these requirements to their suppliers. Also the suppliers do not engage or cooperate in sustainability activity implementation as they are aware that the SMEs are lack bargaining power, skills and resources. High cost associated with the implementation of SSCM, insufficient training, lack of experience and insufficient knowledge about SSCM are some of the barriers face by the medium sized organisations when implementing SSCM (Alzawawi, 2014). Further, Upstill-Goddard *et al.* (2016) mentions poor communication of internal organisations and within organisation as a barrier to implement SSCM in SMEs in the construction industry.

The section 2.6.7 is intended to assist organisations understand the barriers that UK SMEs in the construction industry face during the implementation of sustainable supply chain management and to achieve the research objectives. The following section provides an overview of small and medium enterprises.

2.7 Small and Medium Enterprises

There is no accepted definition for SMEs although researchers are interested in this area (Kot, 2018). Also another reason for not having a specific definition is the difficulty of defining SMEs beyond the quantifiable employee turnover or employee numbers (Ashby, 2014). According to Department for Business, Energy and Industrial Strategy (2018), a UK SME can be defined as an organisation that has 0-249 employees. Further, Department for Business, Innovation and Skills (2012), defines a UK SME as an organisation that has a turnover of less than £25 million.

Although the contribution of SMEs to the economy is considerable, they affect negatively on environment and society (Dey *et al.*, 2019). SMEs' perform in a competitive environment is the reason for the negative effects on the environment and society. For SMEs, it is important to generate business to keep floating and SSCM implementation helps them to achieve this target through generating more business (Upstill-Goddard *et al.*, 2016). Yet, SMEs consider sustainability as costly and unnecessary activity unless it generates financial benefits to them.

However, 'Larkfleet Limited' is one of the award winning constructions SMEs who practices SSCM successfully. The company was established in 1998 and currently situated Lincolnshire, UK. In order to achieve the environmental sustainability, the company focuses on building a

sustainable future by prioritizing the sustainable building methods and renewable energy technology (Larkfleet Group, 2021). Environment protection through wildlife protection, promoting greener ways of living and using low carbon building methods are the main targets of the company. Apart from the environmental sustainability, the social sustainability is achieved by providing training and skills opportunities for the workforce.

The objective of conducting comprehensive literature review of SMEs was achieved in this section. The following section (2.8) reviews the theories that relates to SSCM.

2.8 Theories Relating to Sustainable Supply Chain Management

2.8.1 Institutional theory

Institutional theory focuses on cultural, social and regulatory influences that encourage an organisation to sustain without concerning obvious economic return (Bruton, Ahlstrom and Li, 2010). In other words, external social pressures in particular coercive pressure (regulatory pressure), normative pressure (social pressure) and mimetic pressure (cultural pressure) lead organisations in implementing SSCM and gain social acceptance (Touboulic and Walker, 2015; Glover *et al.*, 2014). Institutional theory is helpful for managers in understanding the implementation of SSCM and the intention behind the implementation (Dubey *et al.*, 2016; Shi *et al.*, 2012). Also the theory explains the environmental and social dimension of SSCM (Seles *et al.*, 2016).

Further, DiMaggio and Powell (1983) discuss that the organisations are similar in form as a result of three isomorphic processes namely coercive isomorphism, mimetic isomorphism and normative isomorphism. The ‘coercive isomorphism’ is the political pressure that guides organisations through rewards, rules and approves (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). The pressure from the governments encourages organisations to adopt socially valuable practices (Berrone *et al.*, 2013). The coercive pressure or the government pressure is an important drive to implement environment management activities (Wang, Li and Zhao, 2018; Sarkis, Zhu and Lai, 2011). Therefore, the SMEs in the UK are more likely to implement environmental management practices as the concern about environmental issues has increased (Brammer, Hojmosse and Marchant, 2012). The ‘mimetic isomorphism’ is the pressure occurs with cognitive uncertainty (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). According to Aerts, Cormier and Megnan (2006), the cognitive

uncertainty occurs when organisations attempt to imitate successful environment related actions of the competitors while there are no clear stages of action. The ‘normative isomorphism’ is the pressure from non-government professionals (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983), either through interactions with professional associations or through training (Aerts *et al.*, 2006). The normative pressures drive organisations to implement environment management activities (Wang *et al.*, 2018). The SMEs in the UK adopt environment management practices as a consequence of professional pressures (Brammer *et al.*, 2012).

2.8.2 Resource based view theory

Resource based view (RBV) was introduced by Penrose in 1959 and consequently developed by Barney in 1991 (Gallego-Alvarez *et al.*, 2015). According to RBV theory, organisations have resources and capabilities as their strengths that guide them to make strategic decisions. Resources are the things that allow organisations to visualise and implement strategies that develop organisations’ efficiency and effectiveness. A resource or a capability that is rare, valuable, non-substitutable and inimitable helps an organisation to achieve sustainable competitive advantage and improve its performance. According to Alwan *et al.* (2017), there are several resources namely building information, workforce, hired equipment and place that are useful to construct a building.

Touboulic and Walker (2015) mention an organisation’s SSCM originates with its rare, valuable, non-substitutable and unique resources. Moreover, the organisation’s inimitable way of utilising those resources leads the organisation to implement SSCM. The theory suggests how an organisation gain competitive advantage focusing on sustainability based actions in supply chain. Shibin *et al.* (2017) agrees this idea and mentions that the resource based theory provides an explanation of organisational resources and their capability to gain competitive advantage. It also explains the economic and resource capability building of an organisation.

Comprehensive literature review on theories relating to SSCM was conducted in order to achieve the objective of the current research study. The next section (2.9) presents a conceptual framework that was used to maintain the focus of the current research study.

2.9 Conceptual Framework

Rossmann and Rallis (2017: 106) define a conceptual framework as a structure that organises the direction and focus of the study. This is the most important step in a research process as it directs the type of data that needs to be collected from a study. Qualitative researches necessarily use conceptual frameworks, when pursuing either an underdeveloped or a new research area (Hughes, Davis and Imenda, 2019). The current research study explores a new research area where there are no previous studies have been done. Therefore, it is necessary to keep the focus on data collection in order to fill the literature gaps.

Below conceptual framework (Figure 10) was developed to maintain the focus on the current research study's objectives that fill the literature gaps and to formulate the interview schedule (refer to Appendix 1). This conceptual framework consists with three parts in order to investigate the key drivers to implement SSCM successfully in UK SMEs in the construction industry, to examine the implementation process of SSCM in UK SMEs in the construction industry and to understand the barriers that UK SMEs in the construction industry face during the implementation of SSCM.

2.9.1 The drivers to implement SSCM

According to Omid, Ali and Saber (2019), identification of external and internal drivers and barriers is important to measure organisations' potential threats and opportunities in implementing SSCM. It develops predictions about potential SSCM implementation issues and to avoid implementation failures.

There are external drivers are government regulations and competitive advantage. The government legislations which classified as a regulatory pressure (Wu, Zhang and Lu, 2018; Taylor and Taylor, 2013; Koh, Gunasekaran and Tseng, 2012), competitive advantage which classified as market pressure (Vargas, Mantilla and Jabbour, 2018; Giunipero, Hooker and Denslow, 2012; Kleindorfer, Singhal and Wassenhove, 2005; Rao and Holt, 2005) and pressure from the media which classified as a social pressure (Govindan *et al.*, 2016; Mathiyazhagan and Haq, 2013; Seuring, 2013; Walker, Sisto and McBain, 2008) are the most discussed external drivers to implement SSCM. Among these internal drivers, the competitive advantage is often highlighted as the main driver for the implementation of sustainability (Zhang *et al.*, 2016).

SSCM needs multi-operational functions such as preventing excesses in operational functions, preventing resource wastage etc. to achieve competitive advantage (Su *et al.*, 2015). The influence and the pressure from the government regulations lead SMEs to implement SSCM in order to avoid any fines or penalties which they will have to pay for not following the legislations (Borasan and Xinyi, 2016). The current research included these three main external drivers into the conceptual framework in order to study whether they are important drivers specifically in the UK construction companies in the SME sector.

The internal drivers were adopted from Saeed and Kersten (2019), Ahmed (2017), Oelze (2017) and Sajjad (2015) as they all agreed with the below mentioned drivers in the figure 10. These drivers lead an SME to implement SSCM. Top management commitment which classified as a corporate strategy, the position of the supply chain which classified as an organisational characteristic and human resource which classified as an organisational resource are the most discussed internal drivers to implement SSCM in the literature. The corporate strategies drive organisations towards SSCM implementation as they are the directions and objectives of the organisations (Hsu, Tan and Zailani, 2016). The corporate strategy is a managerial decision, interpretation and a perspective which has an enormous influence on implementing SSCM with the focus of achieving competitive advantage. Managerial decisions are made by the top management who has the power to decide what plans to be implemented (Kausar, Garg and Luthra, 2017). Accordingly, the implementation of SSCM depends upon the commitment of the top management. The demands of the service users and the pressure from the stakeholders, force the top management to commit towards the implementation of SSCM (Walker and Jones, 2012). Available and adequate organisational resources such as human capital ease the implementation of the SSCM (Saeed and Kersten, 2019; Schrettle *et al.*, 2014). The current research included these three internal drivers into the conceptual framework to explore whether they are useful drivers for the UK construction SMEs.

2.9.2 The barriers to implement SSCM

Figure 10 adopted barriers namely financial constraints, scarcity of organisational resources, pressure from the competitors and lack of knowledge from Ahmed (2017), Oelze (2017), Ansari and Kant (2017), Sajjad (2015), Alzawawi (2014), Meqdadi *et al.* (2013) and Pedersen (2009) as they highlighted these barriers. The barriers are divided as internal and external. All of these

authors explain finance as an internal barrier to implement SSCM. According to Omid *et al.* (2019) organisations have to manage insufficient financial resources and high cost that involve with SSCM implementation. The next barrier is the lack of organisational resources. Once again, finance of an organisation plays an important role in gathering sufficient resources to implement SSCM (Oelze, 2017). Therefore, in order to implement SSCM successfully, both financial and insufficient resources barriers must be minimised or if possible eliminated in their entirety. The current research study included these barriers into the conceptual framework in order to clarify whether the UK construction SMEs face the same barriers and to clarify how they overcome from these barriers.

The pressure from the competitors and the lack of knowledge are the external barriers used in the conceptual framework of the current study. Although the literature mentions competitors' pressure as a barrier none of them explain how it really works. Therefore, the current research study added this by hoping to collect perceptions about this particular barrier as well. Then lack of knowledge or awareness about the benefits of sustainability is another main barrier to implementation of SSCM (Moktadir, 2017). The reasons behind lack of knowledge is the information gap, lack of commitment from the senior management, lack of education and training about sustainability and limited access to information.

2.9.3 The implementation process of SSCM

The literature identified three SSCM implementation processes as reviewed in the section 2.6.5. The researcher of the current research study wanted to have an open mind about all the three processes as there are no researches done on implementation process of SSCM in UK construction SMEs. Therefore, in the conceptual framework the title 'implementation process of SSCM' is presented without mentioning any specific process steps. The presented conceptual framework is useful to identify the drivers that lead the UK construction SMEs to implement SSCM and to identify barriers that needs to be removed in order to achieve success in the SSCM implementation.

Figure 10: Conceptual framework

(Source: Compiled by the author)

The section 2.10 summarises the literature review chapter.

2.10 Summary of the Chapter

In this chapter, the researcher has critically evaluated a comprehensive literature review on supply chain, supply chain management, sustainability, sustainable supply chain, sustainable supply chain management, implementation processes, theories and concept of SMEs in order to achieve the first objective of the current research study.

Supply chain of an organisation is the financial flow, material flow and information flow between the main contractors and the suppliers. Transparency, dependency and distance are the three dimensions of supply chain which helps to maintain efficiency of the supply chain. Supply chain in the construction industry highlights a non linear pattern as a result of the size and the complexity of construction projects. Managing these construction supply chains requires understanding of product's quality and services, logistics, organisations, activities, resources and information that transform raw materials in to a final product. In general, the supply chain of an organisation significantly contributes to the sustainability.

SCM has several definitions which began to define it as an organisational strategy, then as management of supply chain business activities, then as management of supply chain relations and then as the coordination of components and material flow. However, SCM helps the construction SMEs to secure their financial status through cost minimisation, revenue maximization and all assets utilisation. It also creates competitive advantages for the SMEs as a result of higher communication levels and responsiveness between them and the customers. The management of the supply chain is important to initiate sustainability practices.

This literature review explores diverse definitions of sustainability. Yet, the current research study highlights sustainability as the development that fulfils the needs of the present generation without compromising the ability of the future generation to fulfil their needs. The concept of sustainability is termed as "triple bottom line" which explains a balance between environmental, social and economic concerns in business contexts. There are direct, indirect and external sustainability performance indicators. Theses sustainability performance indicators are helpful when implementing SSCM as they generate the understanding about the sustainability characteristics and impacts of organisational activities.

Sustainable supply chain is the balance between environmental, social and economic concerns throughout the supply chain of an organisation. Implementation of sustainable supply chain is challenging as lack of knowledge, workforces' and suppliers' resistance to change, cost associate with implementation and as a result of lack of leadership commitment. Management of sustainable supply chain allows the suppliers to decide whether they want to incorporate the economic, environmental and social concerns with their business processes and it helps to minimise the challenges of sustainable supply chain implementation.

SSCM is a strategic integration of economic, environmental and social concerns into inter-organisational business system. It minimises the reputation risk, helps to achieve business growth, increases profitability and etc. There are three dimensions of SSCM namely environmental SSCM; social SSCM and economic SSCM. The environmental SSCM is the most important dimension as it makes positive impacts on the social and economic SSCM. It is an important study area. Yet, the literature review highlights the fact that the literature or the researches on SSCM in SMEs are underdeveloped.

Following review of the literature on dimensions of the SSCM, the current research study reviewed the three existing SSCM implementation processes namely seven step SSCM implementation process; SSCM implementation decision making cycle and environmental management system. However, none of these processes are from the UK construction companies in the SME sector. Therefore, the theoretical contribution of the current research study is a novel contribution for the existing knowledge.

Then a comprehensive literature review on institutional theory and resource based view theory was conducted as a result of the current research study's reviewed literature on enablers such as top management commitment, position of the supply chain, human resource etc. and barriers to implement SSCM such as finance, organisational resources, pressure from the competitors, lack of knowledge etc. None these existing literatures are from the UK constriction SMEs. Therefore, the theoretical contribution of the current research study is novel for the existing knowledge.

The conceptual framework that includes drivers, barriers to be removed and the implementation process (not a specific process) was developed after reviewing the sustainable literature critically in order to maintain the focus of the current research study when collecting and analysing data.

The most discussed drivers (top management, position of the supply chain, human resource, government legislations, competitive advantage and media) and barriers (finance, organisational resources, pressure from the competitor and lack of knowledge) in the literature were used in the conceptual framework as the researcher found them important. None of the implementation processes were included in the conceptual framework as there were three different processes mentioned in the literature.

The next chapter (chapter three) presents the research methodology which was adopted in the current research study.

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

“Methodology refers to how the researcher goes about practically finding out whatever he or she believes can be known” (Antwi and Hamza, 2015).

The current research study defines the research methodology as the plan used to obtain the research aim and objectives. The aim and objectives of the current research study were designed after reviewing the literature that indicates a research gap in implementation of SSCM in UK SMEs. In order to achieve the aim and objectives, the current study has developed the case study research methodology by identifying and defining the key criteria applicable to the UK construction companies in the SME sector such as the key drivers to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully in UK SMEs in the construction industry; the implementation process of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in the construction industry; the barriers that UK SMEs in the construction industry face in the implementation of sustainable supply chain management and the recommendations that can be utilised by UK SMEs in the construction industry to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully. The research methodology includes the entire framework of the practiced research process. It clearly describes the techniques used in selecting sample, data collection and data analysis in order to conduct a practical research investigation.

The researcher identified some published work with similar methodologies. One of them was the work done by Alhilou (2015) which adopted interpretive philosophy, inductive approach, exploratory research design, qualitative and multiple case studies as the research method. The data were collected through semi-structured interviews, observations and field notes. The qualitative thematic analysis was used to analyse collected qualitative data. The selected research methodology has helped the researcher to generate an in-depth understanding of a new insight about a phenomenon.

The current research methodology chapter comprised ten sections. The case study research methodology section (3.2) briefly discusses Yin's (2018) 'case study research methodology' and 'research onion' suggested by Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016) as they have quite appropriately and successfully assisted the researcher throughout the current chapter. Section 3.3 reviews the research philosophy followed by section 3.4 which mentions the research approach. Section 3.5 describes the research design which includes research choice, research strategy and research time horizon. Sample selection, ethical consideration and semi-structured interview schedule creation is discussed in the section 3.6. An overview of the data collection is presented in section 3.7 followed by data analysis in section 3.8. Audience identification and case study's format are discussed in reporting section (3.9). Validity (3.10) and reliability (3.11) are introduced as quality measurement of the research. The final section provides a summary of the chapter (3.12).

3.2 Case Study Research Methodology

The current research study followed Yin's case study research methodology (Figure 11). According to Yin (2018), a research can adopt case study research methodology if it aims to explain a contemporary phenomenon extensively. Ridder (2017) also mentions that the case study investigates real life phenomenon in-depth. Accordingly, the current research study adopts in-depth multiple case studies methodology to develop a new insight about the phenomenon of the implementation of sustainable supply chain management in the UK construction SMEs.

(Source: Yin, 2018)

The current study also utilised Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill's research methodological steps (Figure 12) when required in-depth explorative understanding about dynamic research component transactions in case study research. Also, the current researcher found critical insights from a literature analysis research, "Yin's work is like as one that does study research at hand as per its research methodology" (Day & Bagnoli, 2019: 18). Therefore, the current research's methodology is built up for the Yin's methodology. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2009) and modified it in the year 2016 in order to raise more comprehensive research questions. As shown in Figure 12, the inner circle of the onion (white and pink coloured layers) address the theoretical considerations while the outer layers address the practical considerations (Saunders *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 12: Research onion

(Source: Saunders *et al.*, 2016)

The academic researchers can argue that it is inappropriate to commence the methodology chapter by mentioning the methodological choice of the research. Having said that, there are no literature that indicates any restrictions to follow a specific structure to write a methodology chapter. However, the researcher of the current study preferred to have a logical structure for this chapter while explaining how the research was actually done. According to Silverman (2017: 471-480), the methodology chapter of a research needs to describe the way it was actually done. Considering the research gaps and the objectives of the current study, the researcher decided to use appropriate combination of both the figure 11 and 12 as a guide to structure this chapter logically. Section 3.2 was useful to develop the chapter without any confusions of the logical structure.

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3.3 Research Philosophy

Mohamed and Amr (2018), mention a research philosophy as the starting point of a research process. The 'research philosophy' is a system of assumptions and beliefs about the development of knowledge (Saunders *et al.*, 2016; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2009). In other words, research philosophy describes the development of knowledge as well as the nature of knowledge (Kellmerit, 2015) that is used in order to collect and analyse data about a phenomenon.

Somehow, philosophical consideration of a research is really important during planning stage of a research as it helps to clarify, recognize and identify or to adopt the suitable research design (Alotaibi, 2013) which includes research question, strategy, data collection procedure and analysis procedure (Khaldi, 2017). The research philosophy determines the objectives of the research. The research philosophical assumption shapes the nature of case study researches (Bhatta, 2018). Therefore, the current research study views the research philosophy as important at the end of the research equally to the beginning as it affects the conclusion of the research study.

According to Saunders *et al.* (2009), there were four main philosophies namely positivism, interpretivism, pragmatism, and realism. In 2016, the number of research philosophies has developed to five. They are namely positivism, interpretivism, pragmatism, critical realism and post-modernism (Saunders *et al.*, 2016).

The positivism research philosophy and the interpretivism research philosophy are the main methodological implications (Alotaibi, 2013). The positivism philosophy relies on scientific methods to find the underlying cause of a situation while interpretivism philosophy seeks to gain subjective understanding of a situation. Also, the researches that use statistical measurement and hypothesis are classified as the researches that use positivism philosophy while the researches that use in-depth investigation and a specific context to be studied are classified as the researches that use interpretivism philosophy (Saunders *et al.*, 2016; Saunders *et al.*, 2009; Carson *et al.*, 2001). Despite these main differences, the case study researches adopt both positivism and interpretivism research philosophies (Bhatta, 2018) according to the aim and objectives of the research. Yet, the current case study research adopted an 'open minded' approach as in

interpretivism research philosophy where it began to collect data without aiming at hypotheses testing.

The pragmatism research philosophy argues that it is not possible to know the truth and reality of an outcome of a practical research by only using positivism philosophy or interpretivism philosophy (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). As a solution the researches began to adopt a combination of both positivism philosophy and interpretivism philosophy that are recognised as the researches that use pragmatism research philosophy in order to contribute practical solutions for research questions (Saunders *et al.*, 2016; Saunders *et al.*, 2009; Carson *et al.*, 2001). The decision to adopt pragmatism philosophy is based upon ‘what works’ for the research in order to achieve the aim and objectives of the study (Mohamed and Amr, 2018). The current research study adopted interpretivism philosophy and not a combination of philosophies as it focused only on conducting an in-depth study about the implementation process of SSCM that includes the enablers and barriers which affect for the implementation of the process. The researcher did not perceive the currently available statistical measurements as helpful and in-depth enough to achieve the aim and objectives of the current research study.

Similar to interpretivism philosophy, post-modernism philosophy leads in-depth investigations of a phenomenon in order to challenge the established ways of knowing and thinking (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). On the other hand, critical realism research philosophy is the analysis of pre-existing structures of reality that form observable events or experiences. The realism philosophy relates to scientific enquiry and similar to positivism philosophy it assumes a scientific approach into knowledge development (Kellmerit, 2015). The current research study investigated a new phenomenon that has not being studied previously. As in the post-modernism philosophy and in the critical realism research philosophy, the current research study did not aim to challenge or analyse any established or pre-existing SSCM implementation processes.

The majority of empirical SSCM researches have adopted modeling as in Lin and Tseng’s (2014) study where they have developed a model to prioritise the competitive SSCM aspects, factor analysis as in Su *et al.* (2015) study which studies validity of the hierarchical structures to achieve SSCM aspects and descriptive statistics which were collected from surveys while few researches have adopted in-depth case study method to explore the SSCM (Lu, 2017). Therefore,

it has become difficult to justify the research philosophy of previous research studies in the SSCM.

However, the current research can be classified as a research that adopts interpretivism philosophical consideration as it conducted an in-depth investigation on the implementation of SSCM specifically in the context of SMEs in the UK construction industry in order to achieve the research objectives and to develop the knowledge. All the research objectives in the current study aim to gather in-depth information that does not provide any statistical outcomes. The understanding which was generated from the collected and analysed data has been used to provide recommendations for UK SMEs to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully. There are advantages and disadvantages of interpretivism philosophy.

3.3.1 Advantages and disadvantage of interpretivism philosophy

According to the literature there are multiple advantages of interpretivism philosophy. This philosophy generates understanding of a phenomenon that has several interpretations (Rahman, 2017). The diversity of the interpretations develops the in-depth understanding of the phenomenon (Pham, 2018). On the other hand, the disadvantage of the interpretivism philosophy is that it generates in-depth understanding of a specific phenomenon that makes it complex to generalise the findings into another phenomenon or a context (Cohen, Manion and Marison, 2017). Despite this disadvantage, interpretivism philosophy based has been used in the current study in order to gather in-depth data to achieve the objectives of the study.

The next section (3.4) illustrates the different approaches that can be used in researches and mentions the specific research approach which was used in the current research study.

3.4 Research Approach

Research approaches are the plans for research that extent the steps from broad assumptions to detailed methods of data collection, analysis and interpretation (Creswell, 2014). This plan involves with the decisions about the research designs or the procedures, data collection research method, data analysis research method and interpretation. The selection of the research approach is based on the research being studied.

Earlier, there were only deductive and inductive research approaches (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). But at present, there are three approaches including abductive research approach (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). A research that uses deductive approach starts with theory and then designs a strategy to test the particular theory. More specifically, the process of deductive research begins with theoretical ideas known to the researcher and then hypothesis development, data collection, data analysis, hypothesis confirmation or rejection and finally revision of theory (Bryman, 2016). In contrast, a research that uses inductive approach starts with data collection in order to explore a phenomenon and then develop a conceptual framework (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). A qualitative research that utilises the inductive approach aims to develop descriptions and conceptual frameworks out of data (Parahoo, 2014). But some methods that come under inductive research approach do not use a conceptual framework (Green, 2014). For instance grounded theory which comes under inductive approach does not use a conceptual framework as it generates a theory or theories from the data. According to Saunders *et al.* (2016), a research that uses abductive approach collects data in order to explore a phenomenon, discovers themes and explains patterns to develop a new or modify an existing theory which consequently tested through further data collection. The abductive approach follows a pragmatist perspective (Mitchell, 2018). It generates set of outcome predictions from the research, in other words a hypothesis to be tested.

Inductive research approach was being used in the current research where appropriate to achieve the research objectives and to develop the conceptual model in line with the research findings. This developed conceptual model is the theoretical contribution of the current study. Unlike in a research that uses deductive or abductive research approach, this research collected qualitative data to explore the implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs. Consequently, the researcher has decided that it is inappropriate to select deductive research approach as this research does not collect quantitative data that evaluates any hypothesis connected to an existing theory, nor does assume that conclusion must be true if the presumptions are true or does not test a theory. Also, the researcher decided not to select abductive research approach as this particular research method does not combine deductive and inductive approaches together; as it does not conduct a hypothesis testing and as it does not further test the developed theory or model. There are advantages and disadvantages of inductive approach.

3.4.1 Advantages and disadvantages of inductive approach

Limited number of studies discusses advantages and disadvantages of inductive approach. One of the advantages is that gathering information that highlights direct connection between the research objectives and findings (Liu, 2016). It also ensures the defensibility and transparency of the research design. This approach is capable of developing a generalised finding which was generated from collected specific data (Gale *et al.*, 2013). According to Machila, Sompaa and Muleya (2018), time consuming is the disadvantage of the inductive approach. Despite the disadvantages, the current research study used this approach in order to develop the conceptual model from the generalised findings and achieve the research objective of making recommendations for the UK construction SMEs who is planning to implement SSCM.

The next section (3.5) describes the research design of the current study. It also provides brief idea about research choices, research strategies and the time horizon which the current research study considered when finalising the research design.

3.5 Research Design

“Research design emerged as a recognizable field of study in the 1960s, at first marked on Design Method at Imperial College, London in 1962” (Akhtar, 2016: 69). The design of the research depends upon the data that needs to be collected in order to achieve the research aim and objectives (Yin, 2018). The research design aims to avoid data that do not address the research questions. Research choice, strategy and time horizon was used as the process of the research design which aims to answer the research question (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). Planning or designing a research fulfils either an exploratory, descriptive, explanatory or evaluative research or some combination of these purposes (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). The aim of this particular research was to explore the implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs which the researcher identified as a literature gap and according to fill this gap the researcher has designed the current case study.

The descriptive research design addresses specific subjects (Mayer, 2015) while gathering information on current state of phenomena (Rahi, 2017) as they exist. The main goal of

descriptive research is to observe the existing phenomena through surveys, content analysis or qualitative study (Atmowardoyo, 2018).

The exploratory research design search for new insights into phenomena and provides clarifications for unclear situations (Mayer, 2015; Dutton, 2013) as in the current research study. The exploratory research uses any research method such as survey, experiment and case study in order to answer the research questions that expect answers for 'what' questions (Yin, 2018). Yet, the exploratory research design most likely to underpin qualitative approach in order to develop new insight (Rahi, 2017). The exploratory research has advantages such as generates new insight; increases the researcher's familiarity of the problem; gathers information to clarify concepts and determines whether it is possible to attempt the research and disadvantages such as interpretation of the data can be biased and inconclusive answers (Swaraj, 2019).

The explanatory research design guides a research to find reasons behind the occurrence of a particular phenomenon (Rahi, 2017). Unlike in the exploratory research design, the explanatory research design mostly underpins quantitative approach in order to develop or test a theory. The explanatory research aims to answer "how" and "why" questions that leads to gather in-depth information about history, experiment or case study (Yin, 2018).

Despite of the identified disadvantages, the current research adopted exploratory research design where it develops a new insight about the phenomenon of the implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in order to understand the phenomenon through conducting in-depth individual interviews. Meanwhile, this particular research avoided producing more descriptive thesis as in descriptive research design. It also avoided relationship establishment between variables as in explanatory research design or developing comparisons between events as in evaluative research design. Further, the researcher found it was not necessary to achieve combined research purpose as this research does not aim to use mixed method research design.

The subsection 3.5.1 discussed the research choice of the current research study.

3.5.1 Research choice

In this section (3.5.1), blend of data collecting methods and analysing techniques is termed as the ‘research choice’ (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). There are three main choices namely mono methods (mono method quantitative and mono method qualitative), multiple methods (multi-method quantitative and multi-method qualitative) and mixed methods (mixed method simple and mixed method complex) (Saunders *et al.*, 2016; Saunders *e al.*, 2009). Using one data collecting method (either qualitative or quantitative) and a matching analysing technique is called as ‘mono method’ while using more than one data collecting methods and analysing techniques is called as ‘multiple methods’ (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). Using a combination of quantitative and qualitative data collection and data analysis techniques is called as ‘mixed methods’ (Saunders *et al.*, 2016).

According to Anguera *et al.* (2018), differences and the definitions of the multi-method and mixed methods are bewildering. Halcomb and Hickman (2015) also accept the confusion between the multi-method and mixed methods. Yet, the authors highlight that the mixed method research are capable of combining both quantitative and qualitative characteristics throughout the research process (e.g. from philosophical underpin to interpretation of the data) while multi-method research is only capable of collecting data using multiple methods (e.g. data collection through focus groups and interviews for multi-method qualitative research or data collection through survey and reports for multi-method quantitative research).

However, mixed method case studies are difficult to execute than case studies that use mono method and they address complicated research question than case studies (Yin, 2018). On the other hand, multi-method case studies help to expose multifaceted insights on a phenomenon (Chandrasekaran *et al.*, 2016). According to the researcher’s comparison on both mixed method and multi-method, multi-method is more suitable to adopt in a case study research.

Yet, this research used qualitative mono method as it aims to use qualitative method for both data collection and analysis, as it is more consistent with interpretivism philosophy and related with inductive research approach. The quantitative mono method was not used in as this particular research as it does not relate with positivism research philosophy, deductive research approach and does not examine relations between variables that provide statistical data.

The next subsection explains the research strategy of the current research study.

3.5.2 Research strategy

Research strategy “*is a process of collecting and interpreting of data with a clear objective*” (Rahi, 2017: 2). Case study, experiment, grounded theory, survey, action research, ethnography, archival research and narrative inquiry are the main strategies of research (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). The selection of suitable strategy depends on the research question, research objectives, available resources and available time duration (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). After considering all these factors the researcher has decided to adopt multiple case studies strategy (5 UK SMEs) as an opportunity to investigate a phenomenon (the implementation of sustainable supply chain management) that has to be studied.

Yin (2018) provides a twofold definition for case study. The first part of the definition describes the scope and classifies the case study as an empirical method that includes in-depth investigation of a current phenomenon (a case) when the boundaries between the real world context and the phenomenon are not clearly evident. The second part of the definition is about the features of a case study. The case study strategy needs these features or methodological characteristics when the context and the phenomenon are not evident in real world situation. The second part mentions “*a case study copes with the technically distinctive situation in which there will be many more variables of interest than data points, benefits from the prior development of theoretical propositions to guide design, data collection and analysis and finally relies on multiple sources of evidence, with data needing to converge in a triangulating fashion.*” (Yin, 2018: 15).

Multiple case studies select two or more cases that are assumed to be literal replications (studies with similar results) or theoretical replications (contrasting results) (Yin, 2018). The multiple case studies provide more valuable insights than a single case study that develops generalised findings. In the current study the 5 UK SMEs in construction industry which already has implemented sustainable supply chain management are selected by assuming that they are literal replications.

Then, the research that uses experiment strategy has a control group and an experimental group. ‘Pre-experimental design’ which involves a systematically selected uncontrolled group, ‘true experimental design’ which involves a randomly selected control group and experimental group

in order to collect quantitative data and develop mathematical analysis models and finally ‘quasi experimental design’ which involves systematically selected participants who can be controlled to a limit are the three approaches that apply while conducting and experimental research (Apuke, 2017). Unlike in the case study strategy, the experimental strategy purposely separates the context and the phenomenon, and then studies the phenomenon of interest (Yin, 2018).

On the contrary to the current research study, the grounded theory strategy formulates a theory about the phenomenon that was studied in a research (Hensel and Glinka, 2017). The grounded theory strategy is useful when performing a qualitative study that does not have formulated hypotheses but which maintains continuous contrasts and comparisons of literature to develop categories and codes that will be used in the theory.

Unlike the case study strategy, survey strategy was not suitable for the current research study as the strategy maintains limited ability to investigate the context (Yin, 2018) and as it correlates with the deductive approach. Similarly, action research strategy and ethnography strategy was not being used as the researcher has limited time duration to complete the research phase. Furthermore, the researchers who use ethnography approach live with the sample they study while this particular research does not require the researcher to live with the selected sample. Archival research strategy was also not being used as this research did not analyse any secondary data of the selected 5 UK SMEs to identify the specific 5 UK SMEs. Finally, this research aims to collect data that flow from specific unstructured research questions and not to collect stories of the participants similar to a narrative inquiry.

The next subsection demonstrates the research time horizon of the current research study.

3.5.3 Research time horizon

This research used cross-sectional study where the data was collected only once at a particular time (Bryman, 2016). The main reason to select the cross-sectional study is the short period of time which the researcher has to complete the research. According to Bryman (2016), cross-sectional study design mostly is used in quantitative researches. However, more often qualitative researches also use this study design if the data is collected through semi structured interviewing. Longitudinal study provides researchers the capability to study transformation and development

which requires long time duration (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, the current study did not use the longitudinal study.

The current research study found section 3.6 is important as it provides a clear idea about how the researcher got prepared for the data collection.

3.6 Prepare

In the current research study, the researcher paid more attention on sampling / case selection, ethical consideration and semi-structured interview schedule as prior preparation to collect the data. According to Yin (2018), good preparation begins with skills and values of the researcher. Asking good questions, listening, being adaptive, having an idea about the issue being studied and ethical considerations are the mentioned skills and values of the researcher. The current research study practiced these skills and values during the data collection preparation stage.

3.6.1 Sampling / case selection

As discussed in section 3.5.2, multiple case studies are the most appropriate research strategy for the current research study. According to Yin (2018), there are two main principles when selecting multiple case studies. First, selecting the cases with predicted a similar result which is called 'literal replication'. Second, selecting the cases with predicted contrasting results which is called 'theoretical replication'. The current research study selected the multiple case studies by predicting to collect similar results.

There are two sampling techniques namely non-probability (non-random) sampling and probability (random) sampling. The literal replication multiple case studies for the current research study were selected by using non-probability sampling as it aimed to use exploratory research design as explained in section 3.5. On the other hand, probability sampling was not adopted as it is not possible to select replicable case studies randomly and as the current research is not based on survey research design.

The current study used purposive sampling techniques, as it is useful to gather data and develop findings that can be generalised (Sharma, 2017). The researcher searched for the construction SMEs in the Companies House UK website and reviewed their annual reports to identify the

SMEs who have implemented sustainable supply chain management successfully. Then the researcher contacted those organisations. Some organisations provided their email addresses and asked to email information about the research but did mention they have busy schedules while others rejected to participate in the research. Although the researcher has sent the information to the organisations who wanted to know about the research, some did not acknowledge and one executive informed that they cannot participate.

Then the researcher contacted an engineer from a large construction organisation and collected contact details of nine construction SMEs in the UK that are deemed suitable for the research. The researcher studied these organisations' websites prior to contacting them and attempted to verify whether they are practicing the SSCM. All nine websites indicated minimum information about the social sustainability and provided minimum information about environmental sustainability through two organisational websites mentioned about economic sustainability. The next step of the researcher was to re-check whether these organisations are registered with the Companies House. After gaining a clear idea about the organisations, the researcher approached them and booked dates for face to face interviews. Thereafter, the sample to collect qualitative data was referred to the respondents (2-3 managers of each 9 UK SMEs) who gave their consent to allocate sometime for face to face interviews.

Table 3 indicates profiles of the sample of the current research study. The data collection of the current research study was interrupted by the corona pandemic and as a result two out of the nine (company F and G) construction companies refused to take part in the research study in order for them to allocate more time on construction project completion. The company H refused to participate in the research as they are unable to share more information apart from their activities that obey the government regulation. The company I refused to take part in the research as a result of the pressure from the main contractors. Yet, the data could be triangulated with the replicable data collected from the other participants in the sample.

Table 3: The profiles of construction SMEs selected

Company name	Number of employees	Industry (construction)	Location	Companies House registration	Published sustainability practices in the website	Data collected
Company A	28	Renovation	Luton, UK	YES	Social	YES
Company B	100	Infrastructure (mechanical and electrical)	Greenford, UK	YES	Social	YES
Company C	61	Groundwork	Surrey, UK	YES	Social and economic	YES
Company D	73	Electrical, plumbing and mechanical	Enfield, UK	YES	Social	YES
Company E	11	Renovation, groundwork and disability facilities	Bradford, UK	YES	Social	YES
Company F	27	Renovation, plumbing and electrical	Harrow, UK	YES	Environment, social and economic	INTERU-PTED
Company G	10	Renovation	Southall, UK	YES	Social	INTERU-PTED
Company H	13	Renovation	Hertfordshire UK	YES	Social	NO
Company I	46	Mechanical and electrical	Kent, UK	YES	Social	NO

(Source: Compiled by the author)

3.6.2 Ethical Consideration

Ethical issues occur at various stages of a research where the researcher has to manage them professionally (Sajjad, 2015). Informed consents, data protection, conflict of interests, participants' privacy, confidentiality, anonymity, trust, deception of participants and harm to participants are included in the ethical consideration. For the current research study, the researcher obtained ethical approval from the University of the West of Scotland (Appendix 2). The ethical issues related to the current study were discussed with the Director of Studies (DoS) and applied for the ethical approval. Accordingly, the current study has obtained ethical approval (Appendix 2) and the researcher has provided the ethical approval letter to all the participants in order to develop trust between the researcher and participants.

The participants of the current study were provided a brief overview of the study, information on the voluntary nature of their participation, information on their rights, information on how the confidentiality of the data will be protected and information on how the current study will maintain the anonymity of the participants. All these information were mentioned in a participant information sheet (Appendix 3). The researcher has emailed the participant information sheet all the participants prior to the interview and explained each information before the interview begins. Thereafter, they were given a consent form (Appendix 4) to sign and confirm their voluntary participation.

3.6.3 Semi-structured interview schedule

The current research used the figure 10 in the section 2.9 (conceptual framework) when developing the semi-structured interview schedule (Appendix 6). It helped the researcher to keep focus on the aim and objectives of the current research study.

The structure of the interview schedule began with the professional background of the participants. This helped the researcher to decide whether the participant is suitable for the research or not. Also, asking professional details helped the researcher to develop the flow of the interview.

Subsequent to the gathering of personal data collection, the questions moved to the wider scope of the SSCM. The researcher included more general questions about the topic by aiming to

clarify his / her understanding about SSCM. Therefore, the second question is aimed to gather an idea about the participant's general understanding of the supply chain management process within a particular construction SME. The next question (third question) was aiming to examine the participant's knowledge about sustainability in general and then the question systematically narrowed down (fourth question) specifically focus on the sustainability in the context of the specific organisation. The fifth and sixth questions were aiming to gain assurance that the selected participants are truly practicing the sustainability.

Then the researcher presented the specific questions related to SSCM. The question seven was included in order to clarify whether the interviewer and interviewee have the same understanding about the SSCM. Following question (question eight) was the presented to verify how long a SME can continue SSCM. After verifying that, the particular SME is practicing environmental sustainability for a sustained period of time, the interview then moves to collect of data on participant's understanding of the importance (question nine) and impacts (question ten) of practicing environmental sustainability.

The question eleven was included by focusing on collecting more detailed information about the barriers they have encountered when implementing SSCM. It is an objective of the current research to study the challenges faced by the UK construction SMEs during the implementation process and the solutions which they found practical and useful. The researcher intended to probe into this question in order to link each barrier for the process steps separately.

The question twelve, thirteen and fourteen were focused on the waste management. The reason to include these questions was to gain further clarifications about the variety of waste that produces by the construction companies annually and to gain an understanding about waste management as the construction companies are generating more waste than any other industry in the world.

The researcher decided to include the next question (question fifteen) as the SSCM is a collaboration of several companies. According to researcher's understanding, the whole supply chain has to be in the same line in order to have an effective SSCM. Also this question helped the researcher to clarify what kind of measure the construction SMEs have when selecting their suppliers.

The question number sixteen was included to gather data to achieve the research's objective. The question number sixteen was presented in order to probe into the on drivers used in implementing SSCM within the UK construction SMEs.

Similar to question number eleven and sixteen, the question number seventeen was presented in order to achieve the objectives of the current research. The researcher requested the participants to explain each process step in order to gather more in-depth data.

The question eighteen was included in order to have an understanding about the reason for not publishing the environmental sustainability in the organisational websites. The last question (question nineteen) was included as this research considers the UK construction SMEs who are willing to implement SSCM. The feedback from the participants who have already implemented SSCM will encourage and guide the audience to implement SSCM successfully.

After preparing the necessary documents and contacting the sample, the researcher began the data collection as discussed in the below section (3.7 data collection).

3.7 Data Collection

Unlikely in the quantitative research where data collection is done by using closed ended questions, the data collection by qualitative research method is done by using open ended questions which might change while conducting the data collection (Mayer, 2015). Apart from the interviews, the qualitative case study researches use documents and observation to collect data and facilitate the validity of the collected data by triangulation (Ridder, 2020). Unlike questionnaires, the semi-structured interviews provide opportunities for the researcher to make changes for the themes and questions if they do not provide any valid information (Saunders *et al.*, 2009). Furthermore, it also allows the researcher to probe in to the crucial information. The researcher did not use structured interviews as this research does not look for statistical data. On the other hand, unstructured interviews were not used either as the researcher had to direct the participants to elaborate further in order to achieve the research objectives.

The basic knowledge about this particular research was developed further through the literature review. This helped to justify identified literature gaps. The researcher aimed to collect data in

order to fill these gaps and the focus of the data collection was maintained through the conceptual framework. The conceptual framework was helpful to develop the semi-structured questionnaire (Appendix 1) which was used to gather primary data as this research aims to adopt exploratory research design and used data triangulation in order to facilitate the validity. The interviews were one to one interviews where the researcher interviewed only one participant of an organisation at a time. A list of participants are mentioned in the below table (Table 4). The interviews (company A, B, C and D) were held face to face at the participants' company premises and the interviews with participants of the company E were conducted as a face to face Skype interviews as a result of the lock down. All the interviews lasted for about 45 minutes to one hour. The researcher observed the active environment of the construction companies while waiting to be invited to conduct the interviews. The pressure of the top management to complete the construction projects on time was observed during the interviews as there were interruptions for the interviews as they had to answer specific questions raised by the workforce. It was challenging for the researcher to keep the participants on focus of what they mentioned before the interviews were interrupted. At these times the researcher restated what they mentioned and motivated the participants to continue with the interview.

Additionally, a researcher must have an inquisitive mind in order to present appropriate questions and develop a rich dialogue with evidence (Yin, 2018). Not only that, a researcher must be a good listener who has the ability to understand large amounts of new information without bias. Also, having a basic knowledge of the study area helps researchers to collect all the necessary data without missing any important information. Finally, a researcher must attempt to maintain higher ethical and moral standards while collecting data.

Table 4: Case study participants

Case study	Number of Interviewees	Job titles
Company A	02	Director General Manager
Company B	02	Director Finance Manager
Company C	02	Director Purchasing Manager
Company D	03	Managing Director Non-Executive Director HSQE and Sustainability Director
Company E	02	Director Assistant Manager
Total	11	Directors Top Level Managers

(Source: Compiled by the author)

The section 3.8 discusses the data analysis method in the current study.

3.8 Data Analysis

This research has adopted thematic analysis method to conduct cross-case analysis of the transcribed (Appendix 7) qualitative data by using the NVivoTM qualitative data analysis software (Appendix 8). The advantages of the cross-case analysis are the case content is made available to the researcher in an easily accessible form; cases are clustered and represented in a visual display to facilitate comparison by the researcher and by others; cases are compared in a method that either centers on the case or on the variables, depending on the goal of the researcher and findings of the case and the cross-case comparison are shared with others (Khan and VanWynsberghe, 2008). As this research aims to use inductive research approach, the analysed data provided specific themes and issues to concentrate on. Therefore, the researcher did not need to pay attention to the themes that have identified in previous researches. This research followed six phase process of thematic analysis. These phases are namely familiarising with

data, generating initial coding, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes and finally producing the report (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The thematic analysis organises and combines findings from large and diverse body of research (Pope, Mays and Popay, 2007).

The section 3.9 discusses reporting style of the current study.

3.9 Reporting

Case study conclusion reporting means bringing its findings and results to an end (Yin, 2018). The method of reporting the research increases the quality of the study (Yin, 2018; O'Brien *et al.*, 2014). In order to report the conclusion of the case study, the current research identified the audience and defined case study's reporting.

3.9.1 Audience identification

The current research study identified the construction SMEs who are willing to implement the environmental dimension of SSCM and academic colleagues who aim to study this particular phenomenon as the potential audiences for the current case study. The section 1.3 (Research Gap) and the chapter two (Literature Review) of the current research were useful when identifying the potential audience for this particular research study. The researcher reported a theoretical contribution that is useful for the academic colleagues' audience while reporting a practical contribution for the construction SMEs audience.

3.9.2 Case study's format

According to Yin (2018), there are four case study formats when reporting. 'Single-case study' is the first case study format that develops a single text to report the case study. 'Multiple-case study' is the second format that produces a report with separate chapters or sections for each case study consists an additional section or chapter with cross-case analysis and results. 'Option for either single- case or multiple- case study' is the next reporting format that based upon questions and answers in the case study database. The final format is the 'option for multiple-case study only' consists of separate cross-case issue in each chapter and section.

The current research study adopted the ‘multiple-case study format’ for the case study report. The reporting of the multiple case studies begins by providing overviews of the case studies as separate sections for each case study (refer to chapter 4). According to Yin (2018), the audience needs to begin making their own cross-case comparison and it can be achieved only by reporting the multiple-case studies separately. Then the chapter 5 (data analysis) provides a cross-case analysis and results of the multiple-case studies.

3.10 Validity

The validity of a qualitative research is defined as the appropriateness of the selected research methodology, analysed data and the appropriateness of the conclusion for the context and the sample (Leung, 2015). It is one of the main features that evaluates the quality of the research (Haradhan, 2017). However, the validity is measured better in quantitative studies than in qualitative studies as there is no universally accepted criterion to evaluate validity (Hayashi, Abib and Hoppen, 2019). Therefore, the qualitative researchers have to focus on generalisability of the findings in order to increase the validity or in other words trustworthiness of the research (Golafshani, 2003). According to Yin (2018), the validity of case studies can be increased by using multiple sources of evidence (triangulation of the data). The current research study addresses the validity by using multiple sources of evidence in order to gather in-depth data to achieve the research objectives mentioned in the chapter one (section 1.5). Multiple sources such as documents and observations are used to understand the case studies while using in-depth interviews to collect data that increase the validity of the research.

3.11 Reliability

Reliability of a qualitative research is defined as following the same procedures which is practiced by an earlier researcher and conducting the same study over again to gather the same findings (Yin, 2018). It is another feature that assesses the quality of the research (Haradhan, 2017). The reliability of the qualitative research depends on the consistency of the data over time (Hayashi *et al.*, 2019; Leung, 2015). The current research study explores a new insight to the research area and does not aim to replicate a research that is done previously. Future researchers can follow the same procedures to gather the same findings as in the current research study and that will be reliability measurement of the research.

3.12 Summary of the Chapter

The research methodology chapter began with an introduction which includes the subheadings at the bottom of the introduction section. Thereafter, it described how the case study methodology of the current research study was developed by combining ‘the case study research process’ and ‘the research onion’ in order to maintain a logical structure for the methodology chapter.

The research philosophy section explained positivism, interpretivism, pragmatism, critical realism and post-modernism. It justified interpretivism as the suitable research philosophy for the current study in order to gather in-depth data to achieve the objectives of the study. Then the chapter moved to research approach section and explained it is necessary to select inductive research approach over the deductive and abductive research approach for the purpose of developing the conceptual model from the generalised the findings and achieving the research objective of making recommendations for the UK construction SMEs who is planning to implement SSCM.

The research design section explains descriptive, explanatory and evaluative research design while highlighting exploratory as the suitable research design for the current research study as it develops a new insight about the phenomenon of the implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in order to understand the phenomenon through conducting in-depth individual interviews. The research design section explains this research as a cross-sectional multiple case study that uses mono method qualitative research choice to collect and analyse data.

The chapter then mentions how the current research study is prepared for the data collection by selecting suitable sample cases, by taking action to gain ethical consideration and by developing semi-structured interview schedule. The data collection section and data analysis section mentions about the qualitative characteristics used in the current research. Finally, the chapter provides a clarification about the audience, case study’s format and review collection in order to achieve the quality expected from this report.

The chapter four provides overviews of the selected case studies.

CHAPTER FOUR: CASE STUDIES SUMMARIES

4.1 Introduction

According to Yin (2018), when conducting multiple case studies each case should have individual case report that leads to a cross-case conclusion. In the current chapter (chapter four), the researcher introduces the case studies or/and companies who participated in the research study. It provides individual case summary sections instead of providing case reports as it only generates basic ideas of the selected multiple-case studies and to make the audience to begin making their own cross-case comparison.

The case study summaries begin with section 4.2 which briefly introduces the case study one (Company A) and moves to section 4.3 which provided an brief introduction of case study two (Company B). Section 4.4 discusses about the case study three (Company C) followed by a brief introduction to the case study four (Company D). The fifth case study is introduced in section 4.6 (Company E). Each of these case study introduction sections discusses the company aim, supply chain system of the company and sustainability practices of the company. The final section (4.7) provides a summary for the chapter.

4.2 Case Study One (Company A)

4.2.1 Introduction

Company A was established in 2015 with just two employees and remains as a small construction organisation with 28 employees. This private limited company is situated in Luton. The company has 5 years of experience in renovation. The renovation projects include commercial and domestic property repair and refurbishment. This company takes responsibility for simple renovation projects and such no complex renovation projects such as renovation of damaged and/or dilapidated properties are renovated. The organisation's renovation works include wide range of services ranging from cleaning, brickwork, carpentry and joinery, decorating, plastering to plumbing and water supply, replacing gas and electricity with full guaranteed professional service.

The company focuses on its clients and accordingly they have developed the company objectives. The company aims to be flexible to each demand and / or every need of their projects, whilst maintaining a helpful and friendly approach. The company has an outstanding reputation, repeat businesses and receives regular recommendations from their clients due to the above flexible and friendly approach and their attention to detail approach.

4.2.2 Supply chain system

Company A has a unique supply chain for each project they complete. The reason behind this uniqueness is the diversity of the construction projects that they have to complete. The end users have different ideas and needs that they expect to be fulfilled by their contractors. Therefore, they provide information about what needs to be done, how they prefer it to be done and their budget. All these ideas, concepts, needs and other related information of the end users' or the clients' are unique from one to another.

It is a small company that has to work under main contractors who manages the information flow. The main contractors gather information from the end user and pass them to the designers who allocate duties and restriction for the company A in relation to a particular given project. Therefore, the client of the company A is the main contractor.

4.2.3 Sustainability

The company A practices environment sustainability and social sustainability. Yet, the company has provided limited information about the social sustainability of the company. It mentions that the welfare of the workers is assured as the company provides them training about the emergency procedure, safety helmets and the first aid boxes are placed in the sites. Moreover, the company makes sure that the workers are not under any pressure. Therefore, the sites open from 8.00 a.m. to 4.00 p.m only on weekdays. The company makes sure all the supervisors understand that they are working in line with the health, safety and environment legislations including Construction Design and Management Regulations 2015 and Environmental Permitting Regulations 2010 in the UK.

4.3 Case Study Two (Company B)

4.3.1 Introduction

Company B was established in 1988 as a specialist electrical sub-contractor. Currently, it is a medium sized construction company that is situated in the Silicone centre in Greenford. The company has worked in multi-disciplinary projects throughout the last 30 years. These multi-disciplinary projects include infrastructure renewals in particular boiler and air handling plant upgrading, systems refurbishments without disrupting the tasks of the day to day activities of the specific building, office layout upgrades, building service maintenance, refurbishment of abandoned office spaces in to residential buildings and luxury homes / apartments and extra low voltage installations to enhance energy management and security infrastructure of the building.

The company focuses on the workforce of the company and accordingly they have developed the company aim. The aim of the company B is to grow progressively and naturally by recruiting the most suitable person for the most suitable position and encouraging their self development. The company provides number of apprenticeships and training programmes in conjunction with universities to develop the skills of its workforce. The company has three main principles primarily centred on their workforce and the clients. They are empowering the workforce, improving their working environment and listening to the needs of their clients. None of the main principles discusses about the environmental management system or environmental sustainability.

4.3.2 Supply chain system

The company B has a diverse supply chain system. In order to fulfil the unique needs of their end users or the clients, the construction company had to purchase different building materials. Consequently, the company A has to use number of manufacturers and suppliers to supply the materials and equipment they need such as lights to pipes, wires, cables, switches etc.

There are many people involve in the supply chain of company. It includes the end clients, the designers, the main contractors, raw material manufacturers and suppliers, specialist equipment suppliers etc. The company has specific suppliers for each project according to their complexity.

4.3.3 Sustainability

Company B practices a combination of environmental sustainability and social sustainability. It maintains the standard of the environment sustainability throughout the supply chain through assessing the sub-contractors. The company achieves business sustainability through social sustainability.

The company website has provided very limited information about social sustainability of the company. It mentions that the philosophy of the company as exceed quality, expectations and within budget while maintaining a safe environment for its workforce. The company mentions its workforce as the main resource for its success.

The company has published its environmental policy statement in the company website. It mentions that the top management will communicate the importance of environmental management system; make sure that the environmental management system is integrated into the company's business processes; make sure that the resources are available for the environmental management system; conduct internal audits of the environmental management system and provide direction and guidance for its employees to follow the system.

Further, the brochures provide by the company mentions that the company has developed an application software where they would be able to interact with their clients and to maintain transparency of the project development. Therefore, paper waste and unnecessary printing has reduced significantly within the day to day company working environment.

4.4 Case Study Three (Company C)

4.4.1 Introduction

Company C was established in 1986 as a specialist groundwork company. It is a medium sized construction company which is situated in Bookham village in Surrey. The company builds reinforced concrete frames and engages in groundwork. Groundwork includes drainage, excavation, highway roads, landscaping pavement and foundations. The employees of the company have more than 30 years of experience in the industry. The duration of the company and the experienced employees have become the reasons for the high standard service demand by its clients.

The company focuses on the quality of the projects and has developed the company's aim to be in line with them. The aim of the company is to develop systems that provide high quality for each groundwork project. The company selects suppliers who have the same goals in order to achieve the company aim. The quality of the projects the deliver leads the company to achieve higher reputation and repeat businesses.

4.4.2 Supply chain system

The supply chain of the company C is a combination of British certified sustainable companies. The company conducts certificate checks for the suppliers who supply materials and follows procedures such as BREEAM. The company as a second tier contractor follows the main contractors' instructions when completing a project. Therefore, it has a unique supply chain.

4.4.3 Sustainability

The company C practices sustainability as they are concern about the future generation. They practice social, environmental and economic sustainability. The company invests its won money to purchase new mechanical equipments. So that it does not have to spend extensively on hired machinery. This leads the company to achieve profits and also to operate more effectively on sites. When it comes to the social sustainability, the company invests in several health and safety training programmes for its workforce. The health and safety advisors regularly visit the construction sites, produce reports and provide advice to the company in order to maintain the high standard expected and provide updates about the developing world on health and safety.

4.5 Case Study Four (Company D)

4.5.1 Introduction

Company D is a medium sized construction organisation that is situated in the Wenta business centre in Enfield. The company focuses on electrical, plumbing and mechanical aspects of a project. The 'company D' was established in the year 2013. Highest standard of service delivery and customer services rendered by the workforce lead the company to achieve a quick growth over the last few years. The aim of the company D is to complete the projects to the client's satisfaction and complete them right first time. The company adapts to the necessary changes on projects with minimal costs or time impact in order to ensure the clients are satisfied and also to achieve the planned outcome.

4.5.2 Supply chain system

The company D is a subcontractor who does minimum level of project designing and who follows the instruction of the main contractor. The company has a unique supply chain as it follows the instruction from the main contractor even when purchasing materials. It has a supply chain which includes the suppliers with same beliefs and practices. Also, the company expects the suppliers to achieve registration requirements such as Fleet Operator Recognition Scheme (FORS).

4.5.3 Sustainability

The company D practices environmental, social and economic sustainability. Sustainability practices have been there from the beginning of the company. The company has redefined its processes, has formed forensic quality checks and has established innovative tools to protect the environment, property and people. The company makes commitments to sustainability practices as its behaviour as an employer affects its team, as its working practices affects communities and as its performance standards affects its customers, end users and the environment.

The company D practices social sustainability by conducting safety training programmes for employees in order to protect them at work. Also the company uses high technology personal alarm system to notice any falls from height and take immediate actions for injured employees, if any. This device helps them save lives at work.

Further, the company operates a Forensically Controlled Installation System which includes Quality Labels and Quality Control Numbers and also conducts manufacturers' quality audits in each site. The completion of forensic quality checks helps the company to allocate tasks for individuals and to educate employees who have not reached the level required by company's quality standards.

4.6 Case Study Five (Company E)

4.6.1 Introduction

Company E has more than 20 years of experience in the construction industry. It was established in 2001 as a disability facility grant work specialist company which is situated in Bradford. Currently, the company is conducting extensions, loft conversion, dormers, chimney construction and plumbing. The aim of the company is to provide high quality services to their clients. The company takes approval from the local building control department for each step they take in order to maintain the quality of the work. Also the company's attention to detail approach let the project to complete on time thus eliminating the unnecessary delays caused by budget management issues. This is the main reason for the company to achieve a very good reputation.

4.6.2 Supply chain system

The supply chain of the company E is a system that moves information, services and materials from local council and supplier to customers. For that the company uses all local suppliers and recognised traders. The supply chain of the company is diverse from project to project. The diverse supply chain systems are based on the clients' requirements, time duration and applicable rules and regulations of the local authority.

4.6.3 Sustainability

The company practices social and environmental sustainability. The sustainability of the company depends upon the understanding of health and safety of the workforce. The company views well-being, safety and health of the workforce as important when operating the business. The continuous monitoring of safety progress helps the company to ensure that the safety programmes are working effectively. The workforce has the right to ensure zero tolerance of any action which could result in ill health and accidents.

4.7 Case Study Comparison

Table 5: Case study comparison

Company Name	Established Year	Location	Specialised Area	Supply Chain System	Sustainability Practices
A	2015	Luton	Renovation	Unique supply chain	Environmental & social
B	1988	Greenford	Infrastructure (mechanical & electrical)	Unique supply chain	Environmental & social
C	1986	Surrey	Groundwork	Unique supply chain	Environmental, social & economic
D	2013	Enfield	Electrical, plumbing & mechanical	Unique supply chain	Environmental, social & economic
E	2001	Bradford	Renovation, groundwork & disability facility	Unique supply chain	Environmental & social

(Source: Compiled by the author)

The five construction SMEs were established in different years and located in different areas in the UK. All the case studies were construction SMEs who specialised in different areas such as renovation, infrastructure, groundwork, electrical, plumbing, mechanical and specialised in disability facility construction. These specialisations highlight all the activities in the construction field.

All the five case studies have unique supply chains for each project as they have to maintain the diversity of the construction projects. The end users pass the information about their needs to the main contractors and the main contractors pass that information down to the SMEs through the

designers. Therefore, the construction SMEs are bound to fulfil the needs of the end users, main contractors and the designers.

The five construction SMEs are practicing the environmental sustainability and the social sustainability while only the company C and D practice all three sustainability practices that includes the economic sustainability. As mentioned in the case study summaries the companies follow the UK government regulation, have environmental policies and conduct product quality checks in order to maintain the environmental sustainability practices. The companies conduct safety training programmes for the workforce as the main system to maintain the social sustainability. The company C maintains the economic sustainability by using own mechanical equipments and it helps to save money without spending on hired machinery.

4.8 Summary of the Chapter

The current case study summary chapter provides a brief understanding about the selected multiple case studies. It provides backgrounds of the companies which included the established year, specialised area, where the specific company is situated and aim of the company. The supply chain system of each company was presented as explained by the participants. Thereafter, it provides the sustainability practices of each company. The summary of the case study two (company B) mentioned the principles of the company while all the other four companies have not published their principles.

The chapter five analyses the collected data from the multiple-case studies and develops a cross-case analysis.

CHAPTER FIVE: DATA ANALYSIS

5.1 Introduction

As has explained in the research gap section of the current study, concerns have been expressed about the knowledge gap within the SMEs on how to integrate SSCM in their companies. It was also evident that insufficient attention has been given to the studies on motivators and barriers to implement SSCM. In addition, no previous research had been carried out on implementation of sustainable supply chain management in SMEs in the UK construction industry. This data analysis chapter fills these research gaps by analysing the collected qualitative data. It also achieves the objective of investigating the key drivers to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully in the UK SME sector, examining the implementation process of sustainable supply chain management in the UK SME sector and understanding the barriers that UK SMES encounter when the implementing sustainable supply chain management.

The data has been analysed thematically with the help of NVIVO software. The themes are sustainable supply chain management, impact of sustainable supply chain management on the SMEs in the construction industry, different aspects of sustainable supply chain management, environmental sustainable supply chain management, waste generation of SMEs in the construction industry, waste management of SMEs in the construction industry, environmental sustainable supply chain management's impact on SMEs in the construction industry, sustainable supply chain management implementation, process, motivators, barriers and solutions.

The current chapter commences with section 5.2 which covers data analysis and interpretation of important terms of the current research study in order to motivate and to develop the understanding of the construction SMEs who are planning to implement SSCM. Sub-section 5.2.1 analyses the collected data on SSCM followed by the analysis of the collected data on environmental SSCM (5.2.2). The data collected on process, motivators, barriers and solutions are analysed under the SSCM implementation sub-section (5.2.3) in order to achieve the objectives of the research. Section 5.3 concludes the chapter by providing a summary.

5.2 Data Analysis and Interpretation

5.2.1 Sustainable supply chain management

The theme (5.2.1) analyses the data collected on the impact of SSCM on SMEs in the construction industry and the differing SSCM aspects that construction SMEs practicing. The construction SMEs who intend to implement SSCM must gain a clear understanding as to whether their companies will have a positive impact or not. After the impacts are understood, they need to gather information about what type or types of SSCM aspects that is important for their companies. The below subthemes (5.2.1.1 and 5.2.1.2) develops the necessary understanding for the construction SMEs to use when implementing environmental aspect of SSCM.

5.2.1.1 Impact of sustainable supply chain management on the SMEs in the construction industry

When the researcher questioned about the impact of SSCM on the participants' companies, most of the respondents expressed views about securing work as the construction companies are based on the construction and demolition projects. Furthermore, some of the respondents stated that the SSCM impact on their companies are not significant as they acquire more projects based on personal contacts, based on price and having correct ethics and policies in place. This is evident from the following responses of the participants.

“Partially yes. Nowadays technology has made everything closer to the browsers. So the clients who want to use construction companies that use sustainable practices will directly contact them. But still they will give priority for their personal contacts. So, sustainable supply chain impacts on the organisation for a certain percentage” (The general manager of company A).

According to the general manager of the company A, the work safety measures of the construction companies depends on the number of works they acquire through personal contacts. Consequently, publishing sustainability practices in the company websites and practicing SSCM are not necessarily the main drivers for a client to select a specific construction company. The respondent had the understanding that the clients browse the company website. Yet, only the

social sustainability practices are published in the company website. The researcher of the current research therefore predicts that the respondent has not demonstrated a genuine interest to include environmental sustainability within their website as they perceive this as an insignificant factor to win construction projects. It is important for the construction SMEs who are planning to implement SSCM to understand that personal contacts as a resource can have a positive impact on acquiring increased number of contracts.

The respondents further described that the securing work is not much depended on the SSCM practices of the companies but on the price they quote for a construction project. This is evident from the statement of the managing director of company B.

“Well ironically.... Although with our standard, with our ISO, with our policies, with our initiatives, with the sponsorships and a lot of variety of things, unfortunately that still cannot count as securing the work. The works secured, 8 to 9 times out of 10 are on price..... There are elements that we did not have correct ethics and policies to follow and we obviously lost them.” (The managing director of company B).

The managing director of company B mentioned that the company practices ISO environment standards and mentioned that the company has environment policies in place. Yet, the respondent did not perceive these actions as the main causes to expand the business and secure work and highlighted price as the main driver. The respondent nevertheless stated that their company could not secure work when the company did not have the correct policies in place. Therefore, the company’s work security nine out of ten depends on price while one out of ten could depend on the SSCM practices. The construction SMEs who are planning to implement SSCM must maintain a balance between the price and the SSCM policies in order to increase the number of contracts they achieve.

Further, the respondents mentioned that the impact of the SSCM on construction SMEs as an element that vary with the size of the construction project. This is evident from the response of the assistant manager of company E.

“It does have a significant impact on the company in case of bigger projects but in case of small project at times the clients choose the service of the company based on the

personal contacts and based on their budget. So I would say the impact is relevant to the project size” (The assistant manager of company E).

According to the assistant manager of company E, the clients or the main contractors of bigger construction projects are interested in the SSCM of construction SMEs as those projects generate more waste and as it is the client’s or the main contractor’s responsibility to make waste management plans. Therefore, in such circumstances the main contractors prefer to hire construction SMEs who already have SSC mechanisms in place in order to reduce waste generation and also to reduce costs associated with waste disposal. On the other hand, the work security from smaller projects depends on personal contacts and the price just as in company A and company B. The construction SMEs that plan to implement SSCM should view their decision as a significant factor that will convey the main contractors to offer bigger contracts for the company that generates more profits.

The supply chain of the construction industry is a unique chain which consists of group of companies or people. The impact of the SSCM is different for each member in the whole supply chain. The director of company C justifies this situation.

“Yes, it all depends with where you are within the supply chain of the industry. Our impact is within the lower range. Ultimately, engineers and architects have greater impact on such things” (The director of company C).

According to the response from the director of company C, each company of the supply chain has impacts of the SSCM on their companies. The companies in the tier one such as the designer and the main contractors would have massive impact on their companies as they are the first line of contacts or scrutiny on large scale projects. The end user of the construction project selects the main contractor depending on its SSCM practices. Then a main contractor obtains a project then only their subcontractors will need to prove the existence of SSCM practices within their organisations. The director of the company C admits that construction SMEs have positive impacts of practicing SSCM unlikely the responses of the general manager of company A, the managing director of company B and the assistant manager of company E. Therefore, it is evident that there are positive impacts on the construction SMEs who are planning to implement SSCM in terms of achieving construction contracts and increasing the profitability.

The next impact of the SSCM on construction SMEs is that it increases the company's reputation or competitive advantage while increasing the profitability.

"It helps us to achieve the competitive advantage and make more profits to the company"

(The finance manager of company B).

The finance manager of company B mentioned that the company B achieved the competitive advantage by practicing SSCM. Practicing SSCM impacts on the decisions of the end users and / or the clients when they decide to apply SSCM across all elements of the construction project. The SMEs in the construction industry depend on the profits they generate. Therefore, gaining more construction projects by practicing SSCM increases the advantage of profit generation. More profit generation impacts on the reputation of a company. The construction SMEs who are willing to implement SSCM must understand the positive link between SSCM practices, securing work, profits generation and competitive advantage.

"Yes, financially it has a bigger impact on us. As I mentioned we pay attention on health and safety of the employees. So I would say that the cost associate with new staff hiring is not necessarily happening in our company as a result of employee turnovers" (The director of company E).

The reputation of the company can be increased not only by practicing SSCM but also by maintaining the expected quality of the construction projects. As an example, the company E is practicing social sustainability aspect of SSCM where it leads the company to deploy well trained labour resources who have the experience in producing quality constructions.

It is therefore evident that the respondents agree that the SSCM has implications on their companies and will continue to provide new experiences on how SSCM impacts on the companies. They have presented their experiences from the environmental dimension, the social dimension and the economic dimension of the SSCM. The construction SMEs who are planning to implement SSCM need to improve their understanding about the possible negative implications the lack of SSCM can have on their companies going forward and therefore the section 5.2.1.1 in this thesis has facilitated them by analysing the impacts of SSCM. Then the next subtheme (5.2.1.2) probes into the different dimensions of the SSCM and analyses the collected data from the respondents on different aspects of SSCM.

5.2.1.2 Different aspects of sustainable supply chain management

When it comes to aspects of SSCM, most of the respondents discussed their concerns about the ‘environmental sustainability’ where they concern about the environment and the ‘social sustainability’ where they concern about the workforce. Only few respondents mentioned about the economic aspect of SSCM. This section is important for the construction SMEs who are planning to implement SSCM, as this will guide them through some of the actions that they can practice to achieve overall success in the SSCM practice. Here the respondents provided examples for the different aspects of SSCM through their working practices.

All the respondents mentioned about the ‘environmental sustainability’ aspect. Yet, the researcher has used few quotations from the interviews to summarise the respondents’ understanding of the environmental sustainability aspect. According to the responses the environmental sustainability is mainly done through waste management. More specifically, they mentioned about recycling of separated waste by using the waste bins or skips.

‘...we have got fully recycled all of the waste coming back from the office, we have got fully separated waste at the side of the office, and we also keep a log of all the heavy recycled products....On our sites we have the ISO standards ensuring that our deliveries are suitability packaged or not packaged to reduce waste. In likes of all the products that are on the sites are packaged and the wastes are controlled’ (The managing director of company B).

The managing director of company B mentioned how effectively the company uses its space to arrange the waste separate before they are recycled. The respondent further explained their expectations from the suppliers in order to protect the environment. These expectations indicate the understanding of the company about how an environmentally sustainable supply chain leads the company to protect the environment. The construction SMEs who are planning to implement SSCM needs to give priority for the environmental aspect of SSCM throughout the whole supply chain.

“Environmental sustainability, as I said, protecting the environment for the future generation. Basically we separate the waste and recycle...” (The general manager of company A).

The general manager of company A provided a simple definition for environmental sustainability dimension which included the future generation. The respondent deemed to be saying that their company does not destroy the environment as the future generation also has to enjoy the natural environment and not only the built environment. Therefore, the company recycles the separated waste. It is important to understand that the SSCM needs to focus on the future generations and therefore the beginners for the SSCM practices must follow waste management steps such as waste recycling.

“We protect the environment by recycling and reusing concrete... We have waste containers and skips to separate reusable and other waste including hazardous waste”
(The director of company E).

The director of company E provided concrete as an example for a generated waste by construction companies that can be recycled and reused. The company aims to protect the environment by separating the waste in to parts that can be recycled and to parts that can be reused. For the separation purpose, the company uses containers and skips to separate the waste.

Some respondents provided examples of practicing environment sustainability in their day to day activities such as drinking tea or using printers. These companies have gone beyond thinking only about massive effects of their activities on the working sites. The construction SMEs who are planning to implement SSCM needs to consider the actions that have to be changed not only in the construction sites but also in the company environments in order to achieve success in the implementation.

“We operate in the likes of marketing but we all use recyclable instead of disposable cups we have (company name) coffee mugs...” (The managing director of company B).

“We have got such as those in place for reusing or recycling office consumables like tonners or it could be aluminium drinking cans and then that is green office concept”
(The non-executive director of company D).

Also, the managing director of company B illustrated that the environment sustainability can be achieved through reductions in carbon emissions by using more sustainable vehicles.

“...we have changed our vans to brand new fleet, we got rid of our old vans and got low emission and highly technologically advanced vans...” (The managing director of company B).

The ‘social sustainability’ is also a commonly discussed aspect of SSCM. Social sustainability is about the health, safety, individual development and happiness of the workforce.

“...we focus on the health and safety of our workers” (The director of company A).

According to the director of company A, social sustainability is about the health and safety of the workforce. He did not perceive individual development or happiness of the workforce as characteristics of the social sustainability aspect of SSCM. Similarly, the director of company E, provides an example of how the company make sure that the workforce maintains health and safety measures.

“The airborne dust is reduced as we use recycled concrete and this increase the health and safety of our workers” (The director of company E).

According to the director of the company E, reusing recycled materials reduce the airborne dust and protects the health of the workforce. The construction SMES who are willing to practice SSCM needs to understand that it will protect the workforce as well as the future generations and therefore they must recycle the construction waste such as concrete.

In contrast to the statements of the director of company A and company E, the managing director of company B explained social sustainability aspect of SSCM as a combination of individual development, health, safety and happiness of the workforce.

“We constantly review our employees. We do our SWOT analysis, one of the points is people in that we would look at development of the individual and apply objectives and indicate the targets the individual need to improve on within the work force, and this is how we maintain the wellbeing of the individuals. We also look at training and development. We also look at growth of them. We are able to look at flexibility they work into. We refurbish our offices and they have health care system in place. We also provide drinks and dispensers. We have initiatives like mango Mondays, training days and pizza Thursday every three weeks. We recently embarked on charity events where employees

get to sociably contribute to our society and different charities. At charity events we get to go away to support different charities, we felt within our managements that we ought to give back to people. So, we have recently done several events over the years such as walking events, cycling events and running events. We have donated our time and got sponsorships for these charities, this was a good team building exercise to unite our people...” (The managing director of company B).

Moving to the next aspect, few respondents mentioned about the economic sustainability as another aspect of SSCM.

“Our team is on constant surveillance on buying and the commercial manager manages and looks after the cost too, we keep supply chain in minimum use” (The managing director of company B).

The managing director of company B explained how they manage the cost of the company and also mentioned the use of supply chain as minimum as possible as an effective way of managing cost. The recycling and reusing method is useful when minimising the supply chain use as the company does not have to purchase new materials. Similarly, the director of company E mentioned how recycled materials can be useful in profit generating.

“Depend upon the size of the recycled concrete we decide to use them for the disability access paving or we make use them as a backfill material. It leads us to make profits as we don’t have to pay landfill tax or transportation cost” (The director of company E).

Finally, according to the director of company E, recycled concrete can be used in a construction for a certain level. The bigger recycled concrete materials are useful for the base of paving while the smaller recycled concrete materials are useful when filling up the gaps (backfill material). Yet, the quality and the strength of the constructed structure get affected by using excessive amount of recycled concrete.

The subtheme 5.2.1.2 analysed the collected data on the different aspects of the SSCM. The environment dimension of the SSCM and the social dimension of the SSCM were discussed widely while only a few respondents provided their experience on the economic dimension of the SSCM. This analysis helps the construction SMEs who are planning to implement SSCM to

develop general understanding about the SSCM dimensions and how these dimensions can be achieved. The next theme (5.2.2) provides an analysis of collected data specifically on the environmental SSCM as it directly links to the current research study.

5.2.2 Environmental sustainable supply chain management

The below subtheme 5.2.2.1 creates the understanding of environmental SSCM importance while the subthemes 5.2.2.2 and 5.2.2.3 generates the understanding about waste generation and management. Then the subtheme 5.2.2.4 develops the necessary understanding about SSCM's impact on SMEs in the construction industry. The respondents agreed that the environmental SSCM is important. Yet, in this section only a few selected statements or data were analysed in order to minimise repetition of responses and analysis.

5.2.2.1 Environmental sustainable supply chain management importance and understanding

Both the respondents from the company A agreed that the environmental SSCM is important and demonstrated their understanding with similar statements. Therefore, the researcher decided to analyse only one response on behalf of the company. The director of company A, illustrated planning the environment protection methods at the beginning of a construction project as important in order to achieve the needs of the clients and to achieve profitability. They aim to accomplish more contracts in the future through the generated profitability. Therefore, the audience of the thesis must understand that the SSCM is important for the long term existence of the construction SMEs.

“... It is massive..... So, it is important to think about environmental protection at the beginning of a project. Also if we do not provide what the clients are asking for, it affects our finance. SMEs depend on their profits to complete the next construction project. I meant to say some main contractors are likely to hire the subcontractors that already have sustainable materials in their stocks. So, we will not be able to have that stock unless we achieve a profit from the previously completed project” (The director of company A).

Similar to the statement of the director of company A, the director of company C mentioned how profitability can be achieved through sustainable material purchasing. The respondent

highlighted that the main contractors are expecting SMEs to use sustainable materials to complete the project. Apart from that, he indirectly mentioned most of the constructions SMEs are using sustainable materials. As a result of this usage, the cost of the sustainable materials has decreased. The reduced purchasing cost lead companies to achieve profitability. This data is important for the construction SMEs who are willing to practice SSCM as it indicates a direct link between the sustainable materials purchasing and profit generation.

“...it is important to go alone a certain direction where I am going to have sustainability. Generally to a certain degree we do get the business that we trade with also looking to use the recycled materials. Also it is cheaper than natural products. So, if you get a sustainable source, you can buy cheaper. This is proven by the fact that more people are now doing it. Also, you have more recycled materials rather than natural materials” (The director of company C).

The managing director of company D had a contradictory idea about the number of SMEs who is practicing environmental SSCM. He mentioned that there is construction SMEs who does not care about the sustainability practices. The main reason for this oversight is the scarcity of cash with lower profits margins and yet he also mentioned that the environmental SSCM is important for SMEs to overcome financial constrains in the long run. This data is important for the audience as it motivates them to implement SSCM.

“It is important for everyone. I do think it is a personal thing whether they believe it or not. There are number of people within the construction industry who do not really care. They just want to make money... Some of those have to be pretty much put in to a corner whatever they have to do because it cost money... There is no money to really do it in the industry and the profit margins are so tight... so all the SMEs struggle. So, it is important for everyone to recognize the need for it” (The managing director of company D).

Larger construction companies in the UK practice environmental SSCM as the government has compliancy regulations and boundaries for them. But for the SMEs there are no such compliances and boundaries as they do not have higher turnovers. There is a possibility that the government will make laws to be followed by the construction companies including bigger and

smaller companies. The finance manager of the company B highlighted this situation as evidence to demonstrate the importance of the environmental SSCM.

“You cannot set boundaries saying look you need to have a certain amount of turnover and then it becomes important. It needs to be consistent from top to bottom whether it is a big organisation or a smaller one. The same rule applies. I would imagine quite shortly there will be something that passes through parliament which will ensure that it will become a law that we all have to comply with. So, I think it is vital for SMEs to comply and be coherent with sustainability” (The finance manager of company B).

Finally, the director of company E illustrated the importance of practicing environmental SSCM in order to manage the waste. The waste can be managed through waste reduction, reuse and recycle. The respondent mentioned that the company uses sustainable materials such as renewable materials which lead the main contractors to hire the company. Therefore, the company generated profits through practicing environmental SSCM.

“It is very important for the SMEs in construction industry as we dispose of a lot of waste. So it is important to manage the waste promptly to protect the environment. Most of our main contractors are likely to hire us as we already use sustainable materials for our projects. This helps us to run the business with profits” (The director of company E).

The current subtheme (5.2.2.1) highlighted that the environmental SSCM is important for construction SMEs as these companies generate massive amount of waste which has negative impacts on the natural environment. Although fewer data has been analysed, all the respondents had the same understanding and view about the environment dimension of SSCM as an important element. This researcher of the current research study presents these data as they are important elements that develop the understanding and motivate the audience to implement SSCM. The subtheme 5.2.2.2 analyses the collected data on waste generation of SMEs in the construction industry.

5.2.2.2 Waste generation of SMEs in the construction industry

Construction companies discard unwanted materials and generate vast amount of waste. There are hazardous wastes such as paint tins and fuel, non-hazardous waste such as packaging and

inert waste such as bricks. Sometimes there are wastes that do not directly classify as hazardous but still they act as hazardous to the environment. For example, boilers and generators are not hazardous but fuel in them are categorised as hazardous. Therefore, it is important for the construction SMEs who are willing to practice SSCM to have a wide knowledge about the waste separation and management.

According to the managing director of company B, the company generates hazardous and non-hazardous waste. The company utilises waste management companies to dispose of the hazardous waste while recycling the non-hazardous waste. The company has the appropriate knowledge about the waste separation and it helps them to manage the waste promptly. Waste separation knowledge and waste management companies are the resources that the audience can use after implementing the SSCM and these resources can help them to achieve success in SSCM.

“...we have plant replacement, where we change large equipments, generators, boilers and the likes. We ask the waste management companies to dispose of the fuel in them accurately as they can cause more damage to the environment. Apart from the fuel, they are recyclable...” (The managing director of company B).

Further, the managing director of company B illustrated that the company generates inert waste as a result of equipment changes in demolition and construction projects. Here, the respondent was speaking in the context of fit out works where interior changes are made according to client’s desire. A ‘Cat A fit out’ or in other words ‘Category A fit out’ includes suspended ceiling installation, floor raising, fire detection installation, mechanical equipment installation and electrical equipment installation. This data helps the construction SMEs who are planning to implement SSCM to develop their understanding about the types of waste they generate.

“If we are doing a fit out of an office block that would be already completed to what we would call as a ‘CAT A fit out’. So the floors and ceilings are in but we go and modify them and put the layouts the clients want. So there can be demolishing waste which will straight away go in to the skips. So the equipments that have recently being installed will straight away go in to the skips, because the client wants a different layout. You have all our new plant that comes..... These heavy materials have reclaim value. We dispose of

them for a minimum cost to someone who will reclaim them. In the industry as we refurbish buildings or anything we generate greater amount of waste” (The managing director of company B).

The director of company D explained the air pollution and sound pollution as consequences of machineries. These machineries consume massive amount of fuel. The old fuel in the machineries such as forklifts must be changed and it generates hazardous waste which needs to be disposed of properly. When the machineries stop functioning properly the company separates the fuel as hazardous waste and machineries as recyclable waste.

“...got fuel waste, got different air from plants, from trucks, from diggers, from all sort of machinery like Forklift. The noise pollution is bad although we are working on that; Armogard cutting stations reduces the noises emission on sites. In regard to waste, noise and dust from abrasion of wheels, from cutting materials create a lot of waste etc. Some of them are microscopic and some of them are very visual. There are more wastes from all aspects. If we can get more clean fuel and convert to cartage to dispose of the waste that would then be a great help. Because of these forklifts and diggers are not regulated like trucks on the roads in regard to fuel consumption. So, it makes us swallow a lot of fuel” (The director of company D).

The non-hazardous waste generation is the most discussed waste category. Because most of the participants mentioned that they generate waste as a result of packaging. They do not want to have damaged materials sent by the suppliers. Even the suppliers do not want to make a loss as they will have to replace any material that is damaged while transporting. Therefore, they sometimes use excess amount of packaging as protection for the materials. It is evident with the few responses mentioned below.

“...it is a must to mention about the packaging waste” (The general manager of company A).

“...there are lot of packaging” (The director of company D).

The general manager of company A and the director of company D that mentioned their companies generate packaging waste while the director of company C viewed using excessive

packing as a method to protect the materials. The new practitioners of the SSCM need to observe their waste to develop the understanding about the amount of packaging waste they generate as it is a must to reduce this type of waste.

“...wastes are the wraps use by suppliers. There are lots of plastic wraps like that. There are lots of materials wrapped with plastic. They use them to protect the product from damage by moisture basically” (The director of company C).

Similar to the statement provided by the director of company C, the managing director of company B viewed using packaging as a material protection. Yet, the company B is trying to minimise the packaging by implementing policies and generating ideas to use recyclable packaging materials. These practices are useful for the construction SMEs to maintain sustainability once they implement SSCM.

“...we have policies, we have supply chains that we promote how everything is delivered, the ways they come on and the recyclable nature of that waste. Normally, in all the kits that come in boxes, around is polystyrene so that is what we are trying to defeat. We do not want anything to get damaged but we also do not want to have twenty layers of protection on. Because eventually all that protection material will end up in the skips. Those protections have to be recyclable” (The managing director of company B).

Similar to the company B, the company D generates recyclable waste including packaging waste on sites. Additionally, the non-executive director of company D mentioned that they generate waste such as food, paper and general wastes inside the company. This data highlights the importance to make waste management arrangement not only for the construction sites but also in the offices of the construction SMEs who are planning to implement SSCM in order to succeed in SSCM practices.

“Construction companies do generate waste through running the offices. That can be food waste, paper waste and general office waste. And in the construction sites it depends on the construction company. So, it may be packaging, it may be off guard and it may be plaster board. In our particular case, they generate recyclable waste. The reason to generate recyclable waste is that if there is any off guard or piping then they all get recycled” (The non-executive director of company D).

Likewise, the construction SMEs can generate non-hazardous waste in the company as well as on the sites which needs to be managed promptly.

Then there is inert waste which is uncontaminated materials and which will not decompose. The construction companies generate this type of waste by purchasing excessive materials such as bricks or during demolition projects. These wastes can be recycled or reused only once as the quality of the material gets reduced. Once the recycled or reused materials go unviable, these become waste that directly goes to landfills or to someone who will reclaim their value. The director of company D justified this situation by providing examples from the company.

“...if you are doing a concrete foundation, the engineer will calculate the materials need to complete the foundation which is not exactly 100% correct. So you might have out spill of materials. So, that becomes a waste product... Similarly, if you order too much stones that would be a similar scenario. Having said that, it is controlled. Because the materials that cannot be reused, we would collect them and send them out. Those are the materials that once it goes off you cannot use it again” (The director of company D).

The company A generates inert waste such as bricks and non-hazardous waste such as metal nails, which can be reused or recycled. Out of the respondents, only the director of company A mentioned nails as a waste which construction companies generate. Unlike stones and bricks, metal maintain the same quality after recycling. Although the metal nails cannot be reused they can be recycled and used to manufacture another product.

“Our waste ranges from nails to building materials like bricks” (The director of company A).

The finance manager of company B mentioned excavated materials as waste generated by the company B. The excavated materials can be classified as contaminated materials and uncontaminated materials. The contaminated materials such as contaminated soil, stones and bricks are classified as non-hazardous waste or hazardous waste. As an example, the contaminated soil becomes hazardous when soil gets contaminated by asbestos fibres which generates during demolition work. This type of waste needs to be sent to the landfills. The uncontaminated soil, stones and bricks classified as inert waste. They can be recycled or reused depending upon the quality of the material.

“If you think about a construction project, a very essential thing is to excavate the ground. So you generate certain amount of waste there. You are putting a foundation and building a structure. So whether it is waste from excavation materials, waste like raw or manufactured material, waste from demolition and none of that can be re-used and some of that would be scrapped or send for something else” (The finance manager of company B).

Waste generation has negative consequences on the finance of construction companies. In one way if a company orders extra materials and if there is excess then the company has spent too much unnecessarily. Then the disposal of the waste adds another expense for the companies. They have to hire waste management companies and pay for the skips. This situation effects on the profits of the construction companies. Therefore, construction SMEs must implement SSCM in order to generate profits from the construction projects.

“Financial wise... I see not necessarily the front end cost but also the cost of disposal of waste where that they have to use additional skips to take those away. That waste might have been generated because someone has not done their job properly or someone has not taken enough care” (The finance manager of company B).

According to the assistant manager of company E, the company has to pay not only for hiring the skips but also for the collecting and transporting the generated waste. The waste disposal cost is higher for the construction companies as they generate significantly larger amount of waste. The company E pays the landfill tax in order to dispose of hazardous waste.

“The skipped waste is dealt by the waste management organisations’ end. It cost us money for skip hiring, skip collection and transportation. Even we have to pay the landfill tax” (The assistant manager of company E).

The current subtheme (5.2.2.2) analysed the collected data on hazardous, non-hazardous and inert waste generation of the construction SMEs. All the companies had the understanding about what type of waste they are generating during construction projects. The construction SMEs who are planning to implement SSCM need to increase their understanding about the different types of waste they are generating in order to reduce the cost on waste disposal. These analysed data indicated that the companies have a clear vision about how they are managing the waste.

Therefore, the next subtheme (5.2.2.3) analyses the collected data on waste management of SMEs in the construction companies.

5.2.2.3 Waste management of SMEs in the construction industry

Waste management strategies and procedures are needed to be planned at the very beginning of a construction project. At this point the construction companies have to pay more attention towards waste reduction, reusing the materials, recycling and waste disposal. It helps the companies to generate profit by incurring less money on waste disposal, reduce cost of buying extra materials, reduce site accidents that can cause as a result of careless material storage, reduce emissions and potential fire hazards. The subtheme 5.2.2.3 analyses the collected data on waste reduction (5.2.2.3.1), reusing the materials (5.2.2.3.2) and waste recycling (5.2.2.3.3).

5.2.2.3.1 Waste reduction

When it comes to waste management, waste reduction has to be at the forefront of the construction companies. To achieve this goal, communication between the construction companies and their suppliers is crucial. Most of the respondents took packaging waste as an example where they can reduce waste generation. Some respondents also mentioned communication as an effective way to make the suppliers aware of the needs and the requirements to reduce packaging waste. This section is important as it develops the understanding of construction SMEs who are planning to implement SSCM on waste reduction and the resources that can be used to reduce waste.

Waste reduction is important regardless of the size of the construction project. Yet, more attention must be given at the beginning of larger construction projects and / or when completing several construction projects at the same time.

“...where there is large scale new build housing or commercial building that is where it is more important. Qualities and the drivers are more noticeable. Because there are ambitions by client communities to reduce waste, to improve the performance of the building that we build and all that leads to sustainable supply chain management” (The non-executive director of company D).

According to the non-executive director of the company D, their company gives more attention to waste reduction as they undertake large scale construction projects. The quality needs to be of even higher level as it is more visible on larger scale housing or commercial buildings. The larger construction projects generate more waste. Therefore, the company profit margin decreases with increased costs associate with waste disposal. From the client's point of view, the increased cost increases their outlays. Therefore, the clients want the supply chain to reduce waste generation. Communication between the client and the suppliers becomes an effective method to reduce waste throughout the whole supply chain.

“We continuously communicate with the suppliers to reduce the waste generation because of the excess packaging...” (The director of company A).

According to the director of the company A, the company communicates and informs the suppliers to reduce packaging but at the same time they do not wish to undertake the risk of materials getting damaged as a result of not having adequate packaging.

“If we take packaging we will not stipulate what packaging has to be provided to protect the equipment. If we stipulate packaging we would put restrictions in place. Imagine that you are sending a material for the site and you want it to be well protected as possible. You do not want to send something that is damaged. So we do not put any constrains to send the goods. But once the packaging comes to site, we would remove that packing and replace with alternative as it can cause any fires in the site. And then put that packaging in segregated waste skips” (The finance manager of company B).

Similar to the company A, the finance manager of the company B mentioned that the company B requests its suppliers to minimise packaging when using the polyester wrapping and boxes. However, at the same time they do not wish to put restrictions on the use of packaging as they want undamaged materials. Once the company receives the materials safely, they remove all the packaging and put them into the allocated skips. The company takes this precautionary measure in order to prevent fire hazards on sites. The company B takes several steps to reduce waste although they do not put restrictions directly to the suppliers. This is evident from the below statement from the managing director of company B.

“We have standard environment procedures within our ISO. We distribute it to all our supply chain and our subcontractors. We ask them and review their procedures. We operate supply chain database that ensure our supply chain is regularly assessed and that we have correct element. We provide feedback for them. Our clients and contractors are constantly assessing us, we get provided with feedback, which help us improve. We operate KPI in the likes of we ask them to assess us and they ask us to assess them and feedback each other in a positive manner” (The managing director of company B).

The communication between the construction companies and the suppliers help to keep the whole supplier chain in a line. Having discussions about procedures to protect the environment, having knowledge about each other’s environment protection procedures and sharing feedbacks about the procedures help all stakeholders to be in the same line of waste management. The company B has a strong communication pattern where they discuss all these points with each other. Therefore, the suppliers of the company are aware about the waste reduction requirements of the company B.

Reducing waste is not an easy task when it comes to the materials that protect the construction equipments and construction materials. Therefore, communication can be effective to a certain limit.

“Our waste ranges from nails to building materials like bricks and blocks and mortar, wood, also it is a must to mention about the packaging waste. We continuously communicate with the suppliers to reduce the waste generate because of the excess packaging but with certain materials it is challenging to reduce the packaging. As we practice sustainability, we use waste management companies to manage this situation. Not having enough space in the construction sites is another reason to these waste management companies to exist” (The assistant manager of company E).

The assistant manager of company E admitted that the company generates waste. The respondent viewed communication as an effective method. Yet, sometimes the suppliers cannot change their actions as there can be negative consequences of those actions. For example, the suppliers have to use excessive packaging to protect construction materials and it is classified as an unavoidable

waste. In situation like this, the company E uses waste management companies in order to remove these wastes from the sites.

“From environmental point of view, we talk about how we are working. Zero waste is in. But it is something really hard to work at the moment... We are trying to resist off sites by reducing plastic. So we do not send plastic wrapping and we will unwrap everything where we can. When we work with our supply chain we also ask them to do that. Cardboard, is not just in recycling point of view and environmental point of view but also in safety pointy of view we are trying as there is a risk of fire” (The HSQE and Sustainability Director of company D).

Similar to the company E, the company D finds it difficult to maintain the zero waste in concept. The company communicates with the suppliers to reduce plastic and cardboard packaging. Yet, it is difficult as there has to be some kind of a protection for the construction materials while transporting them. Similar to the company B, the company D removes all the plastic and cardboard packaging from the sites in order to minimise fire hazards.

According to the analysed data in this subtheme (5.2.2.3.2), the waste reduction is an important aspect and there is a common waste management method practiced by the construction SME sector. The companies have their own method of waste reduction. Therefore, the construction SMEs who is planning to implement SSCM can have their own method of reducing unnecessary waste generation. Reusing is the next alternative for the construction companies when managing waste as it is difficult for the companies to reduce waste.

5.2.2.3.2 Reusing the materials

This section is important for the construction SMEs who are willing to implement SSCM as it develops understanding on waste management by reusing the reusable materials. Reusing the construction materials is the next aim of the construction companies in order to manage the waste they currently generate and the waste that has already been generated. Reusing is useful if there is any material used in the previous construction projects that is suitable for the current construction project. Checking material stock inventory is therefore curial before ordering any

new materials in order to maximise profit and also to reduce excess materials in the stocks. The company A follows this reusing method.

“We check the stocks before we take new materials from the suppliers. So we can reuse what we have and we will not have much waste at the end. If we take something from suppliers we specify what need to be supplied...” (The director of company A).

The director of the company A mentioned that the company prefers to reuse construction materials rather than purchasing new materials. It helps the company to reduce waste such as packaging. Therefore, costs such as transportation and waste disposal can be reduced which in turn leads the company to improve on profitability.

The companies can use their own method when separating waste that can be reused from other waste. The company E uses containers and skips to separate the wastes.

“We have waste containers and skips. Reusable things go to the containers and other wastes including hazardous waste go in to the skips” (The assistant manager of company E).

Using containers to separate reusable construction materials again reduce the cost of hiring a separate skip. A skip can be used when the company decides to dispose waste such as hazardous waste. According to the researcher of the current research study, the company E is more successful in budget handling as it gives more attention to simple and practical ways of cost reduction.

“The waste management companies will segregate the waste like plastics, metals and things like that. Then they will send certain things to reuse and recycle. We will get a consignment notes saying that this amount of waste you have provided, this amount of waste have being recycled and so on. They have ways to segregate the waste” (The finance manager of company B).

The company B also reuses the construction materials. According to the finance manager of company B, they separate the generated waste and uses waste management companies to recycle

the waste where practical and to dispose the hazardous waste. Once the company hires a waste management company, they request all necessary documents to evaluate the amount of waste that the company has removed from the site, the amount of recycled waste and the amount of waste that has gone to landfills. This type of evaluation helps construction SMEs to develop a general understanding about the kind of waste a particular company would generate the most and take actions accordingly during the next construction project. Therefore, the particular company can achieve profitability not only by reusing but also through minimising waste generation.

The amount of generated waste depends on the size of the construction project. It is evident from the response of the non-executive director of company D.

“...on large construction sites now you are getting to a situation where construction companies are diverting waste from landfill. So only may be between 1 out of 10 percent of materials are going to landfills. The rest they are going to reuse or recycle” (The non-executive director of company D).

The company D reuses construction materials as much as possible and reduces the waste generation throughout the present construction project. When it comes to larger construction projects, the company D tends to generate more waste that can be reused in the next project or waste that can be recycled. The company generates reduced amount of waste that need to be disposed as the company is practicing environment dimension of SSCM. According to the researcher of the current research study, the company D can be perceived as a construction SME that practice SSCM effectively.

The two respondents of the company C admitted that the company reuses construction materials. The reason to highlight this is that only one respondent from each company admitted that their respective companies are reusing construction materials. Therefore, the researcher of the current research study decided to analyse both responses.

“...when you get a job in a certain area like a job involving weight baggage lot of sand is coming out from that. That sand we can reuse elsewhere. We can reuse it for backfills and stuff like that. We can also sell it back to our suppliers to reuse as a recyclable material. So it is quality saving digging out 300 tones of sand because we have already

got it there. We are trying to reuse as much as we can” (The purchasing manager of company C).

According to the purchasing manager of company C, the company reduce cost and at the same time save the environment through reusing construction materials. The respondent took sand drops out from the weight baggage as a material example that the company reuse. The company C also has financial benefits in reusing construction materials. If the company reuses the material on another construction project the company can reduce purchasing cost and if the company sells it back to the suppliers the company generates an extra income. The respondent mentioned that the company protects the environment by reusing sand. Because the suppliers does not have to extract excessive amount of sand for company C’s next construction project.

“...if you order too much stones that would be the similar. Having said that is controlled. Because the materials that cannot be reused, we would collect them and send them out... It tends to go for recycling purposes. Unless there are some wrong things all of them go to landfills” (The director of company C).

The director of company C mentioned the stone inert waste as an example of construction materials that the company reuses. Further, the respondents mentioned that the company separate the waste and send out the waste that needs to be recycled or that needs to be disposed. Yet, it is obvious that the company uses the landfills as the last option to dispose the generated waste if they cannot be reused or recycled.

The analysed data in the subtheme 5.2.2.3.2 indicated that the construction SMEs reuse the materials as much as possible they can in order to reduce waste generation and to reduce the cost associate with procurement. Therefore, the construction SMEs who is planning to implement SSCM has to consider reusing their construction materials. The next subtheme (5.2.2.3.3) analyses the recycling actions of the case studies.

5.2.2.3.3 Recycling

In the construction industry few construction SMEs have the capacity to recycle the waste within the construction site itself. The company D is one of those construction SMEs who has the capacity to recycle their generated waste on the construction site.

“On a site it could be how we can recycle. It is something that we do. We try to recycle everything. The scrap we have, we do not re use it. We recycle it and use that money on charity or whatever we are doing” (The HSQE and Sustainability Director of company D).

However, this is not the same for all the SMEs in the construction industry. The SMEs in the construction industry who do not have the capacity to recycle waste on construction sites use waste management companies to recycle them. It is not only because they practice SSCM but also because of the limited space available in the construction sites and being SMEs they do not possess the financial muscle to bear capital expenses related to recycling.

“As we practice sustainability, we use waste management companies... Not having enough space in the construction sites is another reason to these waste management companies” (The director of company A).

According to the director of company A, the company uses waste management companies as an element of the company’s environmental SSCM practices. The size of the construction site leads the company to use waste management companies and remove waste from construction sites. The waste management companies separate the waste and recycle what can be recycled.

“We use specialist waste management contactors. It is lot more cheaper than we recycle the waste by ourselves...” (The finance manager of company B).

Similar to company A, company B uses waste management companies to remove waste from sites. The company B aims to reduce the recycling cost by letting the waste management companies to recycle the waste for them.

The above mentioned responses show that the SMEs in the construction industry have limited resources. The company A and the company B do not wish to transport those waste back to their companies and recycle the waste in their companies as it require further current expenditure, wider space and capital expenditure on recycling equipments. Therefore, waste separation in a cost effective methods is of paramount importance when transporting waste generated by

construction SMEs to the recycling centres and more importantly persuade the wider sector in to the SSCM concept.

“Vast majority of the companies use waste management system on site. So in there they have a recycle area and segregation area for timber and metals and plastics and a general waste bin. So you work out where should be that waste go. Like timber goes to timber skip, plastic goes to plastic skip and general waste like non recyclable goes to landfill skip” (The director of company C).

According to the director of company C, the construction companies have to separate waste by using several skips. Here, the researcher of the current research study has a doubt about this method. The reason is that the budgets of the construction SMEs are tight. Using several skips for each recyclable waste material increases the cost of the company. Therefore, the company C needs to pay more attention in to this situation and use below mentioned waste separation methods such as in the company D.

“Generally it is done by the main contractor. When we are talking about general waste the main contractor disposes them. It is required under their contracts to do that. It depends with the size of the contract. They tell subcontractors how it should be done. We deal with the big sites, well organised building sites. Smaller size sites like a house would go down to contractors. They will just throw everything into the skips without any separation. The bigger sites are well organised and they are way ahead and the smaller ones need to follow them. May be when they bring skips they can have separate containers in the skips. That is a good idea. If they bring a skip may be quartering the skip by using two sheets of metal and cross them over. So they can separate the waste like one for copper, one for cardboard, one for plastics and one for other wastes” (The director of company D).

The director of company D mentioned that the construction SMEs have effective waste management than the main contractors. The main contractors use skips to collect all the waste together with the purpose of removing the waste from the smaller construction sites. The construction SMEs separate the waste generated from larger construction projects and collect

them in the skips. Unlikely the company C, the company D uses separation folds in the same skip in order to become more cost effective.

The construction companies have to be more careful when selecting a suitable waste management company. They decide to hand over the waste to the waste management companies in order to recycle or dispose the waste without doing any harm to the environment. Therefore they have to select the waste management companies with licenses and certificates. Here are the examples for the types of waste management companies the construction SMEs use.

“We check their licenses before hiring them...” (The director of company A).

The company A has the understanding of what type of waste management companies need to be hired to dispose the waste. The director of company A confirmed that they check licenses such as waste carrier license and waste management license prior to hiring waste management company. The company C follows the same procedure when selecting suitable waste management companies on the projects.

“...our suppliers would be that who have waste transfer license that show that they can carry it. They have skip license that shows that they responsibly dispose the materials as well you can get reports to show how much they have recycled, how much went to landfills and where the recycled materials goes and what they are used for. We would not ever use any waste carrying without those licenses in place” (The purchasing manager of company C).

According to the purchasing manager of company C, the potential waste management companies need to have waste skip license and transfer licenses. In order to recycle or dispose the generated waste the construction companies have to use skips to separate the waste accordingly. Therefore, the skips must be placed in the construction site or closer to the construction site if the construction site is smaller in terms of site footprint. The waste management companies need to have a skip license when carrying the skip out of a construction site. Then the waste transfer license provides the waste management companies the permission to carry the waste to the recycle sites or to landfills depending on the type of waste. Checking the waste management

certificates also helps the construction companies to decide on the suitable waste management company.

“We call the waste management company to come and dispose of the waste... We still have to pay for these and again we don’t use the cheapest in the market because it is not economy but sustainability. We use companies that have certificates” (The managing director of company B).

Similarly, the managing director of company B illustrated how the construction companies are taking the responsibility to manage waste in order to protect the environment. The respondent mentioned that the company B checks the certificate such as FSC (Forest Stewardship Council) certification before the company hires a waste management company. The company hires the appropriate waste management companies and not the cheapest. The company B generates enough financial income to pay for these companies although they do not have enough financial resource to recycle the waste at the company premises.

The construction companies do not just hand over the waste to the waste management companies and end the contract with them. Beyond that, the construction companies evaluate how the waste is managed. The construction companies use reports and documents to trace or to gather information about how much waste was generated, how much waste was recycled and how much waste was released to the landfills. It was already evident from the response of the purchasing manager of company C and further it is justified by the responses of the director of company A and the managing director of company B.

“...we ask them to provide reports on how they handled the waste, how much of waste went into landfills etc...” (The director of company A).

“All of the products are then traceable and this provides company with documents that the products are recycled and where it is gone. This is how we manage sustainability” (The managing director of company B).

Further, according to the finance manager of company B, there is no guarantee that the evaluation is correct although the waste management companies provide the reports and document to show how they have managed the waste.

“So we use licensed contractors... We have told that 90% of the waste goes to the landfills. I think these figures have been manipulated. Because it probably does not go to the landfills in the UK and perhaps it goes somewhere else. You cannot neglect this...”
(The finance manager of company B).

The finance manager of company B viewed that most of the waste probably does not end up in landfills in the UK. It is therefore the researcher’s view that whether the broader topic of waste end-up in landfills or not should be studied separately as a single statement from a respondent would not be sufficient enough to arrive at a credible conclusion. At the same time, this is not something to be neglected.

The current subsection (5.2.2.3.3) analysed the collected data on waste recycling. All the companies recycle their recyclable waste in order to be more sustainable. The construction SMEs who is willing to practice SSCM are advantaged from this section as it develops the understanding about recycling materials and benefits of recycling. The companies who have the capacity to recycle waste on site can have an increased profitability than the companies who have to hire waste management companies. Yet, any company who recycle their recyclable material is capable of making cost savings by not having to pay landfill tax. More importantly, they will be making a positive contribution to the environment by practicing SSCM in their construction companies as well as establishing itself in the industry as a company who is ethical to the human beings and kinder to the environment. The next section (5.2.2.4) analyses the data collected on environmental SSCM’s impact on construction SMEs.

5.2.2.4 Environmentally sustainable supply chain management’s impact on SMEs in the construction industry

Here, the researcher of the current research study wanted to establish whether practicing environmental dimension of the SSCM by the SMEs encourage their clients to select them as service providers, and thereby creating a competitive advantage for themselves. According to the collected data, the competitive advantage was one of the positive impacts while profitability was

highlighted as another positive impact of the environmental sustainable supply chain management on their construction companies.

The managing director of the company D admitted that environmental SSCM has an impact on the company. Yet, the researcher of the current study analysed the respondent's statement as an unclear response.

“Yes it has impacted on us. This is a definite process that we have to follow. That is the only way to go. People have to follow them and that it is very good. It needs to continue. But it is very limited as we are a subcontractor” (The managing director of company D).

Further, the managing director of company D mentioned that the construction SMEs need to practice environmental SSCM and then also highlighted the fact that them being a subcontractor is a limitation. The client or the main contractor always instruct the subcontractors or the SMEs on what materials they have to use. Therefore, it is important for the whole supply chain including the end user and the main contractors to be on the same line of thinking. The non-executive director of company D also had the same understanding about the impacts of the environmental SSCM on the company D.

“If you can demonstrate responsible management of procurement goods and services, then that can be an advantage when you work where you find the clients that have similar values. If you can demonstrate which is waste and improve efficiency in supply chain provision and also in the delivery of goods and service, and then that supports to flow of capital. And that means you can become more profitable” (The non-executive director of company D).

According to the non-executive director of company D, practicing the environmental SSCM is more advantageous when the clients have similar practices in place. The respondent mentioned that the profitability can be achieved when the whole supply chain aims to achieve the same outcome of becoming environmentally sustainable. Then the waste generation gets reduced and equally the cost associate with waste disposal gets reduced. Therefore, there is a positive impact of the environmental SSCM on the company D.

“There might be financial impacts but it’s hard to explain... It definitely effect negatively on competitive advantage if we can’t get the right product for right price. But if we have a decent supply chain we can guarantee what we are doing...” (The HSQE and sustainability director of company D).

The HSQE and sustainability director of company D highlighted the financial gains and the competitive advantages as the impacts of the environmental SSCM for the company. According to the respondent, the clients prioritise the construction companies that implement the practice of using sustainable materials for the right price.

“It has an impact on us. It increased our profitability. As we have environmental protection practices in place our waste is reduced, energy consumption is reduced and transportation is reduced. So, our cost has reduced and profitability has increased” (The assistant manager of company E).

According to the assistant manager of company E, the environmental SSCM practices impacts on the company E. The company generates a reduced volume of waste in comparison to the pre-SSCM implementation times which also leads to reduction in transportation and disposal. The company utilises recycled material which leads to reduction in energy consumptions. These environmental SSCM credentials increase the profitability of the company E.

“It does not have a visible impact on us. In terms of financial capital, it can impact. Generally speaking unsustainable thing are more expensive” (The director of company C).

The director of company C agreed that the environmental SSCM has financial impact on the company. The respondent perceived sustainable construction materials as not expensive when compared to unsustainable construction materials. The company C reduces the material cost of the company by purchasing sustainable materials from the suppliers. Yet, the respondent stated the cost reduction as an invisible impact as if the cost is higher the company includes that to the bill that needs to be paid by the client. Therefore, the company can achieve profitability whether the company practices SSCM or not. The purchasing manager of company C had a better understanding about the company situation when it comes to the impacts of environmental SSCM.

“No, it is widely available now. It is not difficult to source. I mean it did impact on the price years ago. Like certified timber and aggregates would have been sometimes nearly double the price of now which is why people were buying cheap timber and imported timber” (The purchasing manager of company C).

According to the purchasing manager of company C, currently the company does not have any impact of environmental SSCM as most of the construction companies now practices this concept. The cost of sustainable materials has reduced as most construction companies are purchasing them. Therefore, the competition is also not there among the construction companies.

Similar to the statement of the purchasing manager of company C, the managing director of company B mentioned that their clients do not select them as they practices environmental sustainable supply chain management.

“... I personally do not believe that people are employing our company because of our environment credentials...” (The managing director of company B).

The financial manager of the company B agreed with the director of the company B. The respondent explained that their clients do not select them because they practice environmental SSCM. Therefore, the company no longer perceives environmental SSCM practices as giving them a competitive advantage but an industry-wide established common practice.

“I think the people that we work with do not work with us because we are the most sustainable company... It does impact on your credential but it does not make you the most attractive... So, because of what clients want it is hard to say that sustainability is the one that makes you more or less attractive...” (The finance manager of company B).

There are other elements that help SMEs to achieve the competitive advantage while environmental dimension of SSCM partially impact on them.

“This is a highly competitive industry where often price stick states who win the work... Because there are other aspects that people would look in companies like better health and safety records or better self deliveries or capabilities with house design facilities or manufacturing facilities” (The finance manager of company B).

The clients look for quality services for lower prices. The elements of competitive advantage in sustainability or the clients' preferred services which include health and safety record of the previous service providers, better in-house design facilities and manufacturing facilities. The reason behind this situation is that the clients have higher living standard expectations.

The analysed data illustrated the diverse perceptions of the respondents on the impact of environmental SSCM on construction companies. The companies A, D, and E and the director of company C share the common view that the SMEs in construction can achieve competitive advantage and generate increased profit when practicing environmental SSCM. However, company B and the purchasing manager of company C mentioned that practicing environmental SSCM does no longer generate a crucial impact on construction companies in relation to gaining a competitive advantage as it has become a widely available practice in the industry which in turn has helped reduce prices of sustainable material. Furthermore, competitive advantage increases more with the quality of previous projects delivered by a particular construction company. All these data are useful for the construction SMEs who are planning to practice SSCM in order develop their understanding on the positive implications of practicing environmental dimension of SSCM.

After developing the understanding on the impact of SSCM on SMEs in the construction industry; the differing SSCM aspects that construction SMEs practicing; the importance of environmental; waste generation of construction SMEs; waste management of construction SMEs and understanding about the environmental SSCM's impact on SMEs in the construction industry, the current research study guides the audience to the next theme (5.2.3) that analyses the sustainable supply chain management implementation. This theme directly link to the research objectives mentioned in the section introduction (section 1.5).

5.2.3 Sustainable supply chain management implementation

The analysis under the sections "sustainable supply chain management implementation" is aimed at achieving the research objectives as mentioned in section 1.5. Therefore the objectives to be focused in this section are to investigate the key drivers to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully in UK SMEs in the construction industry; to examine the

implementation process of sustainable supply chain management in the UK SMEs in construction and to understand the barriers that UK SMEs in the construction industry face during the implementation of sustainable supply chain management. This section includes the process (5.2.3.1), the motivators (5.2.3.2), the barriers (5.2.3.3) and the solutions (5.2.3.4).

5.2.3.1 Process

The current research study analysed collected data on the implementation process in order to achieve the research objective of ‘to examine the implementation process of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in the construction industry’. According to the respondents of companies A, C, D and E, they have used the seven process steps of SSCM implementation (figure 5) while the company B has used the environmental management system as the implementation process of SSCM (figure 7). The researcher of the current research study observed that the case studies or the companies have not followed each and every step depicted in figures 5 and 7. Therefore, the processes mentioned in the literature review (subsection 2.6.4) and the processes explained by the respondents have minimum differences.

None of the companies had a written document on the SSCM implementation process and not all the respondents were confident on their responses. Therefore, the researcher of the current research study selected the data provided by the respondents from each company who had a wide understanding about the implementation process and who seemed more confident on their responses.

5.2.3.1.1 The seven process steps of SSCM implementation or similar process

The company A (case study one) has used five implementation process steps out of the seven process steps of SSCM implementation (figure 13 below) protocol. The director of company A has a wider understanding about the environmental SSCM implementation process of the company. Yet, the respondent explained the process steps rather than naming them. Therefore, the researcher of the current research study linked the explanations with the categories in the implementation process. Accordingly, the company A has mapped the company’s supply chain; has formulated supplier requirement and made them binding; has identified significant sustainability impacts, assessed risk and determined action areas; has evaluated the sustainability

performance of supplier and binding competencies and finally the company A has also adapted internal structures and process.

Company A initiated the SSCM model on the motivation and the initiation of the company director and the following activities take place in the process:

Firstly, the company A understood about my suppliers” (Interviewee from company A).

The formulation of supplier requirement and making the binding with the company requirement is important as it helps to hold the supply chain activities or the

practices. The director of the company A has increased his understanding on ISO 14001 with the help of main contractors, websites and a consultant. Consequently, the respondent could pass correct information for the suppliers.

“I introduced them the ISO 14001 system. The members who were willing to have a change stayed with us while others not. I gathered more details about the ISO 14001 systems. I asked from my main contractors and searched in the websites. I took help from a consultant” (The director of company A).

Furthermore, the director of company A has done an impact analysis of construction materials with the help of the team members and the consultant. The discussions have highlighted the amount of waste the company and its supply chain generate and the negative impact on the climate change.

“Then I had meetings with my team members including the consultant to systematically organise information about our materials and their negative impacts on the environment. Actually, what we found is really important for the construction industry. Our projects impact on the whole ecosystem as we generate massive amount of waste that makes changes in the climate. Also we contribute to the air pollution and water pollution where it has a direct impact on the people’s health. Natural resource usage is another huge negative impact” (The director of company A).

The general manager of company A agreed with the director of the company A. The respondent mentioned the consultant was helpful in identifying unsustainable materials their suppliers have been providing and to obtain a comprehensive understanding on the issue of company’s waste generation. Thereafter, the consultant has linked these unsustainable actions with the climate change. Therefore, the workforce of company A has found environmental SSCM as an important process that the company needs to implement.

“We had discussions about our suppliers, about their materials and their impacts on us and the environment. The consultant explained the impact of unsustainable materials and the waste we generate. He explained us about climate change” (The general manager of company A).

Consequently, the company A has evaluated the sustainability performance of suppliers and binding competences. The company has presented the finding of the impact analysis to the suppliers and has requested them to analyse their own business processes accordingly. The suppliers who have realised the negative impacts on the environment as a result of their own acts have subscribed to the environmental SSCM and signed memorandum of understandings which amply demonstrates their willingness to change.

“We shared all these information with our suppliers. We asked them to analyse their own processes and to think how they contribute to these negative impacts. Then again we gathered their consent on whether they are ready to change their processes or not. We signed contracts with the suppliers who were ready to accept our requirements” (The director of company A).

Finally, the company A has adapted internal structures and process according to the designed SSCM. The company A does not have any specific targets or objects as the company is a small construction company where the clients make decision on behalf of them. Nevertheless, the whole supply chain aims to reduce, to reuse or to recycle the construction waste. The respondent mentioned that implementation of SSCM is not expensive for a construction SME.

“The consultant suggested me to have specific targets or objectives. But I did not agree with that as we are a small business. But we all aim to reuse or recycle the materials we have already. Before we talk about the negative impacts, we did not try to reuse or recycle what we have. We always tried to purchase new materials. But we changed our system. I think this new system is a profit generator rather than an expense” (The director of company A).

The company A has used their main contractors, websites and a consultant as the resources to implement SSCM. These resources have developed their understanding and guided them throughout the implementation process. Communication can be categorised as an important tool that helped the company A to widen their knowledge of their projects' negative impacts on the environment and guided the whole supply chain in the direction of SSCM. Whereby, having SSCM implemented is also helping them to generate more profit.

Similar to Company C (case study three) has utilized the implementation process steps from the seven process steps. Company C has modified the seven process steps by including an extra step. Accordingly, Company C has a better understanding of the supply chain; has identified significant sustainability risks and action areas; has adapted internal structures and processes; and finally, has implemented the requirements and made them binding (figure 14). The process is a cyclical process that leads to a deeper understanding of the SSCM.

Figure 14: SSCM implementation process of Company C

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The company C has generated an understanding about the SSCM as an initial step to implement environmental SSCM. The company has utilised construction companies, a consultant and websites information of the main contractors in order to gather more information about the SSCM.

“Try to understand what SSCM is. You can always look in to the websites, hire a consultant and discuss with other companies in the industry” (The purchasing director of company C).

The director of company C agreed with their purchasing director.

“...gather as much as information you can about what are the sustainable products you can use. Ask people. People might not have them written down but they might have them in their heads what you could and should use as an alternative for certain things. Of course the people who have already started this might have the certain amount of knowledge. You go and ask from 100 people how I can become more sustainable” (The director of company C).

Then the company C has mapped the supply chain. The company has identified the positive values of their suppliers such as having positive impacts on the natural environment. The company C has reduced the time they spent on supplier evaluation as the purchasing manager had the experience of selecting sustainable suppliers.

“I have done that through experience rather than using supplier evaluations. I have to mention that the suppliers I normally use have activities that have beneficial impacts on the environment” (The purchasing manager of company C).

The company C has identified significant sustainability impacts, assessed risks and determined action areas as the next environmental SSCM implementation process. The company has utilised consultants to identify the impacts of environmental sustainability on their company. However, the company has still had to prioritise the needs of the main contractors which in a way has limited the comprehensive identification of the negative sustainability impacts.

“As the next step try and identify any impacts of sustainability on the organisation. Gather more information and consultancy guidance if there are any risks or negative

impacts and take actions to reverse them. Make sure that you fulfil the needs of the clients while making the changes. Our opportunity to identify significant sustainability impacts is very limited. Because I am working towards a specification so I know what I am already looking for. I am not choosing a product for the client and submitting it saying this is what you should use. They are telling me what I have got to order. So that is down to them and to their architects, designers and engineers. That is not our responsibility here...” (The purchasing manager of company C).

Then the company C has adapted internal structures and processes which is different from the main contractor. The company C has included the targets to the business process in order to follow during the implementation. The company C as a SME has to follow the guidelines provided by the main contractor. Regardless of this main contractor driven construction process, they have still chosen to amend their business process accordingly to implement the SSCM.

“We have internal procedures and processes. But it is completely different from the main contractor. Develop a guidelines or targets to follow during the implementation” (The purchasing manager of company C).

The target such as requesting and utilising only the sustainable materials has been incorporated in to the business process during the implementation phase.

“The process is asking or requesting from your suppliers, I want this material to be sustainable. And to a certain degree that is driven by the fact that such materials will be enough for the work we operate. So if you want to save money and also to be kind to the environment you look for recyclable materials” (The director of company C).

Finally, the company C has formulated supplier requirements and made them binding. This process step has helped the company C to identify which supplier is willing to change. Then the company has signed contracts with the suppliers who are willing to change and removed the suppliers who are not willing to change.

“...start analysing the resources or the suppliers who already practice this. If there are any suppliers who do not practice this then make an influence. But they need to have the

willingness to change their procedures. If not, get rid of them and hire new people” (The purchasing manager of company C).

Similar to company A, company C has used their main contractors, websites and a consultant as resources to implement SSCM. These resources have guided them throughout the SSCM implementation process. For the company C, being a SME was a barrier when implementing the SSCM as the company has to follow the guidance provided by the clients or the main contractors.

The company D (case study four) also has adapted five steps from the seven process steps of the SSCM implementation. The company D has appointed a non-executive director to take the responsibility of implementing the SSCM. This indicates that the company D had a decent understanding about the SSCM.

“I took a non executive director. He laid the ground rules for us” (The managing director of company D).

According to the non-executive director the company D mapped the supply chain; identified significant sustainability impacts, assessed risks and determined action areas; analysed gaps and derive measures; adapted internal structures and processes and finally formulated the requirements and made them binding (figure 15).

Figure 15: SSCM implementation process of Company D

ou l t e t)

The company D began the CM i n i s b t supply chain. The company has generated the unders a t a s has generated the understanding about the activit n t mp ne its and mitigates damages. Direct communicatio i t s i l pa y D to gather more i t s c in.

“...understand what the n i o 2. And when it is i wh e e d o i n g to increase the positive benefits o So it can be done through speaking to suppl and ng he out . ed collaborating

with them and making sure the right questions to ask” (The non-executive director of company D).

Following which the company D has identified the significant negative impacts on sustainability and regulated actions to minimise it. The company has utilised direct actions where possible while utilising influential actions for the supply chain. Communication and understanding has become important methods to interact with the suppliers.

“...understand the direct and indirect impacts, what can you control directly and what you need to start to influence. When you do something in the office environment you can control or you can negotiate with your landlords. And whether it is on supply chain, whether it is labour or services or whether it is goods then understanding what skills and quality requirement to have more or labour. And then with materials it is more than longer-term conversation because if you have certain requirements that cannot be met immediately but at least through the conversation those suppliers would know that you would want to purchase their products in the future if they could meet certain criteria. That is a healthy signal on demand side” (The non-executive director of company D).

According to the non-executive director of company D, the next step of implementing environmental SSCM was the gap analysis and develops measures to eliminate them. Here, reviews of the supply chain have been helpful to analyse the gaps that exists within the current sustainability practices.

“...identify any gaps by reviewing the supply chain” (The non-executive director of company D).

The HSQE and sustainability director of company D mentioned the elements that they have assessed in their supply chain.

“Review where we are, what we are doing, what do we have to have in place, what training do we need to do to deliver that and then put the process in place. Once you done that you need to have a review period. Same time there needs to be strategic timeline” (The HSQE and sustainability director of company D).

Then the company D has adapted the internal structures and processes in order to implement SSCM. Here, the company has developed their environment policy to keep the whole supply chain into one direction. The environment policy of the company D was developed according to the government environment protection procedures.

“...then we developed our environment policy. You have got the policy operating procedures so everyone knows the government rules and regulations” (The non-executive director of company D).

Finally, the company D has formulated supplier requirements and made the suppliers binding. During this implementation process step, the environment policy which includes the government rules and regulation was discussed with the suppliers in order for them to decide whether they are capable of complying with the policy. The suppliers who agreed to the policy had to sign a memorandum of understanding in order to formalise their partnership with the company D and its procedures.

“Formalizing government procedure was done through contracting. We specify certain level of supply chain...” (The non-executive director of company D).

The company D has employed a non-executive director in order to successfully implement the SSCM. The non-executive director had the experience and understanding about the SSCM and about the implementation of the SSCM. Similar to the company A, the company has utilised direct communication in order to interact with the supplier effectively. Increased understanding about the government rules and regulations is a motivator for the company D and its suppliers to decide and to maintain the SSCM.

Similar to the companies A, C and D, the company E (case study five) has utilised five process steps from the seven process steps of SSCM implementation. Mapping the supply chain; identifying the significant sustainability impacts; assessing risks and determining action areas; adapting internal structures and processes; formulating the requirements for suppliers and making them binding and finally evaluating the sustainability performance of the suppliers and building competencies were the process steps of environmental SSCM implementation of the company E (figure 16).

Figure 16: SSCM implementation process of Company E

ou l t e t)

The company E has begun the im m i o a t c m y's supply chain. The company E has collected de rs bus ne s pr ses, whether the suppliers are practicing the ironmental SSCM a a w t hey are supplying sustainable materials. Both the : e om E r his initial process step.

"In the start we ily uppl n. e e t aterials they are sending us" (T a sistant manager of company E).

The director of company E agreed with their assistant manager.

“In the start we looked into our supply chain and tried to understand what they are doing in relation to sustainable supply chain management. We directly contacted them and discussed with them to collect all the details” (The director of company E).

Thereafter, the company E has identified the significant sustainability impacts on personal, organisation and environment level. The manager of the company has played an important role when communicating with the team.

“Then our manager explained the whole team about the concept and its impact on the personal, organisation and environmental level” (The assistant manager of company E).

According to the director of company E, the company has explained their requirements from the suppliers rather than giving the opportunity for the suppliers to explain their requirement. Here, the company E had to use effective communication in order to generate the correct knowledge and understanding about SSCM among the suppliers. .

“Then we explained the suppliers about our requirements. As most of them didn’t have the understanding we had to explain the concept of sustainable supply chain management and its impact on the organisation and environment...” (The director of company E).

The third SSCM implementation process step of the company E was adapting internal structures and processes. The company E could adapt the new change for a certain degree as the company is SME who works according to main contractor specifications.

“We also modified some of our construction techniques to welcome the change and slowly but gradually we adopted the sustainable supply chain” (The assistant manager of company E).

Then the company E has formulated supplier requirements and made them binding. The company has analysed requirements of the suppliers. The suppliers who are willing to practice

SSCM could have requirements such as training on how to integrate sustainability in to their business procedures. Direct communication has been an effective method to identify who is willing to change and their requirements in order to implement the discussed changes.

“In the next step, the suppliers were analysed based on their requirements if they are following sustainable supply chain and we gave the chance to decide what to do for those who are not following. For this purpose we directly contacted them and discussed with them” (The assistant manager of company E).

The director of the company E agreed with the assistant manager of company E. The company E has given the opportunity for the suppliers to decide whether they want to change their business procedures or not. Then they formalized the partnership by signing legally binding contracts.

“The suppliers were given the opportunity to decide whether to adapt to the new changes or to leave the chain. The suppliers who were ready to adapt had to analyse their system and to decide how they are going to make these changes signed contracts with us” (The director of company E).

Finally, the company E has evaluated the sustainability performance of suppliers and built competences. After signing the contracts, the company E has requested the suppliers to assess their business procedures in order to maintain the code of conduct. The company has organised trainings if they have found any gaps between the code of conduct and what they are actually doing.

“Then the suppliers who decided to follow sustainable supply chain had to do assess their companies. According we provided training” (The assistant manager of company E).

The director of the company E did not mention that they provided training for the suppliers. Instead the respondent mentioned that the company E provided advices for the suppliers to improve. Somehow, the company E helped the suppliers to overcome their barriers.

“At last we checked their self-assessment and gave our ideas to improve. So now we have a sustainable supply chain” (The director of company E).

Similar to the company A and the company D, the company E has utilised direct communication in order to gather information from the supply chain and to distribute knowledge to the supply chain. Similar to the company C, the company E mentioned that the company could change their procedures to a certain level as the contractors have power over the construction materials and procedures the SMEs use during a construction project.

5.2.3.1.1.1 Summary of the implementation processes in the seven process steps of SSCM implementation or similar process subtheme

Seven process steps of SSCM implementation & modified process step	The company A (case study one)	The company C (case study three)	The company D (case study four)	The company E (case study five)
Generating understanding about SSCM	-	1 st step	-	-
Mapping the supply chain	1 st step	2 nd step	1 st step	1 st step
Identifying significant sustainability impacts, assesing risks and determining action areas	3 rd step	3 rd step	2 nd step	2 nd step
Analysing gaps and measures	-	-	3 rd step	-
Adapting internal structure and processes	5 th step	4 th step	4 th step	3 rd step
Formulating supplier requirements and binding	2 nd step	5 th step	5 th step	4 th step
Evaluating the sustainability performance	4 th step	-	-	5 th step
Reporting	-	-	-	-

Table 6: The SSCM implementation processes of case studies (Source: Compiled by the author)

The company A, the company C, the company D and the company E have followed the seven process steps of SSCM. Yet, the companies have modified the process according to their understanding and according to their needs. These modifications have developed four unique SSCM implementation processes.

When it comes to the differences of the implementation processes, the company C has included one extra step to the SSCM implementation process. The company has initiated the process by generating the understanding about SSCM. According to the researcher of the current research study, generating a general understanding about the SSCM is an important process step if the construction SMEs have never heard or seen how SSCM works in the construction industry. Many studies have been done on general SSCM except the studies on SSCM of SMEs in the UK construction industry. The above section 5.2 in this thesis fills this gap by providing an analysis of the important features of SSCM in the construction companies in the SME sector. The companies A, the D and E definitely have developed their understanding about the SSCM although they have not specifically mentioned this as an implementation process step. If not these companies would not have got motivated to implement the SSCM. Therefore, the researcher of the current research study views generating understanding about the SSCM as an important process step (figure 17).

Then only the company D has practiced the implementation process step of analysing gaps and measure. According to the research of the current research study, analysis of the gaps within the existing company objectives and processes are important for the construction SMEs in order to improve their environmental SSCM credentials. The companies A, C and E have not specifically mentioned about the gap analysis and measures as they have adapted the internal structure and processes according to their needs in implementing environmental SSCM. The construction SMEs can skip this implementation process if they are confident that they are not going to overlook the importance of sustainability objectives and measures when adapting the internal structures and processes.

Nevertheless, only companies A and E have evaluated the sustainability performance of their suppliers after they have signed contracts. This is an essential process step to keep the whole supply chain relevant as well as sustained in the long run. If a supplier is not obeying the code of conduct the relevant SME should be able to identify this gap and provide the particular supplier the required training. This will also be helpful for the supply chain as they will be able to recall the requirements, rules and regulations of the construction SMEs which they are legally obliged to abide by.

When it comes to the similarities of the environmental SSCM process steps, the companies A, C, D and E have mapped their supply chains; have identified sustainable aspects; prioritised and determined actions; have adapted internal structures and processes; have formulated supplier requirements and make them binding but none of the companies have reported the analysed data or the changes made during the implementation process. Reporting helps the stakeholders to generate an in-depth understanding about the construction SMEs. Therefore, it is important to include this process step into the environmental SSCM implementation.

After considering analysed qualitative data, the researcher of the current research study developed the figure 17 which included seven process steps that the respondents have used to implement SSCM successfully. The reporting process step is not included in this figure as none of the responded agreed on this step. The objective of examining the implementation process of SSCM in UK SMEs in the construction industry is achieved successfully.

Figure 17: Seven steps of SSCM implementation

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In contrast to the companies A, C, D and E the company B has followed similar steps as in the environmental management system. The subsection 5.2.3.1.2 analyses the environmental SSCM implementation process of company B.

5.2.3.1.2 The environmental management system or similar processes

The company B (case study two) has used the environmental management system as the SSCM implementation process. According to the managing director of company B, the company has hired a consultant to guide them through the environmental management system process.

“We have used consultants to understand the SSCM, assess the waste we generate and how to develop effective SSCM” (The managing director of company B).

The finance manager of company B agreed with the managing director of the company and mentioned how the consultant began the implementation process by providing guidelines and explanations about the SSCM.

“The consultant provided us guidelines and explained the importance of that to our organisation. So we had a structure in place...” (The finance manager of company B).

Then the consultant has developed the environmental SSCM process steps with the management of the company B. Accordingly, the company B has developed their environmental policy; planned what need to be done; implemented the identified objectives; checked and made the corrections accordingly and finally conducted management reviews (figure 18).

Figure 18: Environmental SSCM implementation process of Company B

(Source: Compiled by the author)

The company B has developed an environmental policy which includes the environment management objective of the company. The consultant guided them through the objectives and policy refining.

“...we have developed an environmental policy including the environment management objectives. As you can see ensuring the integration of the environmental management system into the organisation’s business process, ensuring that the resources needed for the environmental management system are available, communicating the importance of

effective environmental management are some of the objectives mentioned in the policy”
(The managing director of company B).

Then the planning stage has initiated by hiring specialists to the environmental SSCM management process. The company allocated budgets to hire these specialists. However, hiring specialists had been challenging to company B as they did not have the understanding of how to find these specialists. The consultant, websites and the main contractors have been helpful in identifying the specialists.

“The consultants made the budgets to hire specialist to implement the environmental management system. It was challenging as most of us did not have the understanding about sustainable supply chain, environment management or ISO 14001. So we hired the right people and it was also a challenge. We followed websites and asked from our main contractors about the right consultants and specialists” (The managing director of company B).

During the planning stage, the hired specialist has identified the procedures and aspects that need to be changed in order to achieve environmental SSCM.

“As the next step these hired specialist reviewed the government legislations like waste disposal legislation. Then they identified our impacts on the environment as we generate a certain amount of waste” (The managing director of company B).

According to the finance manager of the company B, the company has utilised ISO standard management templates during the planning stage in order to understand the necessary changes of the company’s procedures.

“We also used a lot of standard templates from ISO standard management. There are straightforward guidelines and things like environmental management 14001. They give you clear guidelines like what we need to have in place and templates for that. We use specialist to develop those to suite our business” (The finance manager of company B).

Subsequent to the plans made, the company began the process of implementation. Here, the responsibilities were allocated to the top management as they have to motivate and influence the

workforce and the supply chain to change according to the identified objectives. Training and communication have become effective when implementing the designed plan.

“Then we conducted series of training session for our top managers and employees. So we all were in the same line” (The managing director of company B).

Then the company B has checked and done corrective actions to maintain the direction of achieving these objectives. Here also the consultant and the specialist were helpful in reminding the company’s environment policy and the objectives that were developed to achieve environmental sustainability.

“Then we had regular checks and reviews to ensure the objectives are achieved and we are in the right track. If we were doing it inefficiently the consultants and specialists were guiding us” (The managing director of company B).

Finally, the company B has done management reviews of the environment policy of the company.

“This policy is reviewed annually. We made sure that the top management are involved and committed for these policies” (The managing director of company B).

The company B has used consultants, specialists, main contractors, websites, budget and ISO standard management templates as resources to implement SSCM. Having these resources available was immensely helpful in achieving their objectives as they wanted to maintain and continue the implementation process rather than encountering issues as a result of not having them. The above response illustrates that it is important to have the management commitment towards the policies in order to achieve and continue them. They have used their resources against their challenges. The respondent however, covertly admits communication as a helpful tool to be in the same path during the implementation process of SSCM.

When explaining the implementation processes, the respondents mentioned few motivators and barriers they faced during SSCM and linked them with their implementation processes. In order to develop a wider understanding about the motivators, the researcher of the current research study analysed the motivators in section (5.2.3.2) below.

5.2.3.2 Motivators

The researcher of the current research study analysed collected data on motivators in order to achieve the research objectives of ‘investigate the key drivers to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully in UK SMEs in the construction industry’. The subsection 5.2.3.1 has illustrated top/senior management commitment and increased understanding about the government rules and regulations as the key motivators to implement environmental SSCM. The previous subsection (5.2.3.1) highlighted the resources that the companies have utilised during the implementation process. The resources such as main contractors, consultants, specialist in the environmental SSCM field, websites, enough finance to implement SSCM and effective communication have the ability to influence an SME to implement SSCM.

Organisations need to have the motivation to decide to implement SSCM. The researcher questioned about these motivators from the respondents. The respondents have commented on the internal and external motivators that guided their companies to implement environmental SSCM. The respondents have also mentioned about the corporate strategy and organisational characteristics as internal motivators while highlighting social pressure, regulatory pressure and market pressure as external motivators.

The top/senior management commitment which is classified as one of the corporate strategies is an important motivator to implement environmental SSCM. This is evident from the below statements;

“It’s just me. I implemented it as I believed protecting environment as a necessity. I started with small steps like cleaning my company. So I could convince my staff it is possible to have a cleaner environment” (The director of company A)

Top management is a strong pillar for the company process change. Implementing a new process needs to be approved by the top management and also they need to believe that their decisions are appropriate. The respondent illustrates that the change need to begin within yourself in order to convince its easiness to the people around you. The assistant manager of company E mentioned that the director of the company took the initiative to implement SSCM.

“Our manager / director is very keen about sustainability or it came from the top of the organisation” (The assistant manager of company E).

The non-executive director of company D agreed with the director of the company A and the assistant manager of company E and explained how they got motivated to implement SSCM.

“Leadership... It was the personal commitment. It was not the case that we got to do it because someone was telling us to do. So it was a personal commitment by the business to ensure that the organisation could be seen as demonstrating best practice regardless of the size and could demonstrate that it is the right thing to do. Actually it benefits of a business” (The non-executive director of company D).

The management of a construction SME has the ability to decide on implementation of environmental SSCM. The construction SMEs do not have to wait until the main contractor suggests them to implement it. Furthermore, the organisational characteristics such as the position of the construction SME in the supply chain can influence the SMEs to implement SSCM.

“...everyone else surrounding you like your suppliers are aware that as well. So you are aware of it and your suppliers are aware of it. So you all are being guided to be more sustainable generally” (The director of company C).

According to the director of company C, the motivation to implement SSCM develops from the supply chain. When the suppliers are more environmentally sustainable than a construction SME, then the particular construction SME gets motivated to practice environmentally sustainable procedures. On the other hand, a construction SME subcontractor who works under a main contractor with strong environmental SSCM credentials will get a huge motivation to implement SSCM.

“The clients. Being a small company we work for the clients. They are educated about the sustainable supply chain management. So our clients are the reason to implement this practice” (The purchasing manager of company C).

Here, the company C viewed the main contractors or the clients as a resource as well. The managing director of company D agreed with the purchasing manager of the company C.

“It was more personnel. I have seen what was being done to use by our client. I thought that was good and I thought we also should be doing that. So we took the ownership for ourselves... We follow the main contractors. And we look what we can learn from them” (The managing director company D).

According to the managing director of the company D, their main contractors had effective SSCM system which created positive outcomes for the natural environment. Another internal motivator is organisational resources such as human resource of an organisation.

“Having specialists was another encouraging factor. They have provided guidance and motivated everyone to follow step by step implementation...” (The finance manager of company B).

The above statement illustrated human resource as a positive motivating factor. When it comes to the human resources, the organisations can use internal staff or hire them as an external resource. However, hiring an external member requires an organisation to have sufficient financial resource in the first place.

Apart from the above mentioned internal motivators, there are external motivation factors too. According to the respondents, these are social pressure, regulatory pressure and market pressure. These external motivation factors are clarified in the responses mentioned below.

“We got a strong social believe that sustainability talking about environment is important for all of us. So we have initiatives for everyone like how can we do things cleaner, how can we do things better... Our work is high profiled and people tend to follow trend. Hence that is why we have consultants and specialist to bring in and promote sustainability at workplace” (The managing director of company B).

Having social beliefs towards a particular thing motivate people to achieve them. Allocated responsibility towards that achievement develops the commitment. Also, when people are around an individual who is committed to achieving something great, get motivated to go beyond that individual.

This particular response is more about the psychological motivation towards achieving something. Also, social belief systems come under external motivation factors to implement SSCM. Moreover,

“There is a strong social pressure on us to make sure that we do something good for the environment” (The managing director of company B).

The pressure from the society leads the companies to follow what the society believes as good. This motivation factor helps the organisations to achieve the competitive advantage. As the construction industry is a competitive industry, the companies try to change their processes and implement what the society perceive as good in order to win more projects. The director of company C agreed with the managing director of company B.

“Now the society is aware about the importance of protecting the environment. So from what surround you socially, from the media, from the people within the industry it is more involved and it is more fashionable to discuss about these things. You are guided to a certain degree” (The director of company C).

The director of company C highlighted the pressure created by the society and the media as motivators to implement SSCM. According to the respondent, the construction industries should follow their society in order to be in the equal standard. Apart from the market pressure there are other external motivational factors such as regulatory pressure.

“The government directs us on well published” (The director of company C).

The director of company C mentioned that the government guides the construction SME on SSCM implementation. The managing director of company D agreed with the director of company C and added the experience of the respondent.

“Also, government regulation. Government has to contact every company... In fact Grant Shapps who is the ex housing minister and he is my local MP who I am going to meet tomorrow, he believes in our business because of what we do well. Sorry I have to bring that in as he is greater than a MP because he really supports our business because he sees what good things we are doing and not only about the profit line. When you got the

government minister's support in that it encourages and inspires the businesses” (The managing director of company D).

The guidance and support of the government increases the motivation of the construction companies to implement SSCM and maintain it successfully. Then the market pressure was presented as a motivator to implement SSCM.

“Competition among the small construction companies was the main driving factor. The main contractors are looking for companies like ours” (The director of company E).

The competitive advantage is classified as one of the market pressures. According to the director of company E, they have got motivated to implement SSCM process in order to achieve competitive advantage.

The researcher of the current research study analysed collected data on motivators and investigated the key drivers to implement SSCM successfully within the UK SMEs sector in construction industry. According to the analysed data the current research has identified the internal drivers and external drivers (table 7). The internal drivers are the top management commitment which is classified as a corporate strategy, the position of the supply chain which is classified as an organisational characteristic and finally the human resource which is classified as an organisational resource. The external drivers are the media and public pressure which is classified as the social pressure, the government legislations which is classified as the regulatory pressure and finally the competitive advantage which is classified as the market pressure. The objective of investigating the key drivers to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully in UK SMEs in the construction industry is achieved while contributing to the literature gap of identified in section 2.6.6.

Internal drivers	
Corporate strategy	top management commitment
Organisational characteristics	the position of the supply chain
Organisational resources	human resource
External drivers	
Social pressure	media and public pressure
Regulatory pressure	government legislation
Market pressure	competitive advantage

Table 7: The drivers to implement SSCM (Source: compiled by the author)

5.2.3.3 Barriers

The researcher of the current research study analysed collected data on barriers in order to achieve the research objectives of ‘understanding the barriers that UK SMEs in the construction industry face during the implementation of sustainable supply chain management’. The subsection 5.2.3.1 illustrated the barriers for SMEs when implementing SSCM.

The companies have faced internal and external barriers when they were implementing SSCM. Most of the respondents mentioned about the lack of knowledge or lack of understanding as an external barrier.

“Knowledge and awareness were also the barriers. I would say our company five years ago compared to now was a completely different landscape. The people that were in the organisation then were very old school. It was kind of get the job and done without excellent thinking. The people now in the company are better at planning, better at thinking, better at engineering, better at health and safety and better at commercial control. So all those little twits made us more aware of what we actually do” (The finance manager of company B).

Here, the knowledge and awareness has become an external barrier as the workforce did not have the ability to gain the required knowledge from the society. Therefore, the perceptions of the former workforce have become unchangeable. According to the finance manager of company B, the lack of knowledge of the internal workforce has led the whole supply chain in to an unstable situation as they did not know how to educate their suppliers about the SSCM. However, the

accessibility to the facilities has increased with the time. The managing director of company D agreed with the finance manager of company B.

“The only barrier was that people’s mindsets... They are not used to it. There should be more dialogue, more advertising about it and more information distributing farther down on the supply chain to believe in it... A lot of suppliers, a lot of manufactures and the retail outlets are bigger enough companies which already know about this. The smaller contractors like tier3 contractors need to bind to it” (The managing director company D).

The perceptions or the knowledge of the workforce and the suppliers were challenging for the company D. The understanding of the suppliers who was at the bottom of the supply chain was low as they were not exploit to systems such as SSCM. Information distribution through effective communication was used in order to change their perceptions. The HSQE and sustainability director of company D explained that not only the supplier but the company D itself did not have the understanding about the SSCM.

“Probably, lack of knowledge. We have been doing it without realizing it. It is the way we are working and the common sense plays a big part of it... Embedding it to our everyday of working was challenging” (The HSQE and sustainability director of company D).

The company D has been practicing SSCM without having the appropriate knowledge about it. Similar to company D, the suppliers of the company A had the understanding barrier at the beginning of the SSCM implementation.

“When we started to talk about sustainability practices our supply chain was not happy as they did not have much understanding or the knowledge” (The director of company A).

The suppliers of company A were not accepting the change they were requested to implement. According to the director of the company A, when the suppliers are not happy they tend to leave the chain. Similar to company A, the company E was also aware about this situation.

“For us understanding was a barrier. Making our supply chain aware about this process was challenging for us as we did not want them to leave us. But still the suppliers who found it impossible left” (The director of company E).

The company E did not want the suppliers to leave the chain. However, they have communicated with the suppliers and have given them the opportunity to decide whether to continue to work with them or not.

The construction organisations have large supply chains where it makes harder for the contractors or the SMEs to evaluate the supplied construction materials. Unlike the main contractors, the SMEs are the tier two companies where they have to work closely with the suppliers.

“...we had a very large supply chain. We were happy with the knowledge and things came on time and the right price was fine. So, actually we had the resource to look beyond the name or the organisation that you see, to see what practices they use, is something that we have not opened our minds set up before and also anything companies made it that was available before...” (The finance manager of company B).

In the past, the concentrations of the contractors including the SMEs were primarily on the profit generation from the resources they purchased from the suppliers. The SMEs did not have the knowledge and understanding to look beyond completing construction projects with the available materials which were supplied by several suppliers. The director of company C agreed with the financial manager of company B.

“It is the lack of understanding of the knowledge in terms of what you could use in material wise in the industry, what are the acceptable recyclable materials, building an understanding and the terminology used within specifications... As we moved forward people would still have in their minds that, that material which is specified has to be a naturally occurred aggregate. Because, they have always been used to it” (The director of company C).

The company C and its suppliers did not have the understanding about sustainable construction materials. Therefore, the lack of understanding about the sustainable materials was another

barrier that the SMEs have faced during the implementation process of SSCM. The purchasing manager of company C also justified the response of their director.

“There would have been product knowledge... You can't just say give me for by two timber because they might send you something uncertified the suppliers are a lot better now than when I first started... have to be very careful with specifics because few years ago as they would not have told you. You would send the order off and they give you pretty much the cheapest item they have or easiest one for them” (The purchasing manager of company C).

The construction SMEs had to educate the suppliers about sustainability materials. The suppliers used to send unsustainable construction materials that increase their profitability as the suppliers did not have the product knowledge. Apart from the lack of product knowledge, the construction SMEs had barriers in understanding the SSCM process itself.

“It was really a matter of identifying what would be the system or the process, what is the right policy to have, what is the operating procedure and then the implementation, misunderstanding of how to put these things in place and then how to contribute to your management system, also executing it and demonstrating the benefits. These are internal barriers...” (The non-executive director of company D).

According to the non-executive director of company D, lack of knowledge on the internal processes, policies and implementation procedures classified as internal barriers.

Then the finance manager of the company B explained resistance for change as another barrier to implement SSCM.

“We had established relationships, we had people that we worked with for number of years, they gave us delivery, and they gave us competitive edge. So, in that respect they had to change with us or we had to change the people that we were used...” (The finance manager of the company B).

The construction organisations have positive relationships with their supply chains. Therefore, the construction organisations wanted their supply chains to change with them in order to

continue this positive relationship and to achieve the competitive advantage. Unfortunately, the suppliers who were not ready to change had to exit the supply chain.

“Change is always profound. Using different suppliers because they have different rights, policy and procedure in place to sustained packaging and equipment, which are recyclable, or has small carbon footprints. The barriers are to change and getting the right people involved and it is also about understanding the process” (The managing director of company B).

But, the construction organisations faced challenges as the suppliers began to leave the supply chain. They had to find suitable suppliers when suppliers leave the supply chain. They had to look for the policies and procedures to select the suitable suppliers. Some suppliers had left the supply chain by imagining that SSCM implementation requires more money.

“The suppliers who found it impossible left the chain with their own consent. Even they thought it is something expensive. But in reality finance was not an issue as it was not expensive” (The assistant manager of company E).

According to the assistant manager of the company E, the suppliers have thought it is an expensive system. However, it was not expensive and quite contrary it was generating profits by creating competitive advantage for the suppliers.

“I have not come across any finance barrier. From our perspective it does not come in to it” (The director of company C).

Similar to the assistant manager of company E, the director of company C did not highlight finance as a barrier to implement SSCM.

“Finance, organisational resources and pressure from the competitors were not barriers for us really” (The director of company E).

The director of the company E agreed with the assistant manager of company E and with the director of company C. Finance, organisational resources and pressure from the competitors is classified as motivators than the barriers to implement SSCM.

The researcher of the current research study analysed collected data on barriers and investigated the barriers that UK SMEs in the construction industry face during the implementation of SSCM. According to the analysed data the current research identified the internal barriers and external barriers. The identified internal barriers are the size of the organisation that is trying to implement SSCM, the lack of knowledge on internal process adaptation and the supplier's resistance to change. Then the identified external barrier is the lack of knowledge about SSCM. The objective of understanding the barriers that UK SMEs in the construction industry face during the implementation of sustainable supply chain management is achieved successfully.

INTERNAL BARRIERS
The size of the organisation
The lack of knowledge on internal process adaptation
The suppliers' resistance to change
EXTERNAL BARRIERS
The lack of knowledge about SSCM

Table 8: The barriers to be removed to implement SSCM successfully (Source: compiled by the author)

Currently, all the case studies are effectively maintaining their SSCM. They have found solutions to overcome the internal and external barriers. The subtheme 5.2.3.4 analyses these solutions.

5.2.3.4 Solutions

The current subtheme (5.2.3.4) explains the understanding about how to overcome the identified barriers when implementing SSCM and to identify the resources they used. The communication was an effective method of finding the solutions for the barriers.

“...educating people from what you know. Trying to explain it to them, look now we are in a green environment. So, we pass information. Form an instance by directing them to look at the recycled aggregates website to see what you can and what you want to build, do more investigation for yourself rather than relying on your past, educate yourself and bring yourself up-to-date” (The director of company C).

The company C has effectively communicated with the suppliers in order to educate and guide them through the implementation process. The company has introduced resources such as website for the suppliers to gain more up-to-date information about SSCM. The company D also utilised effective communication as the solution to overcome the barriers.

“Just through educating our people. Now we are looking to add resource or bring in the people who believe it or open to believe it or learn about it. The people who do not believe in sustainability needs or environmental needs or wildlife needs, if they would not believe it they would not progress through our business” (The managing director company D).

The company D has given equal opportunities to learn about SSCM for the suppliers who was willing to change and who was not willing to change. The company has tried to make a progression in the suppliers who was not willing to adapt to the changes. The HSQE and sustainability director of company D agreed with their managing director.

“You got to have an ending mind... If it works we continue. If it doesn't work we find a way to fix it. One we communicate and let people know what the vision is and we are working. Two going back and checking what we are doing and make sure we are doing it right. Three, is reviewing what we can do” (The HSQE and sustainability director of company D).

The respondent mentioned that the construction SMEs have to be prepared to make changes accordingly to the developing knowledge. The respondent provided a small process the company followed at the beginning of SSCM process. The company D used communication as a method to pass their vision to the suppliers. The company D has amended the changes for their method of doing their tasks in order to guide the supply chain. Finally, the company has reviewed the changes and outcomes of them.

“We conducted meetings with our suppliers and main contractors. Our main contractor had a clear understanding about sustainable supply chain as they had this system in place already” (The director of company E).

The company D has communicated with the suppliers and with the contractors together in order to pass the information effectively. The main contractor has become a resource when educating the suppliers. The contractors could guide the company E to educate, monitor and evaluate the suppliers.

“It is a matter of understanding. The governance you need to put in to place. You can talk to experts for advice. And then through monitoring and evaluation of supply chain you can identify which suppliers are meeting your standards or not” (The non-executive director of company D).

The company D has used experts to educate the suppliers, to control the implementation process and to assess the suppliers through monitoring and evaluation. Effective communication through the experts has been helpful for the company D.

Thereafter, the identified final solution was to allocate some time for the suppliers to adapt to the changes.

“It took time to shift the practices which were in place from years but slowly and gradually we managed to change and adopted the sustainable practices” (The assistant manager of company E).

According to the assistant manager of the company E, it has not been easy to change the procedures that the suppliers were following. Nevertheless, the company has managed to make the changes gradually. The purchasing manager of the company C agreed with the assistant manager of the company E.

“It changed with time. The supplier came to know that we are not going to buy anything that is unless certified. Because, we have restrictions to that as well... All of the non-certified materials have been phased out and then the certified goods are coming into stock more often, the demand is gone up, the supply is gone up and the prices have risen but the material qualities better as well. Now we can buy certified materials as a lot cheaper than they used to be able to, because there is so much more of it available” (The purchasing manager of company C).

The company C has communicated with the suppliers and has informed them that company requires sustainable construction material. Furthermore, the company C has given the suppliers time to experience the reductions in the purchases. During this period the suppliers have decided to change the materials they are supplying. Similar to company C, company A mentioned time as the solution to overcome the barriers.

“It changed with the time. Everyone started to follow sustainable practices. We hired a consultant and asked from our main contractors how to implement this process” (The general manager of company A).

The company A has utilised the main contractors and a consultant in order to develop an understanding about the SSCM implementation process. Hiring the right people has helped the company B as well.

“We overcame from them by finding the right specialist. We have taken one consultant and a guide full time. In regards to the environment and ISO we have a consultant to guide and nature us throughout that. We have taken more resource in regards to HR specialist. We can always refer to the Reviews. More about bring in the specialism and this will bring in new ideas” (The managing director of company B).

The company B has hired a consultant and a HR specialist in order to generate new idea to make changes for the internal processes and to hire new suppliers in order to fill the gaps in the supply chain. Continuous reviews and effective communication have been helpful to overcome from the barriers when implementing the SSCM.

The research of the current research study analysed the solutions to overcome from the barriers to implement SSCM in order to identify the resources the construction SMEs have used. The identified solutions were the education, guidance, letting the supplier to make the decision on whether to adapt themselves to the SSCM or not and give them a reasonable time for that change. The effective communication, main contractors, websites, specialist consultants and HR specialists were the resources that were utilised when practicing the solutions.

5.3 Summary of the Chapter

This chapter achieved the research objectives of investigating the key drivers to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully in UK SMEs, examining the implementation process of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs and understanding the barriers that UK SMES face in the implementation of sustainable supply chain management. Analysed data in each theme is important for the construction SMEs who are planning to implement SSCM.

The SSCM theme (5.2.1) identified the impacts of the SSCM the construction SMEs such as securing work, profit generation and competitive advantage. These positive impacts can also be achieved with resources such as personal contacts and low price for high quality work. The below section 6.2.1 will focus on a discussion about the analysed impacts of SSCM on the SMEs and the existing literature on the impacts.

However, there has to be a balance between the SSCM practices and these resources in order to maintain SSCM. Subsequently, the different aspects of SSCM are discussed in the subsection 5.2.1.2 with given priority for the environmental aspect of SSCM as all of the responded mentioned about this. The SSCM aspects focus on the future generation before they make any procedures to practice not only in the construction site but also in the office environment. Then in-depth analysis of environmental aspect of SSCM (section 5.2.2) highlighted profit generation through waste management as the main benefit of implementing SSCM in the construction SMEs. The below section 6.2.2 (Different aspects of SSCM) will focus on a discussion about the analysed aspects of SSCM and the existing literature on the different aspects. Then, the below section 6.2.3 will focus on a discussion about the analysed environmental SSCM and the existing literature specifically environmental aspect.

This overall analysis of section 5.2.1, links to the objective of the implementation process of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs. The reason is that the construction SMEs who decide to implement SSCM need to generate the general understanding about the SSCM.

Then the objective of examining the implementation process of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs was achieved successfully by analysing the collected data. The examined implementation process includes SSCM understanding generation; supply chains

mapping; sustainable aspects identification; prioritising and determining actions; gaps analysis; internal structures and processes adaption; supplier requirements formulation and make them binding and sustainability performance evaluation. The companies A, C, D and E agreed on this process while the company B introduced environmental policy development, planning, implementation, corrective action and management review as their SSCM implementation process. The companies use websites, contractors etc. as resources to achieve the process steps. The below section 6.3.1 (Process) will focus on a discussion about the analysed processes and the existing literature on the implementation processes.

Then, the objective of investigating the key drivers to implement sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in the construction industry was achieved successfully. The top management commitment, company's position of the supply chain and human resources are the identified internal barriers. The pressure from the media, government legislations and competitive advantage are the identified external drivers to implement SSCM in construction SMEs. The below section 6.3.2 (Motivators) will focus on a discussion about the analysed and existing drivers to implement SSCM successfully.

The objectives of understanding the barriers that UK SMEs in the construction industry face during the implementation of sustainable supply chain management were achieved from this analysis. The identified internal barriers are size of the organisation, lack of knowledge on internal process adaption and suppliers' resistance to change. The identified external barrier is lack of knowledge. The participants mentioned that cost is not a barrier to implement SSCM. The participants used effective communication, specialist etc. as resources to overcome from the identified barriers. The below section 6.3.3 (Barriers) will focus on a discussion about the analysed and existing barriers to implement SSCM successfully.

The chapter six provides a comparison between the literature and the findings of the current research study.

CHAPTER SIX: FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

6.1 Introduction

This thesis commenced by providing an introduction to the current research study that included research gaps of implementation process of SSCM in SME sector, driver to implement SSCM and barriers to implement SSCM. Based on these research gaps, the researcher of the current research study developed the aim and the objectives. This particular research collected qualitative data from the selected case studies and analysed thematically in order to investigate the key drivers to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully in UK SMEs in the construction industry, to examine the implementation process of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in the construction industry and to understand the barriers that UK SMEs in the construction industry face during the implementation of sustainable supply chain management. The current chapter (chapter six) interprets the findings collected from the analysed data by referring to the literatures provided in this thesis.

This chapter commences with section 6.2 which covers SSCM including impact of sustainable supply chain management on the SMEs, different aspects of sustainable supply chain management and environmental sustainable supply chain management. This section followed by section 6.3 which discussed SSCM implementation that includes the implementation process, motivators to implement SSCM and barriers to implement SSCM. Section 6.4 concludes the chapter by providing a summary.

6.2 Sustainable Supply Chain Management

This section (6.2) discusses the findings of the current research study and the previous literature that relates to the findings. Impacts of SSCM on SMEs (6.2.1), different aspects of SSCM (6.2.2) and environmental SSCM (6.2.3) are discussed in order to develop the understanding for the construction SMEs and to generate a theoretical contribution for the academics.

6.2.1 Impact of sustainable supply chain management on the SMEs

The section 2.6.5 has reviewed the previous literature on the impacts of the SSCM on organisations. The researchers have highlighted higher reputation (Geach, 2016; Tseng *et al.*, 2015), profitability (Golicic and Smith, 2013; Carter and Rogers, 2008) and competitive advantage (Xia *et al.*, 2018; Adetunji *et al.*, 2011) as positive impacts of SSCM. Findings from the current research study agree with these authors. As examples, the director of company E mentioned that they achieved a positive reputation while the finance manager of company B stated that they achieved improved profit margins by gaining a competitive advantage through practicing SSCM.

It is observed that the impact of SSCM on the SME sector in construction depends primarily on the size of the construction project. The companies in tier one and/or the main contractors tend to employ SMEs who already practice environmental SSCM on larger projects as it makes easier for them to delegate and coordinate the waste management process. This is because the complex and large construction projects generate more waste (Al-Werikat, 2017) that warrants SSCM to be in place (Dijk *et al.*, 2014).

Furthermore, the actual impact of the SSCM on construction SMEs varies depending on the position of a particular company in the supply chain. More specifically, the SMEs come under tier two companies where they have fewer impacts than the main contractors who are in tier one. As an example, the main contractors can achieve competitiveness if they fulfil the sustainability demands of their client's (Athapaththu and Karunasena, 2018).

Unexpectedly, some of the respondents mentioned that securing work does not necessarily depend on the SSCM practices of their compaies but rather as a result of their reasonable pricing and personal contacts. Adetunji *et al.* (2011) have mentioned that the end clients or the owners

select main contractors predominantly depending on their price and consequently, the main contractors have to follow suit when selecting subcontractors which in this research means SMEs. Furthermore, some main contractors covertly select subcontractors based on their personal contacts (Geach, 2016). However, this finding cannot be generalised as only the general manager of company A and the managing director of company B subscribed to this view. Therefore, a comprehensive research needs to be done in order to analyse the reality of this finding.

The section 6.2.2 discussed the literature and findings on different aspects of SSCM.

6.2.2 Different aspects of sustainable supply chain management

Even though the construction companies in the SME sector have the ability to practice environmental, social and economic dimensions of the SSCM they tend to prioritise environmental and social sustainability aspects of the SSCM. However, in the rationale section (1.2), Markman and Krause (2016: 4) highlighted that the environment must be the main priority of the SSCM. In this backdrop, the researcher of the current research study decided to research on the implementation of environmental dimension of the SSCM.

6.2.3 Environmental sustainable supply chain management

The findings of the current research study demonstrate that the UK construction companies in the SME sector generate more waste than other industries where it requires them to make decisions on the environmental SSCM at the beginning of a project. This finding links to the analysis in section 6.2.3.1 where increased building needs of the people contributing to the generation of vast amount of waste annually is discussed (Yilmaz and Bakis, 2015; WRAP, the National Federation of Builders and Envirowise, n.d.). The waste management in the construction industry should begin at the design stage of a project as it has the opportunity to minimise or to prevent the materials use of that can possibly generate inert waste, non-hazardous waste and hazardous waste (Wibowo *et al.*, 2018). The findings illustrate that the construction companies generate hazardous waste that needs to be reduced, non-hazardous waste and inert waste that can be to be reused or recycled. Having this understanding helps the construction SMEs to develop an understanding about their waste and make conscious decisions to implement environmental

SSCM with the objective of minimising or to preventing waste generation and to manage the residual waste in an environmentally sustainable manner.

The finding shows that the construction companies in the SME sector who practice SSCM achieve higher competitive advantage and profitability through cost reduction. The cost reduction includes reduced waste transpiration cost, reduced purchasing cost and reduced price for sustainable materials. Dadhich *et al.* (2015) agrees with this finding by highlighting profits generation through waste disposal and reduction in cost of transportation as positive impacts of the environmental SSCM on construction organisations. Lim *et al.* (2017) further strengthens this finding by identifying competitive advantage as a positive impact of the environmental SSCM.

The section 6.3 discusses the implementation of SSCM specifically the environmental dimension of SSCM.

6.3 Sustainable Supply Chain Management Implementation

The discussion under the section SSCM aims to explain and evaluate the research findings by presenting their relations to the literature and the research objectives. This section includes the process (6.3.1), the motivators (6.3.2) and the barriers (6.3.3).

6.3.1 Process

This section discusses the findings and the literature in order to achieve the research objective of ‘to examine the implementation process of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in the construction industry’. The reporting of the environmental SSCM implementation and the lessons learnt philosophy is not happening in the construction SMEs and it is a limitation for the researchers and the companies who are planning to implement them. Sajjad (2015) and Zimon *et al.* (2019) agree with the researcher of the current research study by highlighting the limited managerial understanding, academic understanding, frameworks and models of SSCM implementation process. However, the findings of the current research study illustrates that the UK construction companies in the SME sector mostly use similar stages such as the seven process steps of implementation (figure 5). However, the environmental management system

(figure 7) or similar process steps as shown in figure17 are difficult to generalise as only one case study has used this particular implementation process.

6.3.1.1 The seven process steps of SSCM implementation or similar processes

Findings of the current research demonstrates that the UK construction companies in the SME sector follow similar steps as in the seven process steps of SSCM implementation which was developed by the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Natural Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety in 2017.

Figure 19 presents both the SSCM implementation processes mentioned in the subsection 2.6.5.1 and in the subsection 5.2.3.1.1.1. Both of the processes have seven steps with minimum differences in the order of the process steps. The findings of the current research illustrate that the construction companies who practice SSCM have an understanding about the resources that can be used for each implementation process of figure 17. In the resource based view theory section (2.8.2), Gallego-Alvarez *et al.*, (2015) explained resources of a company as a strength that leads the company to make strategic decisions. Furthermore, Touboulic and Walker (2015) mention that the way of using the resources guide a company to implement SSCM.

Figure 19: Comparison of two implementation processes

Figure 5: Seven process steps of SSCM implementation

(Source: Federal Ministry for the Environment, Natural Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety, 2017)

Figure 16: Seven process steps of SSCM implementation

(Source: Compiled by the author)

(Source: Compiled by the author)

Unlike the seven process steps developed by the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Natural Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety, the seven process steps developed by the researcher of the current research study began the process with generating an understanding about SSCM. Unlikely, in the German seven process steps, the company C has mentioned this process step as important that allows the companies to develop understanding about the SSCM with the help of available resources. The section 5.2 and 6.2 help the audience which includes the UK construction SMEs who aims to practice SSCM to improve their understanding about the SSCM. Apart from this particular thesis, the construction SMEs can use websites, other companies' data in the field and specialist consultants as resources to develop their understanding.

Furthermore, both process steps identify mapping the supply chain as the next process step. Yet, the German seven process steps do not give priority for the available resources that makes the implementation process easier as mentioned by the company A, C, D and E. The findings of the current study demonstrate main contractors, websites, consultants and direct communication as resources to map the supply chain. According to Udawatta *et al.* (2015), communication is an effective technique to manage and reduce waste throughout the supply chain. The supply chain mapping process step can be implemented by collecting details about the business processes of the suppliers, by gathering details about the environmental SSCM practices of the suppliers, by checking whether they are supplying sustainable materials and by identifying the positive values of their suppliers such as having positive impacts on the natural environment.

The findings of company A, C, D and E on the third process step (identifying significant sustainability impacts, assessing risks and determining action areas) mention staff members, consultants and direct communication as resources to identify unsustainable materials and the negative impacts on the environment such as climate change. On the other hand, developing the necessary understanding about the negative impacts on the environment motivates the construction companies to implement SSCM. Paulraj *et al.* (2017) also mention that the willingness to reduce the negative environmental impacts as a motivator. Further, the findings highlights that the construction SMEs have to prioritise the needs of the main contractor and it becomes a barrier for the SMEs to identify the negative sustainability impacts on the environment.

The analysis of gaps and measures is the next common process step of the figure 5 and figure 17. In this process step, the UK construction SMEs have the opportunity to review their supply chains and collect details on the current sustainability activities and materials. Here, the companies can use the details collected throughout the supply chain mapping and allocate more time provide necessary trainings for the suppliers. The identification of process and structural changes occurs in this stage. According to the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Natural Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (2017), the SMEs develop mission statements which include the main objectives of the companies. The company D follows this process step. However, the findings of the current research study (including company D) evidence that SMEs of the construction industry cannot have specific targets or objectives due to main contractors or the clients making decisions on behalf of them.

The fifth process step is adapting internal structure and process which is again a common process step in both the implementation processes. The findings illustrate that the construction SMEs aim to reduce, reuse or recycle the waste materials although they cannot have specific targets and accordingly they change their 'internal' structures and the processes. Young *et al.* (2015) mentions the processes and structures as the organisational factors that guide the performance and the activities of a company. For example, prior to the SSCM implementation, the construction SMEs might have purchased materials without reviewing the sustainability of the specific materials. Therefore, with the implementation of SSCM, the construction SMEs can change their processes of purchasing materials and may specifically request sustainable materials from their suppliers. The consultants are the human resources who can guide the companies through the changes successfully.

Both the seven step implementation processes formulate supplier requirements and make them binding. The findings demonstrate main contractors, websites, specialist consultants, direct communication and training as resources to formulate supplier requirements and to make them binding. This process step identifies the suppliers who are willing to adapt to the changes and if applicable to identify who is willing to comply with the environmental policy of the company. The suppliers who then decide to be the supply chain partners of the company should enter in to legally enforceable agreements and replacing the suppliers who are not willing to change their business processes with willing entities. Training can be provided for suppliers who require more

understanding about how to implement environmental SSCM. Overall, this process step helps the whole supply chain to be in the same thought process.

The final process step of the seven process step of SSCM implementation (figure 17) is the evaluating sustainability performance of suppliers and building competences. The implementation process developed by the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Natural Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (2017) also practice this process step but not as the final process step. It (figure 5) reports the findings of the evaluation. The company A and E practices this step as it greatly helps the stakeholders and the companies to elevate their competitive advantage. Nevertheless, the reporting stage is not used in figure 17 as the findings illustrate no information about reporting of evaluated sustainability performances of the suppliers. However, the evaluation of the sustainability process step expects the suppliers to conduct self assessments of their business procedures with the purpose of maintaining the contract or the code of conduct. If necessary, guidance and more training can be provided for the suppliers who find gaps between the contract and their business procedures.

The reporting step as in the implementation process developed by the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Natural Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (2017) was not mentioned by any of the companies. Therefore, the research did not include this process step in to the figure 17.

The subsection 6.3.1.2 discusses the findings on the environmental management system or similar implementation process steps.

6.3.1.2 The environmental management system or similar process

As mentioned in the 6.3.1, only one case study (Company B) has used the environmental management system or similar process steps. Therefore, the researcher of the current research study finds it difficult to generalise the findings on this process.

Figure 20 presents both the environmental management system processes mentioned the subsection 2.6.5.3 and 5.2.3.1.2. Both of the processes have environment policy stage, planning stage, implementation stage, checking/corrective action stage and management stage. The difference of the two processes is the steps under each main implementation stage. The findings

of the current research demonstrate that the company B who practice environmental management system process has the understanding about the resources that can be used.

Figure 20: Comparison of two environmental management system processes

(Source: Stapleton, Glover and Davis, 2001)

(Source: Compiled by the author)

(Source: Compiled by the author)

The first step of the process is developing an environmental policy. The consultant is the resource of the company to guide them through the policy development. The environment policy discusses the objectives of the company towards achieving environmental SSCM. According to the Business Environment Council and Environmental Protection Department (2005), it is a mandatory to include protection of the environment as part of the company objectives.

The planning of the implementation is the next process step. Hiring environmental SSCM specialists is helpful for the companies who are planning to implement environmental SSCM. The consultants, websites and the main contractors can guide the company to find an environmental SSCM specialist. During the planning stage, the specialist can identify the existing procedures and the aspects which need to be changed in order to achieve the environmental SSCM. The findings illustrates that the ISO standard management templates are helpful when identifying the necessary changes.

The next process step is the implementation of the designed plan. The specialist can allocate responsibilities for the top management as they have to motivate the workforce and the supply chain. Effective communication and training help the top manager to influence the workforce and the suppliers to change in order to achieve the environmental policy which includes the objectives.

Then the checking and corrective actions are needed to be identified in order to achieve the environmental policy and the objective. The consultant and the specialist are important resources who can keep the focus of the top management on the policy and its objectives.

At the end of the process, the management reviews are needed to be done annually in order to check the progress and to identify the necessary changes. Findings illustrate that the top management need to get involved in doing the reviews.

6.3.2 Motivators

The section 6.3.2 discusses the findings and literature in order to achieve the research objective of investigating the key drivers to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully in UK SMEs in the construction industry'. The findings demonstrate that the implementation of SSCM depends on the companies' motivation. Silvester (2016) agrees with this finding and introduces the motivation as the main indicator of the decision to implement SSCM. Furthermore, the findings reveal that the selected companies have the necessary understanding about the motivators. In the institutional theory section (2.8.1), Dubey *et al.* (2016) and Shi *et al.* (2012) illustrate that the understanding of the motivators and the drivers help the manager to make the decision to implement SSCM.

The current research study divides the gathered motivators into internal and external drivers similar to Saeed and Kersten (2019), Oelze (2017) and Ahmed (2017) (refer to Appendix 9). The top management commitment, the position of the supply chain and human resources are the internal motivators to implement SSCM. The media and public pressure, government legislation and competitive advantage are the external motivators to implement SSCM.

According to the findings, the most important motivator is the top management commitment. It helps to make the necessary changes for the company process as the approval for the changes comes from them. The commitment and support of the top management not only leads the company to implement the SSCM but also to maintain the process (Bastas and Liyanage, 2018; Oelze, 2017; Walker and Jones, 2012).

The company's position of the supply chain is the next motivating factor to implement SSCM. The selected SMEs are tier two construction companies who have main contractors above them and suppliers below them. The tier two SMEs are pressured to implement SSCM, when the companies above (tier one) and below them (tier three) have the knowledge about SSCM. According to Saeed and Kersten (2019), the company's position of the supply chain is classified as an organisational characteristic.

Further, the resources of the company such as human resources also motivate the company to implement SSCM. The findings highlight the main contractors and specialist consultants as the human resources who can influence the construction SMEs to implement SSCM. Saeed and

Kersten (2019) and Schrettle *et al.* (2014) also classify resources as motivators to implement SSCM.

According to Sajjad (2015) and Morali and Searcy (2013), the pressure from media, the pressure from clients or from main contractors and the pressure from stakeholders lead companies to implement SSCM. The findings illustrate media and public pressure which is classified as social pressure that motivates construction SMEs to implement environmental SSCM. Furthermore, social pressure is a psychological motivation in other words with the pressure construction SMEs develop a need to achieve environmental SSCM.

The regulatory pressure is another external factor that motivates construction SMEs to implement SSCM. Government laws and regulations are two ways the government influence the companies (Silvester, 2016; Bjorklund, 2011). Where the regulatory pressure increases the market pressure which intern increases the inter-company competitiveness. The causal effect of this is the creation of passive motivation within the SMEs to gain a competitive advantage by implementing the environmental SSCM.

The section 6.3.3 discusses the barriers to implement SSCM.

6.3.3 Barriers

The section 6.3.3 discusses the findings and literature with the purpose of achieving the research objective of understanding the barriers that UK SMEs in the construction industry face during the implementation of sustainable supply chain management. The findings of the current research study illustrate that the knowledge, resistant to change, size of the company and internal process adoption as the barriers to implement SSCM. There are internal and external barriers (Ahmed, 2017; Oelze, 2017; Sajjad, 2015) as explained below.

The main barrier to implement environmental SSCM is the lack of knowledge. It classifies as an external barrier. The limited access to information coupled with non-exploitation of the potentials of new systems like environmental SSCM is the main reasons for the lack of knowledge within the SME sector in construction. Ansari and Kant (2017) and Alzawawi (2014) also confirm this finding by mentioning lack of knowledge as a barrier to implement SSCM. In order to overcome the lack of knowledge barrier and to implement environmental SSCM, the

construction SEMs have to identify the resources needed such as effective communication to guide and educate the workforce and the suppliers, websites with up-to-date information and specialist consultants.

The findings highlight the internal process adoption is another barrier that happens as a result of lack of knowledge. The effective communication to with the workforce is helpful to change internal processes and methods. When making the changes to the processes the main contractor and specialist consultant can be helpful in educating, monitoring and evaluating the process.

Resistance to change is a major barrier when implementing environmental SSCM. This is an internal barrier that needs to be overcome in order to keep the whole supply chain in the same line and thereby to reduce costs. The available literature also supports this argument (Ahmed, 2017; Oelze, 2017; Pinto and Allui, 2016; Sajjad, 2015). The findings illustrate and provide an opportunity for the suppliers to decide whether to adapt their procedures and processes or not to support the construction SMEs to overcome the barrier.

Another internal barrier is the size of the company according to the respondent. Ahmed (2017), Oelze (2017), Pinto and Allui (2016) and Sajjad (2015) agree with the research finding by stating the company size as a barrier to implement environmental SSCM. The construction SMEs predominantly being tier two companies have to work closely with larger supply chains in order to provide high quality sustainable materials for the main contractors.

As everyone else, the sustainability of SMEs too depend on annual turnover and profit margins. As a consequence, construction SMEs aim to complete projects with the limited resources available without paying much attention to sustainability of the materials being used. According to Ansari and Kant (2017); Meqdadi *et al.* (2013); Alzawawi (2014) and Pedersen (2009) , the construction SMEs who plan to implement environmental SSCM might think it as an expensive process even though the reality is quite the contrary. The findings further reinforce this view.

6.4 Summary of the Chapter

The current findings and discussion chapter provides a theoretical contribution to fill the gaps in the available literature about the SSCM implementation process, about the drivers to implement SSCM and the barriers to implement SSCM. The findings on key drivers to a successful implement of SSCM within the UK SME sector in construction, the implementation process itself and the barriers that UK SMEs in construction would encounter during implementation are discussed with a comparative analysis of existing literature where necessary. The resources to implement the environmental SSCM and the solutions to overcome from the barriers are also presented in this chapter.

The chapter seven provides the conclusion of the current research study.

CHAPTER SEVEN: CONCLUSION

7.1 Introduction

The chapter seven returns to the research objectives of the current research study and addresses its aim by relating the findings presented in chapter five and six with the research objectives. The current chapter presents the research summary in section 7.2. Section 7.3 presents the research finding of the current research study. Following, the contributions of the current research study both to existing knowledge and to the construction SMEs are mentioned in section 7.4. The limitations of the current research study are discussed in section 7.5. Finally, possible future research is outlined in section 7.6.

7.2 Research Summary

The existing literature revealed a gap in the implementation of SSCM in SME sector as discussed in the introduction chapter (chapter one). In particular, lack of research on the implementation process, the drivers to implement SSCM and the barriers to implement SSCM. Therefore, the current research study focused on the in-depth understanding of UK construction SMEs' SSCM implementation process steps, drivers to implement SSCM and barriers to implement SSCM.

A conceptual framework was developed based on the literature. This conceptual framework was utilised to maintain the focus on the current research study's objectives and to formulate the semi-structured interview schedule.

The reason of utilising multiple case studies for the current research study, as discussed in the research methodology chapter (chapter three) was to generate more valuable insights than a single case study in order to generalise the findings. The findings of the current research study are based on the companies that were successful in their SSCM implementation. The selected multiple case studies are shown to support the same findings and therefore the replication is achieved. The only finding which is not a replication is the SSCM implementation process of company B.

7.3 Research Findings

7.3.1 Research objective: to investigate the key drivers to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully in UK SMEs in the construction industry

According to Bastas and Liyanage (2018), Oelze (2017), Sajjad (2015) and Walker and Jones (2012), drivers to implement SSCM identification is an important research area that has limited studies being done. The current research study presents internal and external drivers to implement SSCM. As discussed in the chapter five and six, the main driver to implement and maintain the SSCM is the top management commitment which comes under corporate strategy. The success of SSCM implementation is questionable without the top management motivation and commitment. Thereafter, the position of the supply chain which comes under organisational characteristics and human resource which comes under organisation resources are also the internal drivers to implement SSCM. The findings show that these drivers are not useful without the top management commitment as the approval to make any changes in the company processes comes from them.

The external pressures lead the companies to implement SSCM. The social pressure through media and public develops a psychological need to implement SSCM while the regulatory pressure which comes from the government makes the companies binding to the laws and regulations. As a result of these external pressures the competitiveness increases and motivates the companies to implement SSCM.

7.3.2 Research objective: to examine the implementation process of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in the construction industry

According to Zimon *et al.* (2019), Kot (2018) and Sajjad (2015) present the need to study the implementation of SSCM in order to develop a model that improves the academic and managerial understanding on SSCM implementation process. Therefore, the author of this thesis presented the seven process step of SSCM implementation (figure 17) and achieved the objective of examining the implementation process of SSCM in UK SMEs in the construction industry. The developed implementation process is a generalised process as all the respondents except company B agreed on similar process steps. The SSCM implementation process presented in this thesis is different from the SSCM implementation process developed by the German Federal

Ministry for the Environment, Natural Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (2017). The steps of the SSCM implementation process in this thesis begins by generating understanding about SSCM, explanation of each process step illustrates the resources required to implement the specific step successfully and ends with sustainability performance evolution of suppliers.

7.3.3 Research objective: to understand the barriers that UK SMEs in the construction industry face during the implementation of sustainable supply chain management

Sajjad (2015) and Zaabi *et al.* (2013) mention barriers to implement SSCM as an important research area that needs to be studied further. The current research study presents internal and external barriers to implement SSCM. As explained in the chapter five and six, the lack of knowledge is the main external barrier to implement SSCM. The lack of knowledge is an outcome of challenges that the SME encounter in of accessing necessary up-to-date information. This barrier makes internal process adoption challenging for the workforce.

Suppliers' resistant to change is an internal barrier that affects the objective of the whole supply chain. The size of the company is another internal barrier that challenges even the companies willing to change with the rest of the supply chain members. In the literature, cost is introduces as another barrier apart from these identified barriers (Ansari and Kant, 2017; Meqdadi *et al.*, 2013; Alzawawi, 2014; Pedersen, 2009). However, the findings of the current research study disagree with the existing literature and demonstrate SSCM implementation as an inexpensive process.

7.4 Research Contributions

7.4.1 Introduction

The findings of the current research study have implications for academic researchers as well as for the construction SMEs who plan to implement SSCM. The following sub-sections highlight the contribution of the current study. The sub-section 7.3.2 presents the contribution to the subject knowledge which includes the implications for the academic researchers. The sub-section 7.3.3 introduces the practical contribution of this research which includes the recommendations for the UK construction companies in the SME sector.

7.4.2 Theoretical contribution

The current research study contributes to the literature by introducing a conceptual model that fills the identified research gaps on drivers to implement SSCM, SSCM implementation process steps and barriers to implement SSCM specifically in the construction SMEs and achieves the objectives of the research. This conceptual model can be used by the academic colleagues who wish to study SSCM implementation.

(Source: compiled by the researcher)

7.4.3 Practical contribution

The current research study aimed to make recommendations to UK SMEs in the construction industry to be able to implement SSCM successfully. The findings of this research can guide the UK construction companies in the SME sector to understand the implementation process of SSCM and resources underpins facilitate implementation success. The following recommendations can be acquired from the research findings;

1. There are no early studies done on the SSCM process of the UK SMEs in the construction industry. Therefore, the figure 17 (chapter five) is the guidance for the UK construction SMEs that are willing to implement SSCM. The findings of the current research study highlights that the top management commitment as the main influence to develop the willingness to implement SSCM. The top management and all other members in company need to acquire the required understanding about SSCM in order to make a worthwhile approach to implement SSCM. This understanding can be developed by browsing websites, by communicating with other companies in the field and by hiring specialist consultants. The developed understanding is useful to map the supply chain. Further, the supply chain mapping can be done with the help of main contractors and specialist consultant, by browsing websites and by communicating with the suppliers directly. Thereafter, the construction SMEs need to identify the negative impacts of their unsustainable materials by communicating with the staff members and the specialist consultant. Afterwards, the construction SMEs need to review the collected details throughout the supply chain mapping in order to analyse the gaps and measures of their suppliers. Providing training for the suppliers can minimise the gaps of their SSCM practices. The next step is adapting internal structure and process although the SMEs have limited opportunity to do so. The specialist consultant can guide the construction SMEs to implement necessary changes in the structure and process. Then, the suppliers who are willing to continue working the specific construction company need to sign contracts to make them bounded for the changes in the supply chain. The main contractors, specialist consultant, websites, training and direct communication are useful during this process step. Finally, the sustainability performance of the suppliers needs to be evaluated by communicating with them.

2. The findings of the current research study recommend that UK construction SMEs need to identify possible solutions for the significant barriers to implement SSCM. As the findings reveal, lack of knowledge is the main barrier to implement SSCM. The construction SMEs can overcome this barrier by educating and communicating with both the workforce and suppliers, by utilising websites with updated information and by hiring specialist consultant. Thereafter, overcome the internal process adaptation barrier by communicating with the workforce and by taking guidance from the main contractors and the specialist consultant. Resistant to change is another barrier to implement SSCM that can be minimise by providing opportunity for the suppliers to decide whether to change their procedures and continue to work with the particular construction SME. The SMEs are tier two companies and the size of the company becomes a barrier to implement SSCM. The construction SMEs need to work closely with the main contractors in order to overcome these barriers. The existing literature mention cost as a barrier for the SMEs to implement SSCM. The findings of the current research study demonstrate that this is not the case or at least not any more.

The section 7.5 illustrates the identified limitation of the current research study.

7.5 Limitations of the Research

The current research study provides valuable insight on how UK construction companies in the SME sector can implement SSCM successfully. Yet, the limitation of this research study needs to be acknowledged.

A limitation encountered in the current research study is lack of previous research studies on supply chain, SCM, sustainability, sustainable supply chain and SSCM and small and medium enterprises. Furthermore, none of the research studies has been done on the implementation of SSCM in the UK SME sector in construction. Therefore, the researcher of the current research study allocated more time in selecting the most relevant literature that relates to the current research topic and if the content is important the researcher tend to use much older literature such as Carter and Rogers (2008).

However, limited access to data is another major limitation in the current research study. The sample of this research is UK construction companies in the SME sector. At the time of

collecting the consent to participate in this research, one company responded by saying that they follow all the government regulation and informed that they are unable to provide any further information. This indicates that the companies are more cautious sharing their sustainability information. Then, another company responded by saying they are SMEs who depend on the profits and work under main contractors guidance. This indicates that the SMEs are controlled by the main contractors and they cannot go against them to take part in the research. Also, construction SMEs are unable allocate time to participate in a research due to their extremely busy schedules of work. Therefore, the collected data of the current research study is limited to few case studies though enough to generalise the findings of this study to reach a conclusion.

The final limitation is inadequate data on reporting of SSCM practices. The respondents have not included reporting in their SSCM implementation processes. Therefore, the current research study could not include this step as the final process step of SSCM implementation process (figure 17).

The next section discussed the opportunities for future research.

7.6 Future Research

As discussed in chapter three, the current research study sought to generalise the findings on drivers to implement SSCM, implementation process of SSCM and barriers to implement SSCM in small and medium sized UK construction companies rather than reflect the experience of the entire population of the UK construction companies. In order to include the entire population, larger scale surveys that generalise the findings could be undertaken. The questionnaire design could be based on the research framework in the current research study (figure 10 in chapter two) and SSCM implementation process (figure 17 in chapter five). However, it is evident that the main contractors are knowledgeable and already fully equipped with the SSCM practices.

The findings of the current research study could be extended to similar contexts. For example, this research was undertaken in the context of construction SMEs in the UK and the research could be extended to construction SMEs in another developed countries. It is likely that findings in terms of drivers, processes and barriers in such research studies could be similar.

Also, this study could be extended to other industries such as manufacturing. The current research study provides possible suggestions for other industries, but further researches need to be conducted to study whether the findings of the current research can be directly generalised to SMEs in other industries.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Semi-structured Questionnaire Schedule Formation

- Questions 1-6 were included in order to decide whether the participants are suitable to take part in the research study and to gain an assurance that the selected case studies are truly practicing the sustainability. It helped to maintain the validity of the data.

1) Professional background

- Working position
- Duration in the organisation
- Years of construction industry experience

2) How do you describe your organisation's supply chain system?

- Who is involved in it?
- Is it a system and what kind of a system?

3) From your perspective, how would you explain sustainability in general?

- So basically you are concern about the future generation?

4) How do you describe sustainability in the context of your organisation supply chain?

5) Do you think this sustainability practice impacting on the organisation and how?

6) Can you specify which sustainable practices have implemented by your organisation please?

- Questions 7-10 were included in order to clarify whether the interviewer and interviewee have the same understanding about the SSCM and how long the case studies have practiced environmental sustainability effectively. These set of questions helped to gain a general idea about construction SMEs in the UK who is practicing environmental sustainability.

7) From your perspective, how would you explain sustainable supply chain management?

8) How long does your organisation practice sustainable supply chain management?

9) To what extent do you think environmental dimension of sustainable supply chain management is important for a SME in construction industry?

- Does construction companies generate waste and what kind of waste?
- How does SMEs dispose them?

10) To what extent do you think environmental dimension of sustainable supply chain management impact on your organisation?

- Question 11 was included to gather data about the barriers faced by the case studies when implementing the SSCM and the solutions they used to overcome from those barriers. The conceptual framework was useful when developing this question as it helped to probe and gather necessary data.

This question aimed to achieve the research objectives: “to understand the barriers that UK SMEs in the construction industry face during the implementation of sustainable supply chain management” and “to make recommendations that can be utilised by UK SMEs in the construction industry to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully”.

BARRIERS TO BE REMOVED	INTERNAL
	Finance
	Organisational resources
	EXTERNAL
	Pressure from the competitors
	Lack of knowledge

11) What were the barriers your organisation faced when implementing sustainable supply chain management?

- Did you have any internal barriers like financial or organisational resources?
- Did you have any external barriers like lack of knowledge and competition?
- How did the organisation overcome those barriers?

- Questions 12-14 were included in order to gain an understanding about the waste generation and management of construction SMEs in the UK. It helped to justify that the case studies are practicing environmental sustainability or not.

12) Can you specify which strategies your organisation is using to manage waste responsibly and continuously attempts to prevent and reduce the production of waste?

- Does your organisation have a program and/or procedures for the management of wastes?
- Does your organisation ensure that waste relevant for recycling is sorted and handed over to a recycling organisation?

13) Does your organisation have targets for preventing and reducing waste production and/or increasing waste recycled and measure its progress against these targets?

- What about government legislations?

14) Can you explain those targets and measurements?

- Question 15 was included to clarify whether the whole supply chains are sustainable and it helped to develop an understanding about the effectiveness of the SSCM of the case studies.

15) How many years have you worked with your main suppliers?

- Do they practice sustainability?
- Can you explain them?

- Question 16 was included to gather data about the drivers to implement the SSCM. The conceptual framework was useful when developing this question as it helped to probe and gather necessary data.

This question aimed to achieve the research objectives: “to investigate the key drivers to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully in UK SMEs in the construction industry” and “to make recommendations that can be utilised by UK SMEs in the construction industry to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully”.

DRIVERS	INTERNAL
	Corporate strategy (top management commitment)
	Organisational characteristics (the position of the supply chain)
	Organisational resources (human resource)
	EXTERNAL
	Regulatory pressure (government legislation)
	Market pressure (competitive advantage)
Social pressure (media)	

16) What driving factors do you think encouraged your organisation to implement sustainable supply chain management?

- Did you have any internal drivers like corporate strategy, organisational characteristics and resources?
- Did you have external drivers like legislations, media and competitive advantage?

- Question 17 and 19 were included in order to gather information about the SSCM implementation processes of each case study. In the conceptual framework a figure was included namely ‘implementation process of SSCM’. Yet, it did not mention any process steps as the literature review highlighted three different SSCM implementation processes.

These questions aimed to achieve the research objectives: “to examine the implementation process of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in the construction industry” and “to make recommendations that can be utilised by UK SMEs in the construction industry to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully”.

17) What is the process that your organisation followed when implementing sustainable supply chain management?

- Who were involved in the implementation of SSCM?

~~18) Have you ever published your successful story? (if not why?)~~

19) What is your advice to the SMEs in the construction industry who is trying to implement SSCM?

- What steps do they have to follow?

Appendix 2: Ethical Approval

18/04/2019

Dear Udara Indumathie Kumarihami Mahagedara,

Your application 7751: Implementation of environmental dimension of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in construction industry., submission 6546, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean

Appendix 3: Participant Information Sheet

Research title:

Implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in construction industry.

Invitation to participate in the research:

I (Udara Mahagedara) am undertaking this research in order to complete my Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) in University of the West of Scotland (UWS). I have obtained ethical approval for my research from the UWS.

What is the aim of this research?

This study aims to make recommendations to UK SMEs in the construction industry to be able to implement sustainable supply chain management successfully.

Why you have been chosen?

You have been chosen as you are a member of a well established UK SME in the construction industry which has already implemented sustainable supply chain management.

Do you have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you decide to take part please keep this information sheet. You will be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time and without any reason.

What will happen if you decide to take part?

If you decide to take part in the research, you will have to inform me a convenient time and a date to conduct a face-to-face interview at your organisation. The interview will take place for 45 minutes to 1 hour. The interviews will be recorded with your permission for the purpose of data analysis or else I will write down the points we discuss.

What are the benefits of taking part?

I anticipate that the findings will contribute to the UK SMEs in the construction industry who is willing to implement sustainable supply chain management.

Will the information you provide be kept confidential?

The personal data, your name and your organisation's name will be anonymous and confidential. The transcript and recording also will be kept anonymous and password protected.

What will happen to the results of the research?

I will write up the findings in my DBA thesis.

Contact for further information

Udara Mahagedara – -----

Appendix 4: Interview Consent Form

Research title: Implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in construction industry.

Research investigator: Udara Mahagedara

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed as part of my research. This consent form is necessary for both of us to ensure that you understand the purpose of your involvement and that you agree to the conditions of your participation. Would you therefore read the accompanying information sheet and then sign this form to certify that you approve the following.

	Agree	Disagree
I am voluntarily taking part in this project.		
I understand that I don't have to take part, and I can stop the interview at any time.		
I have read the Information sheet.		
I can ask any questions I might have, and I understand that I am free to contact the researcher with any questions I may have in the future.		
The interview will be recorded and will be password protected.		
Any summary interview content or direct quotations from the interview that are made available only in the DBA thesis will be anonymized so that my organisation or I cannot be identified.		

The interview will take 45 minutes to 1 hour. I do not anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to withdraw from the research at any time without providing any reason.

Printed name

Participant Signature

Date

Researcher's Signature

Date

Appendix 5: Completed Interview Consent Forms

Interview Consent Form

Research title: Implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in construction industry.

Research investigator: Udara Mahagedara

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed as part of my research. This consent form is necessary for both of us to ensure that you understand the purpose of your involvement and that you agree to the conditions of your participation. Would you therefore read the accompanying information sheet and then sign this form to certify that you approve the following.

	Agree	Disagree
I am voluntarily taking part in this project.	✓	
I understand that I don't have to take part, and I can stop the interview at any time.	✓	
I have read the Information sheet.	✓	
I can ask any questions I might have, and I understand that I am free to contact the researcher with any questions I may have in the future.	✓	
The interview will be recorded and will be password protected.	✓	
Any summary interview content or direct quotations from the interview that are made available only in the DBA thesis will be anonymized so that my organization or I cannot be identified.	✓	

The interview will take 45 minutes to 1 hour. I do not anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to withdraw from the research at any time without providing any reason.

18.07.2019
Date

18/07/2019
Date

Personal details withheld.

COMPANY A

Interview Consent Form

Research title: Implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in construction industry.

Research investigator: Udara Mahagedara

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed as part of my research. This consent form is necessary for both of us to ensure that you understand the purpose of your involvement and that you agree to the conditions of your participation. Would you therefore read the accompanying information sheet and then sign this form to certify that you approve the following.

	Agree	Disagree
I am voluntarily taking part in this project.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that I don't have to take part, and I can stop the interview at any time.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have read the Information sheet.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I can ask any questions I might have, and I understand that I am free to contact the researcher with any questions I may have in the future.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The interview will be recorded and will be password protected.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Any summary interview content or direct quotations from the interview that are made available only in the DBA thesis will be anonymized so that my organization or I cannot be identified.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

The interview will take 45 minutes to 1 hour. I do not anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to withdraw from the research at any time without providing any reason.

18.07.19

Date

18/07/2019

Date

Personal details withheld.

COMPANY A

Interview Consent Form

Research title: Implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in construction industry.

Research investigator: Udara Mahagedara

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed as part of my research. This consent form is necessary for both of us to ensure that you understand the purpose of your involvement and that you agree to the conditions of your participation. Would you therefore read the accompanying information sheet and then sign this form to certify that you approve the following.

	Agree	Disagree
I am voluntarily taking part in this project.	✓	
I understand that I don't have to take part, and I can stop the interview at any time.	✓	
I have read the Information sheet.	✓	
I can ask any questions I might have, and I understand that I am free to contact the researcher with any questions I may have in the future.	✓	
The interview will be recorded and will be password protected.	✓	
Any summary interview content or direct quotations from the interview that are made available only in the DBA thesis will be anonymized so that my organization or I cannot be identified.	✓	

The interview will take 45 minutes to 1 hour. I do not anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to withdraw from the research at any time without providing any reason.

2/07/2019
Date
02/07/2019
Date

Personal details withheld.

COMPANY B

Interview Consent Form

Research title: Implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in construction industry.

Research investigator: Udara Mahagedara

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed as part of my research. This consent form is necessary for both of us to ensure that you understand the purpose of your involvement and that you agree to the conditions of your participation. Would you therefore read the accompanying information sheet and then sign this form to certify that you approve the following.

	Agree	Disagree
I am voluntarily taking part in this project.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I understand that I don't have to take part, and I can stop the interview at any time.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I have read the Information sheet.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
I can ask any questions I might have, and I understand that I am free to contact the researcher with any questions I may have in the future.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The interview will be recorded and will be password protected.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Any summary interview content or direct quotations from the interview that are made available only in the DBA thesis will be anonymized so that my organization or I cannot be identified.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

The interview will take 45 minutes to 1 hour. I do not anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to withdraw from the research at any time without providing any reason.

02/07/2019
Date

02/07/2019
Date

Personal details withheld.

COMPANY B

Interview Consent Form

Research title: Implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in construction industry.

Research investigator: Udara Mahagedara

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed as part of my research. This consent form is necessary for both of us to ensure that you understand the purpose of your involvement and that you agree to the conditions of your participation. Would you therefore read the accompanying information sheet and then sign this form to certify that you approve the following.

	Agree	Disagree
I am voluntarily taking part in this project.	✓	
I understand that I don't have to take part, and I can stop the interview at any time.	✓	
I have read the Information sheet.	✓	
I can ask any questions I might have, and I understand that I am free to contact the researcher with any questions I may have in the future.	✓	
The interview will be recorded and will be password protected.	✓	
Any summary interview content or direct quotations from the interview that are made available only in the DBA thesis will be anonymized so that my organization or I cannot be identified.	✓	

The interview will take 45 minutes to 1 hour. I do not anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to withdraw from the research at any time without providing any reason.

9 JULY 19

Date

09/07/2019

Date

Personal details withheld.

COMPANY C

Interview Consent Form

Research title: Implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in construction industry.

Research investigator: Udara Mahagedara

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed as part of my research. This consent form is necessary for both of us to ensure that you understand the purpose of your involvement and that you agree to the conditions of your participation. Would you therefore read the accompanying information sheet and then sign this form to certify that you approve the following.

	Agree	Disagree
I am voluntarily taking part in this project.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
I understand that I don't have to take part, and I can stop the interview at any time.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
I have read the Information sheet.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
I can ask any questions I might have, and I understand that I am free to contact the researcher with any questions I may have in the future.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
The interview will be recorded and will be password protected.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	
Any summary interview content or direct quotations from the interview that are made available only in the DBA thesis will be anonymized so that my organization or I cannot be identified.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	

The interview will take 45 minutes to 1 hour. I do not anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to withdraw from the research at any time without providing any reason.

09/07/19
Date

09/07/2019
Date

Personal details withheld.

COMPANY C

Interview Consent Form

Research title: Implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in construction industry.

Research investigator: Udara Mahagedara

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed as part of my research. This consent form is necessary for both of us to ensure that you understand the purpose of your involvement and that you agree to the conditions of your participation. Would you therefore read the accompanying information sheet and then sign this form to certify that you approve the following.

	Agree	Disagree
I am voluntarily taking part in this project.	✓	
I understand that I don't have to take part, and I can stop the interview at any time.	✓	
I have read the Information sheet.	✓	
I can ask any questions I might have, and I understand that I am free to contact the researcher with any questions I may have in the future.	✓	
The interview will be recorded and will be password protected.	✓	
Any summary interview content or direct quotations from the interview that are made available only in the DBA thesis will be anonymized so that my organization or I cannot be identified.	✓	

The interview will take 45 minutes to 1 hour. I do not anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to withdraw from the research at any time without providing any reason.

260619
Date

26/06/19
Date

Personal details withheld.

COMPANY D

Interview Consent Form

Research title: Implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in construction industry.

Research investigator: Udara Mahagedara

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed as part of my research. This consent form is necessary for both of us to ensure that you understand the purpose of your involvement and that you agree to the conditions of your participation. Would you therefore read the accompanying information sheet and then sign this form to certify that you approve the following.

	Agree	Disagree
I am voluntarily taking part in this project.	✓	
I understand that I don't have to take part, and I can stop the interview at any time.	✓	
I have read the Information sheet.	✓	
I can ask any questions I might have, and I understand that I am free to contact the researcher with any questions I may have in the future.	✓	
The interview will be recorded and will be password protected.	✓	
Any summary interview content or direct quotations from the interview that are made available only in the DBA thesis will be anonymized so that my organization or I cannot be identified.	✓	

The interview will take 45 minutes to 1 hour. I do not anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to withdraw from the research at any time without providing any reason.

26/6/2019
Date

26/06/19
Date

Personal details withheld.

COMPANYS D

Interview Consent Form

Research title: Implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in construction industry.

Research investigator: Udara Mahagedara

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed as part of my research. This consent form is necessary for both of us to ensure that you understand the purpose of your involvement and that you agree to the conditions of your participation. Would you therefore read the accompanying information sheet and then sign this form to certify that you approve the following.

	Agree	Disagree
I am voluntarily taking part in this project.	✓	
I understand that I don't have to take part, and I can stop the interview at any time.	✓	
I have read the Information sheet.	✓	
I can ask any questions I might have, and I understand that I am free to contact the researcher with any questions I may have in the future.	✓	
The interview will be recorded and will be password protected.	✓	
Any summary interview content or direct quotations from the interview that are made available only in the DBA thesis will be anonymized so that my organization or I cannot be identified.	✓	

The interview will take 45 minutes to 1 hour. I do not anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to withdraw from the research at any time without providing any reason.

5.7.2019
Date

05/07/2019
Date

Personal details withheld.

COMPANY D

Interview Consent Form

Research title: Implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in construction industry.

Research investigator: Udara Mahagedara

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed as part of my research. This consent form is necessary for both of us to ensure that you understand the purpose of your involvement and that you agree to the conditions of your participation. Would you therefore read the accompanying information sheet and then sign this form to certify that you approve the following.

	Agree	Disagree
I am voluntarily taking part in this project.	X	
I understand that I don't have to take part, and I can stop the interview at any time.	X	
I have read the Information sheet.	X	
I can ask any questions I might have, and I understand that I am free to contact the researcher with any questions I may have in the future.	X	
The interview will be recorded and will be password protected.	X	
Any summary interview content or direct quotations from the interview that are made available only in the DBA thesis will be anonymized so that my organization or I cannot be identified.	X	

The interview will take 45 minutes to 1 hour. I do not anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to withdraw from the research at any time without providing any reason.

14/05/2020

Date

14/05/20

Date

Personal details withheld.

COMPANY E

Interview Consent Form

Research title: Implementation of sustainable supply chain management in UK SMEs in construction industry.

Research investigator: Udara Mahagedara

Thank you for agreeing to be interviewed as part of my research. This consent form is necessary for both of us to ensure that you understand the purpose of your involvement and that you agree to the conditions of your participation. Would you therefore read the accompanying information sheet and then sign this form to certify that you approve the following.

	Agree	Disagree
I am voluntarily taking part in this project.	✓	
I understand that I don't have to take part, and I can stop the interview at any time.	✓	
I have read the Information sheet.	✓	
I can ask any questions I might have, and I understand that I am free to contact the researcher with any questions I may have in the future.	✓	
The interview will be recorded and will be password protected.	✓	
Any summary interview content or direct quotations from the interview that are made available only in the DBA thesis will be anonymized so that my organization or I cannot be identified.	✓	

The interview will take 45 minutes to 1 hour. I do not anticipate that there are any risks associated with your participation, but you have the right to withdraw from the research at any time without providing any reason.

14.05.2020
Date

14/05/20
Date

Personal details withheld.

COMPANY E

Appendix 6: Semi-Structured Interview Schedule

- 1) Professional background
 - Working position
 - Duration in the organisation
 - Years of construction industry experience
- 2) How do you describe your organisation's supply chain system?
 - Who is involved in it?
 - Is it a system and what kind of a system?
- 3) From your perspective, how would you explain sustainability in general?
 - So basically you are concern about the future generation?
- 4) How do you describe sustainability in the context of your organisation supply chain?
- 5) Do you think this sustainability practice impacting on the organisation and how?
- 6) Can you specify which sustainable practices have implemented by your organisation please?
- 7) From your perspective, how would you explain sustainable supply chain management?
- 8) How long does your organisation practice sustainable supply chain management?
- 9) To what extent do you think environmental dimension of sustainable supply chain management is important for a SME in construction industry?
 - Does construction companies generate waste and what kind of waste?
 - How does SMEs dispose them?
- 10) To what extent do you think environmental dimension of sustainable supply chain management impact on your organisation?
- 11) What were the barriers your organisation faced when implementing sustainable supply chain management?
 - Did you have any internal barriers like financial or organisational resources?
 - Did you have any external barriers like lack of knowledge and competition?
 - How did the organisation overcome those barriers?
- 12) Can you specify which strategies your organisation is using to manage waste responsibly and continuously attempts to prevent and reduce the production of waste?

- Does your organisation have a program and/or procedures for the management of wastes?
 - Does your organisation ensure that waste relevant for recycling is sorted and handed over to a recycling organisation?
- 13) Does your organisation have targets for preventing and reducing waste production and/or increasing waste recycled and measure its progress against these targets?
- What about government legislations?
- 14) Can you explain those targets and measurements?
- 15) How many years have you worked with your main suppliers?
- Do they practice sustainability?
 - Can you explain them?
- 16) What driving factors do you think encouraged your organisation to implement sustainable supply chain management?
- Did you have any internal drivers like corporate strategy, organisational characteristics and resources?
 - Did you have external drivers like legislations, media and competitive advantage?
- 17) What is the process that your organisation followed when implementing sustainable supply chain management?
- Who were involved in the implementation of SSCM?
- 18) Have you ever published your successful story? (if not- why?)
- 19) What is your advice to the SMEs in the construction industry who is trying to implement SSCM?
- What steps do they have to follow?

Appendix 7: Transcript Sample

Interview Schedule (COMPANY B)

Professional background

Q: Working position

I am the managing director.

Q: Duration in the organisation

I have been with this organisation 5 and a 3 quarter years.

Q: Years of construction industry experience

I have been in the construction industry since I left school at the age of 16, so now 30 years.

Q: How do you describe your organisation's chain system?

Our supply chain is very influenced by our work, we have a very constrained within specification within contracts and within construction requirements of our contracts. Although we have a level of freedom in developing our supply chain, we are very restricted driven by specification. We also are driven by cost because we are working in a very extremely competitive market. Our market is typically makes 3-5% net profit which is pretty much the norm in any M&E stock construction bias business. The 5 being the highest of that, but it's very much driven by that. Our supply chain we have tools in place to manage it, we have supply chain data bases, we assess our supply chain, we also look at the sustainability within our supply chain.

The word sustainability being quiet flexible into whether it is sustainable for us for the business or for the environment, sustainable in different ways, but we have processes in place. I have printed out a few here for you to have a look at. They snap shots of weather what we do to achieve sustainability. We look as a SME where we are trying to align with similar line companies. So we have a tendency of our supply chain to cover everything.

We cover from a vast amount of materials being mechanical and electrical. You got to appreciate obviously that we are not a construction as in builders; we are a construction service related. Our

supply chain is probably more diverse than any other element in the market because we buy everything from a 1000 different types of lights to pipes, wires, cables, switches it is just extremely diverse in equipment's. We use a massive selection of suppliers, specialised lighting to specialist sub contractors because all through we provide, we are also able to direct 120+ direct staff employees as workers, we still out source large parts of specialists from duct work to insulation. So our supply chain covers everything from subcontractors to specialist supplies to typical wholesales to what we class as our bread and butter known as our general day-to-day materials. Obviously large equipment's such as generators, boilers and big equipment. We spend 4 to 5 million pounds a year on larger infrastructure equipment. Our chain is very diverse in equipment's.

When you look at how we explain our supply chain, it is extremely diverse and managed in a variety of completely different ways such as every day material that are driven by cost. We also maintain a standard, you can always buy cheaper but our reputation is very important to us, so we make sure that we can make large deals with the higher quality products and get them at least as the similar price. So instead of drive down the cheaper end of the market we obviously drive down to get more known brands, traceable brands and sustainable brands. So that we can make sure we do not have any failure.

Then we got our sub contractors supply chain where we looking for alliance with similar minded size companies. In subcontractor size companies, we take smaller companies to grow with us. But then you have to go back and start again. Because as they grow their flexibility, price, work approach change and naturally inherit your systems and your qualities which is fine. But eventually you start to lose that energy because a smaller company can grow quicker than you would grow in a more sustainable manner. For us it's very diverse from materials to sub contractors to specialism. We all have named equipment's, for example this project we are currently working on at the moment a CAT A for an office block for that we will need about 80 to a 100 named products from the likes of fitting to sealing the types of valve we would install. So a lot of named products, the supply chain is very different and will help us buy products from different companies.

Q: Does it involve the designers as well in your supply chain?

Yes it does, again our work is very divers. So we have standard contractors where they design for us. They are staged to design for us and we deal with to coordinators, they give us the names of the products they wish to use for there projects. We also now do large amount of design building work where we then have an element of control because we in source or outsource the designs or the design verification process. The design process is heavily processed and we have to finish the process. So we do have a level of that but it can depend with the contracts.

Q: From your perspective, how would you explain sustainability in general?

Is the sustainability talking about for the organisation or environmental or both? Because from the point of sustainability of the business and from ours is that we use a lot of trainees, we have half a dozen of apprenticeship presently under way, we have a graduate scheme, we also have a junior engineering scheme and like I said we are teamed up with Greenwich university. So we take 1 to 2 graduates a year. We have extensive training matrix for existing and new staff on regular basis, we also have opportunities for both genders in work force, to grow within the business and we also promote training and development. So from the point of business that is one element.

Then we have sustainability in the context of the environment. SWAT analysis in our business we look at different areas from environment. We have a set of objectives that have driven through business. Through our directors that we review on constant basis we have an IOS system, 9001, 14001 and 45001. Also we provide constant assessment and reviews of our system.

When we look at the sustainability from the point of environment or from the business, I think our opportunities are limited. Because we are defined by what processes we use and the products we use, we do try and reduce waste on our working site as well as construction sites. We promote any re use materials, we have got separation skips and we also try and recycle.

Sustainability is a very a broad term to me. A lot of our contractors are also bringing in people so we have people to work for us when skill shortages are there and it's on constant basis that we

have the right people to go on to get the job done correctly and efficiently and as sustainably as possible.

Q: How do you describe sustainability in your context of your organisation's supply chain?

In a lot of cases in a supply chain we don't always have full control of who we use and where or when to use them, but we do have it on certain projects and our sub contracts are assessed on their environmental policies during and ending of each project of have they actually implemented, do they operate with reduced waste, how are they actually performing? We screen their policies; we look for pro acting companies. Again we are limited with what our options are. Where possible we promote environmentally friendly approach to our works. We have a subcontractor data base and a supply chain. So it is the same thing. We have a lady called Daniel that rings the engineer's up and ask outstanding questions as such, are the guy's performing? Have we made sure that they are following environmental policies? – Do they actually mean anything? We basically asses them. We do with the best reasons and that is a managed process. Anyone that we believed either does not have the same ethics and policies as us are generally be doubted the process. The people we asses as suitable or resist are rewarded or penalized accordingly.

Q: Does sustainability impact on the organisation?

Well ironically I think efficiently working will always be very good for the environment, efficiently as in the way it is done in a plan and most effective manner. We will have benefits on both. We also have to secure work in a very busy and very competitive market although with our standard, with our ISO, with our policies, with our initiatives, with the sponsorships and a lot of variety of things, unfortunately that still cannot count as securing the work. The works secured, 8 to 9 times out of 10 are on price, which we have being lucky enough to secure the higher profile project or 2 out of them which we been working on is the Buckingham Palace and the House of Parliament. They are driven by your proposal, your initiatives and your delivery team and the way have being proposed to do the job. But there is only 60-40 against of 55-44 against cost to the proposal and a lot of that was again the engineer's solutions it is not the work. There are elements that we did not have correct ethics and policies to follow and we obviously lost them. Everyone else in the market place has an environment policy and environmental sustainability of

most of these projects is being assessed. I think there is a total ignorance behind what can be changed and affected.

Q: Can you specify which sustainable practices have implemented by your organisation?

Depending on the word sustainability, is that environmental led or is that organisation based, we have touched on training to make our company sustainable. We have new trained skilled people to address the skills shortages. As far as the environment goes we have changed our vans to brand new fleet, we got rid of our old vans and got low emission and highly technologically advanced vans, we have got fully recycled all of the waste coming back from the office, we have got fully separated waste at the side of the office, and we also keep a log of all the heavy recycled products. Everything is reported in our equipment's are efficient and we are also efficient workers. On our sites we have the ISO standards ensuring that our deliveries are suitability packaged or not packaged to reduce waste. In likes of all the products that are on the sites are packaged and the wastes are controlled. We operate in the likes of marketing but we all use recyclable instead of disposable cups we have east west connect coffee mugs. Chris our commercial manager who you are going to see next does our commercial buying not random things and being careful with every supplier on site. Our team is on constant surveillance on buying and the commercial manager manages and looks after the cost too, we keep supply chain in minimum use. We can always buy something down the road but it means it is not sustainable to that level? And are they the right standards that meet requirements? When we are not the in charge of the site we work with different other constructors and there is 15 to 20 different waste bins. We also provide recycling certificates and recycle excessive packing.

Also we do have a very long Gevity of our work force. We are very lucky across the board. We constantly review our employees. We do our SWOT analysis, one of the points is people in that we would look at development of the individual and apply objectives and indicate the targets the individual need to improve on within the work force, and this is how we maintain the wellbeing of the individuals. We also look at training and development. We also look at growth of them. We are able to look at flexibility they work into. We refurbish our offices and they have health care system in place. We also provide drinks and dispensers. We have initiatives like mango Mondays, training days and pizza Thursday every three weeks. We recently embarked on charity events where employees get to sociably contribute to our society and different charities. At

charity events we get to go away to support different charities, we felt within our managements that we ought to give back to people. So, we have recently done several events over the years such as walking events, cycling events and running events. We have donated our time and got sponsorships for these charities, this was a good team building exercise to unite our people. We raised 60 to 70 thousand but it was more about get out people involved than the money. People in generally are looking more flexibility in working so we offer flexibility.

Q: How long does your organisation practice sustainable supply chain management?

It is always there. I thinking knowing what is that fully mean and how and where we document it. We have being in ISO9001 and 14001 now 45001. Probably the last 4 years we have much better records. We have records by the nature of ISO, by having a management system that is clearly documented and records. We definitely had more recordable system for the last 4 years. But we have being practicing that for 30 years. I think if our supply chain was not sustainable we would have struggle during that time. People like to work with us because we pay the bills on time, we treat the people that we want to be treated, we have our suppliers' day and we have estimate days. So we had their feedback all the time.

Q: To what extant do you think environment dimension of SSCM is important to SMEs in the construction industry?

I think most SMEs have other factors that they cannot control like specifications, clients, main contractors and etc. Most SMEs work for main contractors. In that case the main contractor will have environment, health and safety for that size. Their policies are upon you. How much we can control that is limited. As we have multiple thinks like he do maintenance, we do projects and we do variety of small works those elements again from the point of sustainability we can always influence it. Like I said you have to have the right policies to influence them.

Q: Does construction companies generate waste and what kind of waste?

Yes, construction companies generate vast amount of waste. It is the nature of the work. Our work is varied. If we are doing a fit out of an office block that would be already completed to what we would call as a 'CAT A fit out'. So the floors and ceilings are in but we go and modify them and put the layouts the clients want. So there can be demolishing waste which will straight

away go in to the skips. So the equipments that have recently being installed will straight away go in to the skips, because the client wants a different layout. You have all our new plant that comes. Like I said we have policies, we have supply chains that we promote how everything is delivered, the ways they come on and the recyclable nature of that waste. Normally, in all the kits that come in boxes, around is polystyrene so that is what we are trying to defeat. We do not want anything to get damaged but we also do not want to have twenty layers of protection on. Because eventually all that protection material will end up in the skips. Those protections have to be recyclable. Those protections have to be recyclable. So we have that waste. We have plant replacement, where we change large equipments, generators, boilers and the likes. We ask the waste management companies to dispose of the fuel in them accurately as they can cause more damage to the environment. Apart from the fuel, they are recyclable. They are recyclable than heavy materials in CAT A. These heavy materials have reclaim value. We dispose of them for a minimum cost to someone who will reclaim them. In the industry as we refurbish buildings or anything we generate greater amount of waste.

Q: How does SMEs dispose them?

We call the waste management company to come and dispose of the waste. They provide us with 10 different bins. We still have to pay for these and again we don't use the cheapest in the market because it is not economy but sustainability. We use companies that have certificates. All of the products are then traceable and this provides company with documents that the products are recycled and where it is gone. This is how we manage sustainability. For this we are using waste management companies.

Q: To what extent do you think environmental dimension of SSCM impacts on your organisation?

I personally do not believe that people are employing our company because of our environment credentials. I think, you would be a foul not to acknowledge it. You can actually do things in environmentally better way but without spending too much money if you are economically clever enough about it. But we are still working with tiny margins and we are dictated in market place about working with very larger amount of clients. It is still about the price. They are our employer so they know that we have a good reputation, they can look at our website and they are

our employer as we are the right credential so we must be environmentally correct. There is a strong social pressure on us to make sure that we do something good for the environment.

Q: What were the barriers your organisation faced when implementing sustainable supply chain management? (any internal barriers like financial or organisational resources, external barriers like lack of knowledge and competition)

Well it is just education isn't it? It is very hard. Change is always profound. Using different suppliers because they have different rights, policy and procedure in place to sustained packaging and equipment, which are recyclable, or has small carbon footprints. The barriers are to change and getting the right people involved and it is also about understanding the process. We have different champions for different elements in business. We have environment and health and safety champion who look at those aspects. They help to train and make aware the people and achieve our objective. All of those people cost money when you have greater level of management, understand, education, policies and procedures. We often use same ideas like what a cost should be. But now we have more people with great ideas than before to tackle waste and other problems at work. We now have environmental manager, health and safety manager and more. We also have more people on site to tackle waste. We are efficient with our work and carry out the legislation. The legislation is not clear on some point and it is not easy follow. These are some of the barriers.

Q: How did you overcome those barriers?

We have a good reputation and we are perceived as a company that is trying to bring in new technology and embrace new ideas. Like I said before a lot of our procedures and working techniques are less labour and less material intensive or likely to remove elements of human waste and material waste. This brings in efficient most of this is driven by our pro-active team trying to make changes. We are also trying to understand the new technology and we show these through social media and our website, by case studies. It's a combination of things to show that you are doing things and moving forward sustainable through a honest company, brexit is another massive minefield of losing a lot of the work force are actually diverse we have very heavy contingence of Romanian and polish workers. But we do what we can by maintaining

staff, offices, training, health and safety, benefit, graduate schemes and apprentices all help for our sustainability.

Q: How did you overcome from the understanding barrier of implementation of SSCM?

We overcame from them by finding the right specialist. We have taken one consultant and a guide full time. In regards to the environment and ISO we have a consultant to guide and nature us throughout that. We have taken more resource in regards to HR specialist. We can always refer to the Reviews. More about bring in the specialism and this will bring in new ideas

Q: From your perspective, how would explain sustainable supply chain management?

The word sustainability covers everything from physically making sure that the suppliers and companies that working for you are wants to work for you down to the fact that they have policy and procedures in line with environment sustainability. This is a very broad question, we have been talking about it for the past few minutes, and every question that you ask is almost the same question but with a very slight different answer. SSCM is about right companies, right policies and right procedures to protect the environment. It is everything we discussed before.

Q: Can you specify which strategies your organisation is using to mange waste responsibly and continuously that attempts to prevent and reduce the production of waste?

We have standard environment procedures within our ISO. We distribute it to all our supply chain and our subcontractors. We ask them and review their procedures. We operate supply chain database that ensure our supply chain is regularly assessed and that we have correct element. We provide feedback for them. Our clients and contractors are constantly assessing us, we get provided with feedback, which help us improve. We operate KPI in the likes of we ask them to assess us and they ask us to assess them and feedback each other in a positive manner. We analyze our SWAT analysis in legal requirement.

Q: You said you have objectives, can you mention few objectives?

One of them are SWAT analysis, here is copy of SWAT. It is objective plan for each element. Reduction of emission and root planning and tracking system on our vans, the copy I handed you show I wrote the planning and tracking system. The copy provides you with this information. So

now we have 2year old van rather than having 5-year-old van, the new van provides lower emission in the likes of new engine. Best environment fleet composition for vehicles. Purchasing, replacing and leasing with EURO 6. Encourage environmental friendly driving this is achieved by tracking system. This is taken forward objectively for SWAT analysis part of our ISO this process covers many different areas. All of this is part of our integration management system these is again is part of ISO which covers the quality, environmental and occupational health. This is sign document, which interlink objective in plans, these are pretty standard it's what we do and how we do it to improve ourselves. We also have suggestion box in the reception, which we look at every month to have a look at and take the points forward.

Q: How long have you been with your main supplier?

We don't have a main supplier. For example you can look at 'Net locks' who supplies us with electrical accessories. John O' Hamlet opened up the business- founder of the business and family that owns 75% of the business till this day. Net locks were the first one to provide with screw fix or a cable to the business. We still heavily utilize them but when I mean we heavily utilise them we limit to 4-5 main suppliers. There is a snap shot of our supply chain, this is only one page that I have printed out for you to have a look at, we have whole book with 154 suppliers that we regularly use. Our work is very diverse, there is no one place that we use from. For example working on office the carpet, door fittings, lightings, cables, they all come from different supplier providing large heavy-duty cables. You Cleveland cable for example they are the best in the world but when we did Buckingham palace they did not have the credential to actually supply the cable for that. Buckingham palace has the initiative to have British to credential, so we had to go on to another supplier who provides this, but we are still using some for the first supplier we used when we opened the company.

Q: What driving factors do you think encouraged your organisation to implement sustainable supply chain management? (any internal drivers like corporate strategy, organisational characteristics and resources? Or any external drivers like legislations, media and competitive advantage?)

We got a strong social believe that sustainability talking about environment is important for all of us. So we have initiatives for everyone like how can we do things cleaner, how can we do

things better. Like I said we support our guidelines with flexibility to try new ideas, to create new concepts, process and reduce man-hours on site in order to reduce waste. We have fabrication shops, we have initiatives, ideas, and different processes and police to try and reduce that. We have specialist to control physical waste generation. Our work is high profiled and people tend to follow trend. Hence that is why we have consultants and specialist to bring in and promote sustainability at workplace.

Q: What is the process that your organisation followed when implementing sustainable supply chain management?

We have used consultants to understand the SSCM, assess the waste we generate and how to develop effective SSCM.

We have used lot of standard templates from ISO standard management. There are straightforward guidelines and things like environmental management 14001. They give you clear guidelines like what we need to have in place and templates for that. We use specialist to develop those to suite our business. We have developed an environmental policy including the environment management objectives. As you can see ensuring the integration of the environmental management system into the organisation's business process, ensuring that the resources needed for the environmental management system are available, communicating the importance of effective environmental management are some of the objectives mentioned in the policy. This policy is reviewed annually. We made sure that the top management are involved and committed for these policies.

The consultants made the budgets to hire specialist to implement the environmental management system. It was challenging as most of us did not have the understanding about sustainable supply chain, environment management or ISO 14001. So we hired the right people and it was also a challenge. We followed websites and asked from our main contractors about the right consultants and specialist.

We have consultants on site to help us and we ask questions such as what will benefit the environment and promote guidelines through ISO. You can have a look at this information on the

Internet and it's a click away. Analysis and SWATS are driven with benefiting the business and this is a learning path.

As the next step these hired specialist reviewed the government legislations like waste disposal legislation. Then they identified our impacts on the environment as we generate a certain amount of waste. Then we conducted series of training session for our top managers and employees. So we all were in the same line.

Then we had regular checks and reviews to ensure the objectives are achieved and we are in the right track. If we were doing it inefficiently the consultants and specialists were guiding us.

Q: Have you ever published your successful story?

No I have never published but we are not research based body tend to promote things on our website which then promotes our work ethics and this also gives influences our company. Everything is done on our own resource and time and finding. And no one has actually come up with the idea that this piece on sustainability is missing on your website until then I will for now continue to write about my previous work I carried out on. Our website is carried out by Louie and I will wait for your piece to publish and then maybe I will put them up.

Q: What is your advice to the SMEs in the construction industry who is trying to implement SSCM?

I don't know what stages they need to follow at the end of the day the sustainability is through their business so; the promotion of it is and to looking to expand where they can actually make a difference. Innovation takes a very long time. But if there is innovation it will change the culture for example if Amazon changes the boxes for every single packaging. You get to educate their mind set.

Appendix 8: NVIVO Coding Sample

Appendix 9: Enablers in the Findings and Literature

(Source: [Saeed and Kersten, 2019](#))

Internal drivers	
Corporate strategy	top management commitment
Organisational characteristics	the position of the supply chain
Organisational resources	human resource
External drivers	
Social pressure	media and public pressure
Regulatory pressure	government legislation
Market pressure	competitive advantage

Table 6: The drivers to implement SSCM (Source: compiled by the author)

(Source: [Saeed and Kersten, 2019](#))